

**Developing an effective training evaluation
framework for manufacturing organisations
in Vietnam**

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland for the award of Doctor of Business Administration

Director of Studies: Professor Eleri Jones

Assessor: Dr. Mona Althonayan

Supervisor 1: Dr. Wilson Ozuem

Student name: Thuy Anh Tran Vu

Student ID: B00316285

Words count: 65,767 words

London, 19th July 2021

TABLE OF CONTENT

LIST OF TABLES	7
LIST OF FIGURES	8
TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS	9
DECLARATION	10
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	11
ABSTRACT	12
CHAPTER ONE- INTRODUCTION	13
1.1. Research Background and Context	14
1.1.1. Human Resource Overview	14
1.1.2. Importance of Human Resource	15
1.1.3. Training overview	15
1.1.4. The importance of training.....	16
1.1.5. Current training evaluation in research.....	17
1.1.6. Current training evaluation in practice.....	18
1.1.7. Purpose of training evaluation	18
1.2. The need for this research	20
1.3. Rationale (justification) of the study.....	22
1.4. Research Aim.....	24
1.5. Research Objectives.....	24
1.6. Research questions.....	24
1.7. Research problem and justification.....	25
1.8. Brief Description of the Research Methodology	27
1.9. Scope of the research	29
1.10. Rationale of the research.....	Error! Bookmark not defined.
1.11. The thesis structure	32
1.12. Summary	35
CHAPTER 2- LITERATURE REVIEW	37
2.1. Introduction.....	37
2.2. Overview of Training.....	38
2.2.1. What is training	38
2.2.2. The importance of training in the workplace.....	39
2.2.3. Differences between training, learning, development and education.....	41
2.3. Different types of training.....	43

2.3.1.	Technical training	43
2.3.2.	Quality training.....	44
2.3.3.	Skill training	44
2.3.4.	Soft- skills training	44
2.3.5.	Professional training and legal training	44
2.3.6.	Team training.....	45
2.3.7.	Managerial training.....	45
2.3.8.	Safety training	45
2.4.	The benefits of training	46
2.5.	The challenges of training.....	47
2.6.	The training process	50
2.7.	Implementing a training program	52
2.8.	Training Strategies	52
2.9.	Pre-training arrangement process	53
2.10.	Impact of training on organisational needs	55
2.11.	Training and employee motivation	56
2.12.	Overview of Evaluation	58
2.12.1.	What is the evaluation.....	59
2.12.2.	Strategies associated with Training Evaluation	60
2.12.2.1.	<i>Cognitive Learning outcomes</i>	60
2.12.2.2.	<i>Verbal knowledge</i>	61
2.12.2.3.	<i>Measurement implications of verbal knowledge</i>	62
2.12.2.4.	<i>Knowledge organisation</i>	63
2.12.2.5.	<i>Measurement Implications of Knowledge organisation</i>	64
2.12.2.6.	<i>Cognitive Strategies</i>	65
2.12.3.	Different types of evaluation.....	65
2.12.4.	The purposes and benefits of evaluation	67
2.12.5.	Evaluation process	67
2.12.5.1.	<i>Planning</i>	68
2.12.5.2.	<i>Implementation – formative and process evaluation</i>	68
2.12.5.3.	<i>Completion – summative, outcome and impact evaluation</i>	69
2.12.5.4.	<i>Dissemination and reporting</i>	69
2.12.6.	Approaches to evaluation	69
2.12.6.1.	<i>Participatory evaluation</i>	70
2.12.6.2.	<i>Empowerment evaluation</i>	70
2.12.7.	Evaluation methodology	71

2.12.7.1. <i>Quantitative method</i>	71
2.12.7.2. <i>Qualitative method</i>	72
2.12.7.3. <i>Mixed method (both qualitative and quantitative methods)</i>	72
2.13. Evaluation of Training effectiveness	72
2.13.1. Training effectiveness.....	72
2.13.2. Training evaluation.....	72
2.13.3. Levels of Training Evaluation.....	75
2.13.4. The benefits of evaluating training effectiveness	85
2.13.5. Challenges of training evaluation	86
2.14. Training evaluation frameworks	87
2.14.1. CIRO framework of evaluation.....	87
2.14.2. CIPP Model of Evaluation	88
2.14.3. Kirkpatrick’s Model	89
2.14.4. Phillips’s ROI Model	92
2.14.5. Comparison of studied frameworks/models.....	94
2.15. Current scenario of training evaluation in manufacturing sector in Vietnam	95
2.15.1. Overview of manufacturing sector in Vietnam	95
2.15.2. Training evaluation in manufacturing sector in Vietnam.....	98
2.16. Conclusion	216
CHAPTER 3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	101
3.1. Introduction.....	102
3.2. Research Philosophy	103
3.2.1. Pragmatism	103
3.2.2. Positivism.....	104
3.2.3. Realism	105
3.2.4. Interpretivism.....	106
3.2.5. Justification for the paradigms and methodology	108
3.3. Research Approach (Deductive versus inductive approach).....	108
3.3.1. Inductive approach.....	108
3.3.2. Deductive approach	109
3.3.3. Justification for choosing inductive approach.....	110
3.4. Strategies.....	111
3.4.1. Documentary materials	111
3.4.2. Observation	112
3.4.3. Questionnaires.....	112
3.4.4. Survey	113

3.4.5. Interview (Qualitative data collection method).....	114
3.5. Choices (Research Methods)	115
3.5.1. Qualitative versus Quantitative methods	115
3.5.2. Mixed methods.....	117
3.5.2.1. <i>Practical use of ‘mixed methods’ in exploratory design</i>	117
3.5.2.2. <i>Justification for implementing mixed methods</i>	118
3.6. Time Horizon	119
3.7. Data collection and Analysis.....	119
3.7.1. Justification for quantitative data collection (survey)	119
3.7.2. Justification for Qualitative data collection (Interview)	120
3.8. Population and Sampling	122
3.9. Pilot study	124
3.10. Delimitations of the study	126
3.11. Ethical Considerations	126
3.12. Conclusion	128
CHAPTER 4- INTRODUCTION TO THE CASES	129
4.1. Introduction.....	129
4.2. Overview of Parent Companies.....	136
4.3. CASE 1: VARD VUNG TAU LTD. COMPANY.....	131
4.3.1. Business Overview.....	131
4.3.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights.....	132
4.3.3. Training overview	133
4.3.4. Training Evaluation	133
4.4. CASE 2: BLUESCOPE VIETNAM COMPANY	134
4.4.1. Business Overview.....	134
4.4.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights.....	135
4.4.3. Training overview	136
4.4.4. Training Evaluation	137
4.5. CASE 3: BAKER HUGHES VIETNAM LIMITED.....	138
4.5.1. Business Overview.....	138
4.5.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights.....	138
4.5.3. Training overview	139
4.5.4. Training Evaluation	140
4.6. Conclusion	140
CHAPTER 5- DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS	141
5.1. Introduction.....	142

5.2. Quantitative data analysis collection.....	143
5.3. Qualitative data analysis	187
5.4. Conclusion	204
CHAPTER 6- DISCUSSION	205
6.1. Introduction.....	206
6.2. Discussion about demography of the participants	206
6.3. Nature and type of training in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations.....	207
6.4. Preparation for training program in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations	208
6.5. Effectiveness of training program in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations	210
6.6. Evaluation of training program at Vietnamese manufacturing organizations.....	212
6.7. Benefit of evaluation process.....	214
6.8. Gaps in training evaluation in the manufacturing organizations.....	215
6.9. The proposed model.....	220
6.9.1. Kirkpatrick's model revisited.....	221
6.9.2. The proposed model.....	221
CHAPTER 7- CONCLUSION.....	227
7.1. Introduction.....	228
7.2. Conclusion	228
7.3. Linking objectives with the findings.....	229
7.4. Linking research questions with the findings.....	230
7.5. Recommendations.....	247
7.5.1. Interactive training sessions	248
7.5.2. Encouraging employee feedback in training evaluation	249
7.5.3. Participatory approach to training evaluation	250
7.6. Contribution of the study	250
7.7. Scope for future research	255
REFERENCES.....	258
Appendix 1- Survey Questionnaire	278
Appendix 2- Interview Questions for Managers	283

LIST OF TABLES

Table 2-1: The differences between learning, training, development and education.....	42
Table 2-2: Benefits of training in the workplace	47
Table 2-3: CIRO Training evaluation framework.....	87
Table 2-4: Kirkpatrick's Model of training evaluation	90
Table 2-5: Strengths and Limitations of Phillips's ROI Model	94
Table 2-6: Comparison of four training evaluation models.....	95
Table 2-7: Growth rates and shares of manufacturing sub-sectors in Vietnam from 1995 to 2010.....	96
Table 3-1: Advantages and disadvantages of conducting survey	113
Table 3-2: Advantages and disadvantages of conducting interview.....	115
Table 4-2: Overview of Vard, BlueScope and Baker Hughes.....	129
Table 5-1: Gender	143
Table 5-2: Age Group.....	144
Table 5-3: Tenure in the organisation.....	144
Table 5-4: Department/area of work.....	146
Table 5-5: Frequency of training program	147
Table 5-6: Primary reason to participate in training	150
Table 5-7: Type of training mostly imparted	151
Table 5-8: Whether use of appropriate ICT is made in training.....	153
Table 5-9: Whether training needs analysis (TNA) is conducted	154
Table 5-10: The objectives of training were clearly defined	156
Table 5-11: Whether participation and interaction are encouraged.....	157
Table 5-12: The content was organised and easy to follow	159
Table 5-13: Whether the training modules distributed were helpful	160
Table 5-14: Application of training to work.....	161
Table 5-15: Whether the trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics	163
Table 5-16: The trainer was well-prepared.....	164
Table 5-17: The training objectives were met.....	165
Table 5-18: The time allotted for the training is sufficient.....	166
Table 5-19: Whether the training rooms and facilities are adequate and comfortable.....	168
Table 5-20: Sharing the learning with co-workers.....	169
Table 5-21: Training for knowledge enhancement and skills improvement.....	170
Table 5-22: Training and improvement in work performance.....	171
Table 5-23: Training and employee motivation.....	173
Table 5-24: Recommending to training to others.....	174
Table 5-25: Feeling on implementing knowledge to work.....	175
Table 5-26: Whether systematic approach to training (SAT) is followed.....	176
Table 5-27: Seeking employee feedback with regards to training effectiveness	178
Table 5-28: Whether employee feedback is valued and implemented.....	179
Table 5-29: Participatory approach to training evaluation	181
Table 5-30: Feeling empowered after training evaluation	182
Table 5-31: Level of satisfaction with the trainer.....	185
Table 5-32: Level of satisfaction with the training program.....	186
Table 5-33: Interviewees participating this research.....	189

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1-1: Structure of the Thesis	35
Figure 2-1: Four basic steps of the Training Process	50
Figure 2-2: The training cycle	51
Figure 2-3: Process of training evaluation	74
Figure 2-4: CIPP Evaluation Model	88
Figure 2-5: Phillips's ROI process	93
Figure 2-6: Manufacturing output by ownership from 1995 to 2014	97
Figure 2-7: The proposed model of training evaluation.....	223
Figure 3-1: Research Onion	103
Figure 3-2: Inductive approach.....	111
Figure 5-1: Gender.....	143
Figure 5-2: Age Group	144
Figure 5-3: Tenure in the organisation	145
Figure 5-4: Department/area of work.....	146
Figure 5-5: Frequency of training program	147
Figure 5-6: Primary reason to participate in training	151
Figure 5-7: Type of training mostly imparted	152
Figure 5-8: Whether use of appropriate ICT is made in training	153
Figure 5-9: Whether training needs analysis (TNA) is conducted	155
Figure 5-10: The objectives of training were clearly defined	156
Figure 5-11: Whether participation and interaction are encouraged	158
Figure 5-12: The content was organised and easy to follow	159
Figure 5-13: Whether the training modules distributed were helpful	160
Figure 5-14: Application of training to work	162
Figure 5-15: Whether the trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics	163
Figure 5-16: The trainer was well-prepared.....	164
Figure 5-17: The training objectives were met.....	166
Figure 5-18: The time allotted for the training is sufficient	167
Figure 5-19: Whether the training rooms and facilities are adequate and comfortable.....	168
Figure 5-20: Sharing the learning with co-workers	169
Figure 5-21: Training for knowledge enhancement and skills improvement.....	171
Figure 5-22: Training and improvement in work performance.....	172
Figure 5-23: Training and employee motivation.....	173
Figure 5-24: Recommending to training to others.....	174
Figure 5-25: Feeling on implementing knowledge to work.....	175
Figure 5-26: Whether systematic approach to training (SAT) is followed.....	177
Figure 5-27: Seeking employee feedback with regards to training effectiveness	178
Figure 5-28: Whether employee feedback is valued and implemented.....	180
Figure 5-29: Participatory approach to training evaluation.....	181
Figure 5-30: Feeling empowered after training evaluation.....	183
Figure 5-31: Level of satisfaction with the trainer	186
Figure 5-32: Level of satisfaction with the training program.....	187

TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS

AOP	Actual organisational performance
B2B	Business to business
CAD	Computer-aided design
CAM	Computer aided manufacturing
CBT	Computer-based training
CIM	Computer-integrated manufacturing
CIPP	Context, Input, Process, Product
CIRO	Context, Input, Reaction, Outcome
CRM	Customer relationship management
EBS	Engineered Building Solutions
EOP	Expected organisational performance
FDI	Foreign Direct Investment
GE	General Electric
HR	Human resource
HRD	Human resource development
HRM	Human resource management
ICT	Information and communication technology
ISO	International organisation for standardization
KPI	Key performance index
OD	Organisational development
ROI	Return on investment
SAT	Systematic Approach to Training
SHRM	Strategic human resource management
SLEPT	Socio-cultural, Legal, Economic, Political, Technological
SMART	Specific, measurable, achievable, reliable, time-bound
T&D	Training and development
TNA	Training needs analysis

DECLARATION

I, THUY ANH TRAN VU, declare that this research thesis is my own unaided work. It is submitted in partial fulfilment for the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Business Administration at the University of the West of Scotland.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Conducting this research titled “**Developing an effective training evaluation framework for Vietnamese manufacturing organisations**” was a challenging, yet an interesting journey. It helped me to enhance my knowledge with regards to the theme chosen for investigation including development of personal skills.

However, successfully completion of this thesis would not have been possible without the valuable guidance and feedback of my supervisors, Professor Eleri Jones and Dr. Mona Althonayan. The moral support, feedback and timely assistance that was received from my Supervisors is incredible that helped to add value to this research. Hence, I own my sincere gratitude to my Supervisors under whose guidance I could complete the thesis with confidence and submit it successfully.

I would also like to thank all managers and employees of VARD Vung Tau Ltd, BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam Limited who took part in the surveys and interviews and shared their thoughts, opinions and ideas with me. Their contributions are significantly valuable to this research.

Finally, I owe my gratitude to my parents and family members who encouraged me to pursue higher education.

I also want to extend my gratitude to the Almighty on whom I have sincere belief.

ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to understand the nature of training evaluation being undertaken by the human resource department of manufacturing organisations in Vietnam based on which the aim was to develop an effective training evaluation framework for the manufacturing organisations. The methodology followed to conduct the research was exploratory, the inductive approach and the mixed methods to data collection. Quantitative data was collected from 372 employees of Vard Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam and Baker Hughes Vietnam. In addition, qualitative data was collected from three managers using semi-structured and included open-ended questions.

Findings indicate that the manufacturing organisations conduct systematic training based on the knowledge gaps and skills requirement of the employees. The HRM departments also implemented specific training evaluation frameworks and models, however, apparent gaps existed in their overall evaluation process. The key deficiencies identified in their evaluation approaches were lack of employee inclusion, feedback sharing and participation in the evaluation process. This study develops a strategic framework for training evaluation based on the Kirkpatrick's training evaluation framework, aiming at manufacturing organisations in Vietnam. It is believed that the framework will help Human Resources (HR) Management Executives to develop and implement and consistent training evaluation processes that enable the entire training function to be optimised. This study is also expected to encourage more researchers from Vietnam and other countries to study the aspect of HR issues in Vietnam, especially corporate training. Furthermore, the experience of developing the framework gained in this research may assist future researchers when undertaking training evaluation in other business contexts.

CHAPTER ONE:

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background and Context

1.1.1. Human Resource Overview

Resource implies “*a source*”, which can be used when required. While each and every resource has a starting point and an end, “human resource” implies human skills, ideas, knowledge, and aptitudes (Burgess and Connell, 2008). While other resources depreciate with time, human resources are subject to appreciation with experience and time. Appropriate human resources ensure that an organisation possesses the right quantity and quality of people at the right time and place to carry out the daily operations. Based on extant literature, HR resources refer to the total knowledge, creative abilities, skills, values and attitudes, talents, and approaches in an individual (Holbeche, 2011). These resources are used in a manner to reap the maximum benefits out of it, and then it is known as “Human Resource Management” (HRM).

HRM is an organisational function that deals with people-related issues such as compensation and benefits, recruitment, organisational development, performance management, wellness, safety, communication, employee motivation, training and development (Qadeer *et al.*, 2011). The purpose of HRM is to achieve maximum HR development, good working environment, and constructive relationship between employees and employer. Budhwar and Debrah (2013) consider HRM to be strategic approach to employee motivation and people development and gaining their commitment to gain their best contribution to organisational success, while meeting their own needs and aspirations. HRM is also a pervasive force, individually oriented, action-oriented, future-focused, and integrative in nature (Hoffmann, 2014). As a comprehensive function, HRM makes possible for employees to effectively and productively contribute to the overall direction of the company and achieve the organisational goals and objectives.

1.1.2. Importance of Human Resource

Proper management of human resources increase their dignity by gratifying their social needs. This is made possible by maintaining the right balance between the job seekers and vacancies available, according to their qualification and experiences (Buller and McEvoy, 2012). The importance of HRM lies in providing appropriate and productive employment, which is likely to provide them with psychological satisfaction. HRM maximises resource utilisation in an effective way and paying compensation in proportion to their contribution (Hong *et al.*, 2012). The importance of HRM also lies in providing a healthy working atmosphere to the employees that promote teamwork, mutual co-operation, and trust. The HR department provides employees with opportunities for career development; thereby increasing their self-esteem and motivation. The HR provides employees opportunities for training and development, improving knowledge, skills and competencies to enhance performance (Sarvanitis *et al.*, 2016). HRM helps an organisation to achieve its goals by aligning the organisational goals and objectives with the personal goals and objectives of the employees.

1.1.3. Training overview

Training has long been recognized as a key strategy for human resources development and as the best insurance policy for an organization against all kinds of inevitable changes and arising needs in the future (Pineda, 2010).

In the literature, there are many different definitions of training. According to Flippo (1984), training is the act of increasing the skills of an employee for doing a particular job. Goldstein (1993:53) defines training in more detail as “*a systematic acquisition of skills, rules, concepts or attitudes that results in improved performance in the working environment*”. Chiaburu and Tekleab (2005:29) see training as “*the planned intervention that is designed to enhance the determinants of individual job performance*”. Training is also clarified as the area where

organizational, industrial and individual development can match, and where human resource and organization growth get blended together (Sundarajan, 2007).

Despite the different approaches, these definitions of training in the literature share two common points: (1) training is the systematic acquisition of knowledge, skills, and behaviours; (2) the goal of training is the improvement of both individual and organizational performance (Goldstein and Ford, 2002), which leads to a strategic competitiveness of the organization (Schraeder, 2009).

1.1.4. The importance of training

The importance of training in the workplace has been long-recognized. Among the three main capital of an organisation –Men, Machine and Material, men are the most valuable resource (Daniels, 2003). This is the reason why organisations spend a huge investment on their human resources, especially training activities. Major organisations annually spend about 2.5 percent of their payroll, which equals several billions of dollars on training (Steensma and Groeneveld, 2010). It is clear that investing in employees' training is a wise business choice that not only yields a significant return on investment but also saves an organisation from having to hire more experienced employees outright.

Training is a critical factor in ensuring that a temporary hire is truly an investment rather than an expense. Recent researches consistently show that companies that fail to train their employees are more than three times as likely to lose them (Dirkes, 2014). To be justified as the most powerful activity among many organisational interventions, training must be therefore managed as a frontline business activity and received sufficient investment (Guzzo *et al.*, 1985).

1.1.5. Current training evaluation in research

According to Kumpikaitė (2007), training evaluation is a systematic process of data collection with regards to the effectiveness and success of training programs. Teasley *et al.* (2008) explain that constructive evaluation takes place when the specific outcome measures are theoretically related to the proposed learning objectives. Evaluation is therefore carried out to find the answer to two alternative questions; whether the objectives of the training were accomplished (learning issues) and whether the achievement of these objectives results in increased performance on the job (issues related to transfer) (Hurn, 2014). While both questions are crucial, Kumpikaitė (2015) emphasises that the most central issue of training evaluation is whether the trainees have assimilated the knowledge covered in the training. Roughton and Crutchfield (2016) argued that evaluation needs to be carried out with the sole purpose to determine whether the training outcomes have been accomplished. However, existing literature studies do not offer any concrete conceptual framework to guide the organisations about how to evaluate the learning effectiveness.

Huge investment in training activities requires evaluation to determine and ascertain the effectiveness of training programs (Bramley and Kitson, 1994; Cheng and Ho, 2001; Beardwell, 2004). Training evaluation can be described as *“a systematic and impartial collection of data and analysing information for managers and all other interested parties about a training programme which can be used to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of particular training measures as a way of achieving organizational objectives, implementing policy and promoting organizational learning”* (Raab *et al.*, 1991:20). James and Roffe (2000:12) provide a simplified explanation of evaluation as a *“comparing the actual and real with the predicted or promised”*. Sharing the same viewpoint, Saad and Mat (2011:17) see training evaluation as *“a measurement which indicates whether the cost incurred in design matches the associated benefits of implementing training program”*.

1.1.6. Current training evaluation in practice

In actual practice, training evaluation establishes the actual framework for developing instruments. It integrates the individual training programs on the basis of the training type, evaluation method, and the best method to execute the evaluation. Training evaluation, in general, comprises of few steps and each step involves explicit data categories (Piwowar and Thiel, 2014), as follows:

Describing the output- Descriptive data are in the form of outputs relating to the training programs and the trainees and include demographic information.

Pre-training assessment- This stage discloses the past experiences of the trainees/participants, current skills and competencies, and their learning needs (Passmore and Velez, 2015). It also includes the anticipated application of acquired learning gained from training.

Post-assessment (response)- this stage addresses the reactions of the participants with regards to the training experience. For instance, the quality of the training material, and skills of the trainer, the learning context, duration of the training program, and general satisfaction may include post-assessment responses (Passmore and Velez, 2015).

Post-assessment (learning) – this is a self-evaluation stage of the knowledge or skills gained by the trainees, and their expected learning application.

Follow up – follow up is a process that includes various methods to evaluate the training outcomes and its effects over an extended period of time.

1.1.7. Purpose of training evaluation

The main purpose of training evaluation is to gain information regarding the effectiveness of the training program, its delivery, and whether it has achieved its objectives. Evaluation of training involves the application of specific methodologies, tools and frameworks to improve the outcomes of future training (Kumpikaitė, 2007).

However, different authors and human resource practitioners have different views and perceptions about training evaluation. For instance, Pineda (2010) considered the purpose of evaluation as justifying or rationalising the existing of the training department and providing substantiation of cost-benefit to the organisation. Meanwhile, other researchers such as Saks and Burke (2012) pointed out that the basic purpose of the evaluation is to examine participants' reactions in terms of their learning, satisfaction, and behavioural development. Topno (2012) viewed the purpose of evaluation as judging the quality and worth of the training program so as to effect improvements and/or acknowledge the benefits yielded by training. It also relates to the understanding of what trainers suppose should be done, and what trainers do in actual practice seem to vary noticeably.

Several researchers such as Shenge (2014) and Aluko and Shonubi (2014) opposed the above ideas on the purpose of evaluation, arguing that the purpose of any evaluation depends on several factors wherein the main purpose is (i) feedback (linking outcomes of learning with training objectives and providing a form of quality control), intervention (in which the evaluation outcomes influence the context in which it is taking place), research (as certain the relationship between training, learning, and transfer of learning to job) control (making use of evaluation to link training with organisational activities, and give consideration to cost-effectiveness), and power games (manoeuvre evaluative data for organisational politics).

Aluko and Shonubi (2014) consider the importance of evaluation with regards to feedback and the resultant issue of control. These authors consider that it is important to make a decision as to whom and how evaluation feedback would be given. Evaluators should be acquainted with the main purposes of evaluation once it is initiated; however, this may be because they have a common perception that the evaluation purpose is to produce a certain data set, or because they have ascertained the purpose the client desires the evaluation to have. Kirwan (2016) argued that the recognition of unexpected side effects of a training program may be an important

purpose of evaluation. Farmer *et al.* (2017) pointed out that it was often difficult to establish the evaluation purpose, as there may be several, moreover, the evaluator may not be able to determine the real purpose of evaluation until the end of the exercise.

1.2. The need for this research

One of the critical reasons for the significant growth of Vietnam's economy as well as the manufacturing sector after Renovation policy is its human capital. The 90 million Vietnamese are young, with 65 percent of the population being less than 40 years old. This youthful population is motivated to work and eager to learn and develop professional skills. Furthermore, Vietnam is now in a period known as the *golden population structure*, which means that there is one dependent person for every two-working people. Hence, these demographic conditions create an abundance of the labour force.

In order to have an effective training program in the workplace, an organization needs to follow its training process systematically. In the training process, training evaluation is the final step which helps the organization to justify the effectiveness of training programs. Training evaluation plays as the critical link between current training and future programs in order to continuously improve the organizational training process. Training evaluation is far beyond an assessment of training effectiveness and should be seen as a strategic tool for development (Brinkerhoff, 2006). Despite its importance, evaluating training has not received adequate attention in the workplace. Various research studies on training evaluation provide evidence that training evaluation is the weakest and most underdeveloped aspect of training (Iyer *et al.*, 2009). Being an HR officer and internal-auditor in a large-scale manufacturing organization in Vietnam, the author has witnessed the fact that training programs are evaluated occasionally without any systematic method. The under-developed or missing stage of training evaluation within the training process is confronting organizations from optimising their training programs.

The main purpose of this thesis is to examine the current scenario of training activities and training evaluation in a focused context of its Vietnamese manufacturing sector. It looks into the process of training from start to finish, from pre-training period to post-training, and from training purposes to training results. It also sets out to explore the roles of companies' management, their employees, and the training providers in transforming classroom knowledge into work performance. This is achieved by exploring training-related activities inside a set of selected manufacturing companies in Vietnam. This is also a stepping stone, planned to supply data for identifying the factors that influence the relationship between business training and companies' performance.

The purpose of the research is also to develop a strategic refined framework for training evaluation, aimed at manufacturing organizations in Vietnam. The proposed framework is based on Kirkpatrick's four-level method of training evaluation and suggested adjustments from valuable researchers. With the intention of embodying all aspects of training evaluation into ONE framework, it provides the general analytical tool for training evaluation to reveal both training outcomes and spot the opportunities for further improvement in training management.

Some recent research shows that Vietnamese employers clearly value training and appreciate the impact that training can have for their enterprise. Training programmes are offered staff regardless of positions and the training needs are also defined clearly according to the organizational and individual objectives. However, the training evaluation process is mostly ignored or under-developed. The training programs at the workplace are assumed to bring positive impacts to the organization. The research carried out by Anh Phan (2008) has examined the training evaluation process in several companies in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam's economic centre. From her research and the author's personal experience as HR Executive in a manufacturing company, there are some significant issues in training evaluation in

Vietnamese manufacturing enterprises. It is, therefore, necessary to conduct empirical research and identify the existing issues in the area of training evaluation in Vietnamese manufacturing organisations and give appropriate recommendations to overcome the identified issues.

This is a common situation for most manufacturing organizations in Vietnam. Therefore, the initial purpose of this research is to enhance the awareness of training evaluation benefits in the workplace. By doing so, this study provides a critical review of training evaluation in terms of its benefits, challenges, and various common models of training evaluation in the literature and business context. The scenario of training evaluation in the Vietnamese manufacturing sector is also examined through several case study organizations. More importantly, a strategic training evaluation framework was proposed based on Kirkpatrick's four-stage model of evaluation, which is considered the most widely-studied and adopted model in both research and business context (Alyahya, 2013). The proposed framework is expected to be applied by HR Management Executives to design and implement rigorous and coherent training evaluation processes that enable the entire training function to be optimised.

There is an emerging need to identify whether the training evaluation framework followed in Vietnamese organisations is effective enough to meet the needs and objectives of the training and whether the ROI (return on investment) in training is adequate. It is also crucial to find out whether the evaluation methods are effective enough to measure the desirable changes it has brought in the learners' work performance.

1.3. Rationale of the study

Training, like any other organisational activity or human resource function, requires financial investment, time and efforts (Ghufli, 2012). Training is a critical investment in the form of a strategy that is undertaken to achieve a range of benefits and outcomes, which could be for both, employees and organisation. Training is an investment that leads to employees'

performance improvement, motivation, provides scope for career development, job satisfaction, and commitment towards the organisational goals (Thakore, 2013). It also helps to reduce employee turnover intention and thereby retention. From an organisational perspective, training is an investment that leads to increased organisational productivity, increased market growth, increased profitability and competitive edge (Bulut and Culha, 2010). However, often manufacturing organisations fail to understand the importance of evaluating their training programs in terms of its effectiveness for yielding beneficial outcomes for the employees and the organisation.

Manufacturing organisations are generally involved in the production of goods by converting raw materials as inputs into finished products as outputs. Large manufacturing firms are usually involved in large- scale production and therefore the likelihood of workplace injuries, accidents and casualties are more (Martinez *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, the need to meet quality requirements and ensure the goods is produced in conformance with client specifications, zero defects, and timely delivery of client orders is a must (Phan *et al.*, 2016). This makes employee training essential and equally essential to understand the effectiveness of training. The human resource managers although invest heavily in employee training, they often neglect conducting an appropriate negotiation for the training programs. Similar is the case with Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, which often pay inadequate attention to the evaluation of the training programs (Nguyen *et al.*, 2011). These companies may fail to implement an appropriate training evaluation framework, or the evaluation may infrequent enough to identify the effectiveness of every training program.

Failure to evaluate the effectiveness of the training programs in an adequate manner makes it difficult for manufacturing organisations to measure the return on investment in training. The HRM fails to identify whether the training programs have been designed and/or customised according to the employees' needs (Nguyen *et al.*, 2011). Lack of appropriate training

evaluation also makes it difficult for the HRM to recognise the change in employees' attitude and behaviour after the training and the extent to which they are able to implement the learning gained from training at work (Van Tuan and Nguyen, 2012). As a result, the gaps in the training programs or existing loopholes cannot be identified; neither the potential outcomes of the training are measured. Therefore, the HRM department and organisational managers may not be aware of whether the investments made in employee training is worthwhile and whether the objectives of the training programs are met.

1.4. Research Aim

This research aims to study theoretical gaps of training evaluation in existing literature, to identify real problems in evaluating training faced by selected organisations, and as a result, to develop an effective framework of best practice for Vietnamese manufacturing organisations.

1.5. Research Objectives

The research aims will be achieved through the following objectives:

- To undertake a critical literature review on training and training effectiveness evaluation and different frameworks of training evaluation
- To examine the current practice of training evaluation and the application of training evaluation frameworks in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam
- To develop a strategic training evaluation framework to enhance the long-term benefit of training programmes and the overall performance of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam.

In order to achieve these above-mentioned research aims and objectives, a set of research questions is to be prepared in the following parts.

1.6. Research questions

Research Question 1: What are the current practices of training evaluation in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam?

Research Question 2: What are the strategic training evaluation frameworks, their strengths and limitations?

Research Question 3: How can the strategic training evaluation framework be developed and applied to enhance the long-term benefit of training programmes in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam?

1.7. Research problem and justification

The issue of training is important as many organisations have induction training for employee orientation while the product and process training to make the freshmen who joined the organisation. The presence of training function in the organisation that is instrumental in skill-building issue needs a deeper introspection as to how much it is effective. Therefore, the training as an intervention that aids in the HR strategy to be aligned to the organisational goals is a vital issue for the organisation (Parmenter, 2012). Inadequate research exists with regards to the training evaluation methods, which is an extended part of the training programme for the Vietnam manufacturing sector context. The problem is that defining training evaluation as a functional element of the HR training and measuring sector-specific effectiveness is absent and feedback is the only route to improve the training intervention. There is a lack of any research that analyses the training evaluation diagnostic tool and would help to redesign the organisational objectives-based training framework, to meet the training goals to aid organisational competitiveness in Vietnam. Training is a system of dissemination of knowledge, skill and competencies, therefore, need an evaluation (period) framework to test its effectiveness and accuracy for the organisational perspective in a Vietnamese context.

Training effectiveness is tested through training evaluation, and for the organisational point of view, it is an issue that HR departments need to implement. The issue is relevant as the HR policies of the organisation need to support the business and the corporate annual goals. The ability of the HR to support and sustain the alignment of their internal functions is dependent on how the firms are using training as a tool to value for the OD (organisational development) in strategic perspective (Ishaq and Mumtaz, 2014). The issue is linked to testing of the gaps in the employee skills and competency deliverables, which is addressed through training interventions and testing the training evaluation forms an important part of the metrics and scale of disseminated knowledge in the workforce. The research, therefore, focuses on the training evaluation methods, the structures and systems which are prevalent to be assessed, that provide an insight to the organisational capability in aligning the HR function to the mainstream operations and meet the organisation strategic goals. The research is justified as the Vietnamese companies are evaluated where the training evaluation in HR function that is tested for the organisational level readiness and strategic competitiveness.

The importance of training effectiveness to HR officials and the board of management using it as a critical tool is tested in this research. In order to increase the competitiveness in the Vietnamese industry as important as the companies face the competition. It also tests the firm-level orientation of how strategic they are in addressing HR function and evaluating the effectiveness of training intervention measurement criteria. The aspect of training being used as a tool at a tactical level to support HR process and the aspect of SHRM that contributes to the Vietnamese industry particularly the manufacturing side is an important driver for understanding the competency-based performance in the different industry sectors. The study defines the standards of the training evaluation process that is existent in different manufacturing industries in Vietnam that contributes to a fair understanding of the nature and status of the training evaluation process that is followed in the manufacturing sector. This is

important as it also delves deeper to find the challenges faced, gaps in the evaluation methods, and the scope of any alternate evaluation method that can be used in Vietnam manufacturing industry.

Potential value this research contributes

The issue is important right now for Vietnam as it is embarking on a growth plan in the South Asian economy, particularly for the manufacturing sector. The method and approach are inward-looking for the nation that is deploying training to benefit the firms engaging in Vietnam. The contribution of the research outcomes to the manufacturing sector about the prevailing training evaluation methods and its effectiveness contributing to the organisation helps to map a guideline for further improvement for other sectors. Hence the criticality of the research, contributing to the HR sector, the manufacturing industries in this research help to identify the gaps and recommend the best practices to over them.

1.8. Brief Description of the Research Methodology

The methodology designed to conduct the current study includes a range of research elements in the form of philosophy, approach, data collection methods and instruments, questionnaire design, and sampling techniques. The choices made in the current methodology are from different options available that could be appropriate to collect data and resolve the research problems. However, the choices made are the most relevant ones and most appropriate to collect data depending on the feasibility of their application, cost-effectiveness, ease of data collection and analysis.

The research methodology includes the philosophy of **pragmatism** in the epistemological position. The researcher's worldview is pragmatism that allows conducting an extensive enquiry into the research problems using a **mixed approach to data collection**, i.e., integrating quantitative and qualitative methods. The research process included in the current methodology

is the **inductive approach** meant to develop new theory and add value to existing knowledge. The type of investigation followed in the current study is exploratory that aligns with the inductive approach to theory building. **The exploratory design** was considered feasible for the current study because the actual research problems were not known while initiating the study. The researcher was unaware of the training evaluation policies and practices followed in Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, the extent of training evaluation followed, its effectiveness and challenges involved. The exploratory design allowed flexibility in terms of collecting data and information from different sources and follow an informal approach to data collection and analysis.

Data was collected using **mixed methods** that involved collecting quantitative data in the first phase followed by qualitative data in the second phase. Quantitative data was collected by implementing a **survey** as the strategy and closed-ended, **structured questionnaires** as the instrument to collect data.

Most of the questions in the questionnaires were designed on the basis of five-point Likert scale to obtain employee response based on a fixed range starting from strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The survey participants involved the employees of three Vietnamese manufacturing companies, namely, VARD Ltd, BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam working with various departments, especially the production department, marketing and sales, finance, and others. On the other hand, qualitative data involved interviewing the human resource managers of the same companies using open-ended questions as the instrument. Individual interviews were conducted from each manager and each interview lasted for around 30-40 minutes approximately. Data obtained from the employee survey are converted into a percentage using a simple Microsoft Excel formula after storing the responses into excel sheets. The cumulative data is presented in the form of tables and graphs. The subjective responses obtained from the managerial interviews are discussed under

specific themes. The similar and dissimilar responses obtained against each question are compared and contrasted and discussed in the context of the research problems.

1.9. Scope of the research

The scope of this research lies in explaining the necessity and importance of training evaluation in manufacturing companies, especially in the context of Vietnam. While it is known that manufacturing companies implement training programs for their employees across different levels, it is not known what training evaluation methods or approaches the human resource management follows to understand or measure the effectiveness of training. This research intends to explore whether Vietnamese manufacturing companies consider training evaluation as a part of their employee training strategy, the nature of the training evaluation exercise if followed, and the extent to which evaluation is conducted for training programs.

By surveying the employees of manufacturing companies and interviewing their HR managers, the researcher intends to find an answer to the aforementioned questions. The findings obtained from employee surveys and managerial interviews will be compared and contrasted against each other and triangulated in order to resolve the questions formulated in this chapter.

The findings, results and recommendations of the research will be shared with the HR managers of the Vietnamese manufacturing companies chosen for case studies. The HR managers will be able to identify the gaps or shortcomings in their training evaluation approach and its implications on business. Moreover, they would be able to understand the significance of implementing a holistic training evaluation framework as suggested by the author of the current thesis, based on the findings obtained from primary research. The HR managers or those responsible for employee training policies and practices can customise the standard training evaluation framework as designed as an outcome of the current research. The HR managers could take immediate steps to examine and eliminate the existing issues in employee training and evaluation and adopt the best practices approach.

1.10. Rationale of the research

Training has been used in developing the skills and knowledge for individual or groups, in order to increase their level of capability, the capacity to learn, achieve their targets and show higher performance. The training, however, is linked to a trade or a profession unlike teaching is related to school, and learning is the process, though employee education in an enterprise is related to the performance improvement agenda. The literature review preliminary study shows the existence of different kinds of training, 'on-the-job' 'off-the-job', simulation training all of which requires different instructor guidance and lesson plans. The evolution of training to develop in the public-sector firms, private sector firms, from manufacturing to service, product to behavioural changes that showed how training interventions applications diversified to meet the different needs (Poston, 2009).

The issue of past academic research has shown the need to adopt the workforce systems, through the training to increase the knowledge, gain skills, improve the productivity and employee output, leading to the organisational efficiency (Sadri and Bowen, 2011). However, the training method and its effectiveness for any given industry need a continual improvement in the metrics and the training design. This is a critical part of the training evaluation process has a range of methods like the Kirkpatrick's Training Evaluation model, Bloom's taxonomy of learning domains, Keller's ARCS model, CIRO framework of evaluation, CIPP Model of Evaluation, Kirkpatrick's Model, Phillips's ROI Model (Snape and Redman, 2010). The comparison of studied frameworks/models helps to understand the underlying philosophies for each of the methods of evaluation of training.

All of these have different methods and applicable to different organisation situation. The importance of the tools for the organisation needs to understand the availability of the

resources, the size of the training programme, and the organisational culture which is most important. As the firms are becoming more strategic, shifting from tactical HR operations, the organisations are therefore depending on making the training to be a key differentiator in building competencies. The preliminary research on the literature distinguished between training evaluation shows that the organisations wanted development issues of an employee while it differentiated education and learning process as each one of the elements forms a different part of the process. The importance of different types of training for different job descriptions showed how the training design conceptualisation varied to meet the organisational needs.

Porter and Spear (2010) argued that though there are different training modules, sub-modules, the importance to understand the barriers and challenges is important when the HR shifts from tactical to strategic arena. The training process and the stages gives a clear outlining of the training end to end process, and how each stakeholder in the training cycle is carrying out the role. Kumpikaitė (2015) cited that the organisational perspective shows that the training strategies to be important before the conceptualisation of training, its goal, the training design and implementation to address gaps is done. The literature review also revisited the training programme criticality and the barriers in implementing the training programme as they need to meet training goal from organisational point of view.

The training module design and its delivery presents the structural challenge for the managers and therefore midway or post-training evaluation gained ground in practice and discussion in the literature review. At the later stage, different forms of training delivery to meet varied organisational requirements come to the forefront especially the employee satisfaction while applying the skill to the new task context (Memon *et al.*, 2016). The training budget and training calendar to manage different pieces of training for job descriptions, for each

department presents the implementation challenge while the greatest challenge is to find out the training content efficacy and accuracy (Ghufli, 2012). This questions the training purpose and tests the TNA (training need analysis) stage which the organisational goal is to impart the skills, behavioural change or knowledge. However, the analysis of the training evaluation as a method tests the efficacy of the whole exercise also shows the pathway for improving the training design and the training programs. The context of the training method evaluation in a sector or a country has a limited volume of research that is a gap, this research explores.

1.11. The thesis structure

The thesis is divided into seven chapters arranged in a chronological manner. The content and purpose of each chapter are described briefly as follows:

Chapter 1- Introduction – This chapter provides the research rationale, research aims, research objectives and research questions. The background context showed how the training in the manufacturing world expanded to meet different job descriptions, aided the services sector to become the mainstay of the company. The need for the training intervention, its formalisation of stages, the training goal and training method is discussed as the industries gained momentum using training method (different) to disseminate knowledge. The criticality of training and equipping employees with a range of skills, behavioural change and productivity were found to be possible. It also identified the research problem in Vietnam industry context, the justification of research. The brief outline of research methods, the research literature at the preliminary stage, the expected research limitations and abbreviations used in the research is detailed in this section. The scope underlines the upper and lower limits of the research.

Chapter 2- Literature review—This chapter is dedicated to addressing the theoretical aspects of the research. Training and evaluation are studied to provide an overview of the definition, different types and methods, the benefits and challenges, and the common process. This chapter particularly looks into training evaluation, its benefits and challenges, different levels of training evaluation and several popular training evaluation frameworks. The theoretical models of training evaluation reviewed in the literature include the CIRO framework of evaluation, the CIPP model of training evaluation, Kirkpatrick’s Model, and Phillips’s ROI Model. This is followed by a critical review of computer-based training, its advantages and drawbacks, and training evaluation in computer-integrated manufacturing. Based on an exhaustive review of extant, underpinning literature the knowledge gaps are identified and discussed and a conceptual framework is designed for the current study.

Chapter 3- Research Methodology- This chapter describes the methodology followed to carry out the entire research, especially the data collection approach. It provides a methodological framework comprising of the researcher’s worldview, i.e. philosophical standpoint, research approach/process, and the type of enquiry. Based on the elements, the data collection approaches, i.e. ‘mixed-methods’ is discussed with key emphasis on strategy to collect data, instrument, and type of questionnaires proposed. The sampling procedure, sample size, timelines (Gantt chart), and ethical considerations are also discussed in this chapter. The choice of each element in the methodology is justified in the context of the research problems and the type of data this is required to be collected to resolve the problems.

Chapter 4 – Introduction to the cases- In this chapter, the chosen manufacturing organizations in Vietnam are studied in terms of their business profile, human resource department, training activities and evaluation. The data set is analysed individually using case study methodology. Evidence from sources inside and outside the companies is used to illustrate and substantiate the emerging issues. Based on each organization’s background

information and opinions from the management and staff, a primary explanation of the training phenomenon is given.

Chapter 5 – Data Analysis and Findings- In this chapter, data obtained from primary research- the quantitative data obtained from the employee survey and qualitative information through managerial interviews are analysed in the context of theoretical discussions conducted in the literature review and findings from the case studies. The results of the employee survey are presented using visuals such as tables and graphs while the subjective information collected from managerial interviews are interpreted by comparing and contrasting the responses of each manager. In this chapter, the conceptual framework developed earlier is put into the application. Data from the individual cases are compared to obtain more general insights about the practice of management and business training in manufacturing organizations in Vietnam, and the effects on business performance. Based on the framework, analysis of the advantages/benefits and disadvantages/impairments from training on the companies is conducted. From the results of the analysis, factors influencing the outcomes and impacts of training are identified.

Chapter 6- Discussion –This chapter conducts an exhaustive discussion based on the overall findings obtained from the research and the significance of such findings with respect to the research problems being investigated. The overall findings obtained from the primary research are triangulated with the theoretical findings obtained from the literature review and secondary based investigation into each of the manufacturing organization. Therefore, the theoretical debates carried out in the literature review are revisited, cross-examined and triangulated against the empirical findings. The discussion is made under specific themes that underpin the research objectives and research questions reflecting the research problems as formulated in the introductory chapter.

Chapter 7 - Conclusion -This chapter conclude the entire thesis by revisiting the research aims and objectives, and questions that were supposed to be resolved. The overall findings and discussion made in previous chapters are summarised against each objective and arguments put forward whether the objectives have been fulfilled or not. The contribution of the research is discussed in association with the implications of the study and how it is useful for the HR managers of Vietnamese manufacturing organisations. Key recommendations are also given based on the gaps and shortcomings identified in the training evaluation methods and approaches of the case study organisations. Finally, the limitations of the study and scope for future research are discussed in brief.

Figure 1-1: Structure of the Thesis

1.12. Summary

The first chapter initiates the topic through the discussion of the background, and gradually building the training method in the industry, its different facets like training design, calendar,

and training modified in different forms for addressing different needs of the organisation. The research aim and objectives along with the research questions are laid down. The research rationale and the research scope help to justify the reason why it is important for the research while the limits of the research topic in the context of Vietnam companies are outlined. The chapter also outlines the problem, the limitations which are apparent right now as the chapter outlines clearly defined show how the research will progress.

CHAPTER 2:
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter starts with an overview of training, its importance in the workplace, the different types of training, its benefits and challenges of training, training process. The differences between training, education, learning and development are also mentioned. The summary of the evaluation is started after that to provide the most general view of evaluation in terms of definitions, different types, purposes and benefits, evaluation process, methods and approaches to evaluation. The two parts overviews of training and overview of evaluation lead to the focus topic of this thesis - Training Evaluation.

2.2. Overview of Training

2.2.1. What is training

Training has long been recognized as a key strategy for human resources development and as the best insurance policy for an organization against all kinds of inevitable changes and arising needs in the future (Pineda, 2010).

In the literature, there are numerous definitions of training. According to Flippo (1984), training is the act of increasing the skills of an employee for doing a particular job. Goldstein (1993) defines training in more detail as a systematic acquisition of skills, rules, concepts or attitudes that results in improved performance in the working environment. Chiaburu and Tekleab (2005:29) see training as “*the planned intervention that is designed to enhance the determinants of individual job performance*”. Training is also clarified as the area where organizational, industrial and individual development can match, and where human resource and organization growth get blended together (Sundarajan, 2007).

Despite the different approaches, these definitions of training in the literature share two common points: (1) training is the systematic acquisition of knowledge, skills, and behaviours; (2) the goal of training is the improvement of both individual and organizational performance

(Goldstein and Ford, 2002), which leads to a strategic competitiveness of the organization (Schraeder, 2009).

2.2.2. The importance of training in the workplace

The importance of training in the workplace has been long recognized. Among the three main capitals of an organization –Men, Machine and Material, men are the most valuable resource (Daniels, 2003). This is the reason why organizations make a huge investment in men or their human resources, especially training activities. Major organizations annually spend about 2.5 per cent of their payroll, which equals several billions of dollars on training (Steensma and Groeneveld, 2010).

According to Arunkumar and Parimala (2012), the fulfilment of the organisation's goals and objectives is one of the core needs of every organisation and effective training plays a key role towards this end. Obeng (2014) points out that employee as executors of the daily tasks are the main driving force for achieving organisational goals and objectives, provided they possess the requisite sets of skills and competencies, and know-how to deliver consistent, or superior performance. It is also essential that employees are trained on the existing policy and practices, work protocols, work culture, working with the required tools and technology, accepting change flexibly, and exhibiting the right attitude and behaviour (Yong and Mohd-Yusoff, 2016). Training contributes to the development of each of such competencies, although, employees can be made aware of these elements through induction programs, counselling, open house forums, or through self -learning materials available on the intranet (Wilson, 2014). However, training provides an interactive platform to the employees and they are superior to gain familiarity with these factors, get their doubts clarified, raise questions or objections if they do not agree with any organisational policy, and give suggestions for any alterations.

Kumpikaitė (2015) argues that training helps to meet the organisational needs, and more precise goals and objectives in two-fold ways. Firstly, customer satisfaction is one of the major goals of any organisation by way of better service delivery and meeting their expectations. Well-trained employees equipped with sound knowledge, up-to-date skills and experience are more likely to deliver a better quality of services than the untrained ones. Moreover, well-trained staff is knowledgeable enough to respond to the customers' queries, issues and problems and thereby provide assurance about the services (Roughton and Crutchfield, 2016). Well-trained staff are also equipped with the skill sets to resolve customers' issues to their satisfaction right in the very first attempt and thereby maintain service dependability (Georgiadis and Pitelis, 2016). Therefore, training programs help employees to meet the service quality dimensions necessary to maintain and deliver superior services to the customers and achieve higher customer satisfaction. Secondly, training helps to increase employee motivation skills improvement, involvement, and engagement. It also empowers employees by instilling confidence in them to remain committed to fulfilling the organisational goals and objectives.

Training relates to up-to-date knowledge, special skills and abilities that needed for employees in any organisation to perform their job effectively. Dent and Holton (2009) point out that post-training, performance measurement signifies the importance of training in better utilisation of resources when the employees are able to deliver superior performance and achieve individual as well as organisational goals. Khan (2012) considers that training in the form of continuous learning is the best way to motivate employees as they are able to upgrade their skills on an ongoing basis and ensuring that their existing skills and competencies do not become obsolete. This experience is motivating for the employees as they gain confidence in performing their daily tasks. However, motivation may be extrinsic or intrinsic and both are related to employee training and its outcomes. Eisele *et al.* (2013) training help employees to acquire new skills

and competencies to enhance performance and thereby gain higher rewards in the form of increased compensation, incentives, or bonuses. Intrinsic motivation is achieved in the form of verbal appreciation, job satisfaction, or an increase in self-esteem as a result of training programs that help to enhance performance.

To that end, it is crystal clear that investing in employees' training is a wise business choice that not only yields a significant return on investment, but also saves an organization from having to hire more experienced employees outright. Training is a critical factor in ensuring that a current workforce is truly an investment rather than an expense. Recent research consistently shows that companies that fail to train their employees are more than three times as likely to lose them (Dirkes, 2014). To be justified as the most powerful activity among many organisational interventions, training must be therefore managed as a frontline business activity and received sufficient investment (Guzzo *et al.*, 1985).

2.2.3. Differences between training, learning, development and education

Training, learning, development and education are frequently-used terms as the indispensable parts of human resource function and management. These four activities are used together in the corporate world and aim at improving the knowledge, performance, quality and productivity of the employees (Garavan, 1997).

However, there are some distinct differences between training, learning, development and education, which are not easily and clearly defined (Harrison, 2000; Buckley and Caple, 2004). With reference to a number of sources, the following differences are believed to be most concrete and systematic.

Basis for comparison	Learning	Training	Development	Education
<i>Time scale</i>	Continuous	Short-term	Long-term	Specified period
<i>Focus on</i>	Values, attitudes, innovation and outcome accomplishment	Knowledge, skills, ability and job performance with concrete goals	Individual potential and future role in workplace	Personal structured development to specified outcomes
<i>Nature of process</i>	Inside out, seeks to do for self	Outside in, done by others	Combination of inside out and outside in	Largely outside in
<i>Orientation</i>	Personal outcomes-oriented	Job-oriented	Career-oriented	Both personal and external specified outcomes-oriented
<i>Objective</i>	Self-actualization or to change behaviour	Specific job related or role requirement	To prepare the individual employee for the next step of his/her career	To get personal specified goals and outcomes
<i>Number of individuals</i>	Only one	Many	Only one	Only one
<i>Common activities and methods</i>	Informal learning methods, learner-initiated methods	Workshops, seminars, etc.	Job-rotation, leadership coaching, counselling, competency modelling, etc.	Lectures, guided reading, debate, self-managed learning
<i>Process of evaluation</i>	Continuous evaluation	Evaluation against specific job performance standards	Evaluation of skills and effectiveness	Evaluation against life goals and personal development
<i>Payback to organization</i>	Immediate and ongoing	Almost immediately in terms of skilled performance	Medium and long-term payback in terms of increased potential	No direct payback

Table 2-1: The differences between learning, training, development and education

Source: Harrison, 2000; Buckley and Caple, 2004

Training is generally regarded as a subset of human resource development. With the ever-changing business environment, it is crucial that organization pay equal attention to both training and development to stay ahead of the competition. In a practical business environment, both training and development are required to work hand in hand for providing the right skills and knowledge to employees and help them get the most of it from both organizations benefit as well as their own progression.

This study will focus on training in the workplace and see training and development to be two different processes.

2.3. Different types of training

In fact, there are many types of training that the companies can use to motivate their staff. Such types are usually applied in all stages in a training process, including orientation, on-site, mentorship and external training. The way of training relies on several factors of the corporations like the extent of resources available for training, the kind of firms, and the priority the company places on training. In general, training is divided into eight (08) primary types as below (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.3.1. Technical training

Technical training is a sort of training required for technological aspects of new employees in some fields. For example, in retail industry, technical training might consist of teaching newcomers how to use the computer system to ring up consumers. Or in a sales position, this kind of training might help the staff know how to use the customer relationship management system to seek new prospects. Even when the organization updates the new version of Microsoft Office, it also requires some technical training of the whole firm to make sure

everyone can use the technology in an effective manner. Technical training is often performed in-house, but sometimes it can also be delivered externally (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.3.2. Quality training

In terms of manufacturing businesses, quality training is vital. It makes personnel familiar with the means of preventing, detecting, and eradicating substandard products. In the situation of high competition, this type of training can bring competitive advantage to the companies since it gives the knowledge to the labour force to help them recognize products that are not qualified enough and teach them how to deal with in this scenario. Some quality training can occur in-house, but corporations like ISO (International Organization for Standardization) also perform external training.

2.3.3. Skill training

Skill training aims to provide proficiencies needed to actually perform the work (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013). For instance, an administrative assistant might be taught how to answer the phone meanwhile a sales staff at Best Buy might be taught in the evaluation of their consumer needs and on how to offer them the information to make a purchasing decision. Most of the time, skills training is delivered in-house and it can contain the use of a mentor.

2.3.4. Soft- skills training

Soft skills refer to personal characteristics, social graces, communication and personal habits that are used to characterize relationships with others (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013). Soft skills might be comprised of how to answer the phone or how to be friendly and welcoming to buyers. In several kinds of jobs, essential soft skills might include how to inspire others, maintain small talk and set up a rapport. Soft skills training can be administered both indoor and outdoor.

2.3.5. Professional training and legal training

Professional training is one kind of training required to update one's own professional field. In some careers, professional training must be implemented on an ongoing basis. For instance, as a result of a change in tax laws, an accountant must acquire annual professional training on new tax codes. Besides, lawyers also need professional training when laws change. Legal training might consist of sexual harassment law training and discrimination law training. Such kind of training is normally provided externally, and it is usually demanded particular professions in which updates happen often like in the accounting industry (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.3.6. Team training

The objective of team training is to develop cohesiveness among team members, permitting them to get to know each other and facilitate relationship building. Team training can be defined as a process that empowers teams to enhance decision making, problem-solving, and team development skills to obtain business results. This kind of training can be delivered both indoor and outdoor (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.3.7. Managerial training

In fact, after a long time of working at one company, the employees might be identified as a candidate for promotion and they need managerial training. Training topics might contain those from our soft skill part, such as how to motivate and delegate, while others may be technical in nature. Several managerial pieces of training might be administered in-house while other training like leadership skills, might be delivered externally (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.3.8. Safety training

Safety training is one kind of training which helps the workforce have skills to protect themselves from injuries caused by work-related accidents. It is extraordinarily vital for

manufacturing organizations that use chemicals or other kinds of hazardous materials in their production. Safety training can comprise evacuation plans, fire drills, and personnel violence procedures. It also is composed of eye safety, first aid, food service safety, hearing protection, asbestos, construction safety. This type of training can be provided either internally or externally (Jahanzeb and Bashir, 2013).

2.4. The benefits of training

A well-managed training programme is believed to bring many benefits to both the organization and employee. The major benefits of training are briefly summarised in the following table conducted by the researcher.

BENEFITS OF TRAINING	
TO ORGANIZATION	TO EMPLOYEE
<p><i>Increase profits</i> Training enhances an organization's revenue in increased sales and referrals, improved customer satisfaction and retention (Kim, 2006).</p>	<p><i>Improve employee performance at all levels</i> Training improves employee performance in quality, quantity, speed, safety, problem solving, attitude, ethics, motivation, leadership, and communication (Goldstein and Ford, 2002).</p>
<p><i>Proper utilization of resources</i> Training helps to increase speed and accuracy reduce duplication of effort and time spent on problem solving and mistake correction (Topno, 2012).</p>	<p><i>Less supervision and more confidence</i> Training reduces the need for detailed and constant supervision. Training also enhances confidence of employees with improved knowledge and skills (Kumar, 1959).</p>
<p><i>Create better organization image & attract new talent</i> (Kumar, 1959) The business with ongoing training attracts better talents as this gives the business a good image of creating a supportive workplace for employees' development opportunities.</p>	<p><i>Increase chances of internal promotion and career progression</i> (Topno, 2012) With ongoing training, existing staff can become more eligible for internal promotions.</p>
<p><i>Improve workforce morale, commitment & Reduce employee turnover</i> Training is a commitment towards developing the skills of employees and cements their importance to an organisation, which improves staff morale and loyalty as well as lowers staff turnover (Shahrooz, 2012).</p>	<p><i>Promote job satisfaction and retention</i> Through continued investment from the business, employees can have a higher sense of job satisfaction, which can improve their motivation towards their work. The more engaged and involved they are working, the higher commitment they have for an organization (Bowes, 2008).</p>
<p><i>Keep up with industry changes & stay ahead of competitors</i> (Topno, 2012). Training increases capacity of an organization to adopt new technologies and methods to comply with any industry regulations and inevitable changes. Training also ensures the staffs are constantly advancing and the organization remains competitive within marketplace.</p>	<p><i>Helps employees adapt to the changes and foster their creativity with new product rollouts after training</i> After training, the employees can master new skills and have advanced knowledge for more ideas of new products (Borate <i>et.al</i>, 2014).</p>

Table 2-2: Benefits of training in the workplace

2.5. The challenges of training

It is no doubt that training today has become more important for the success of any company. With the growing demand for training, the entry of newcomers, and globalization, the role of the training manager is also changing. Apart from training quality, the modern training

managers must also make sure that the training is engaging, effective and delivered on time with the smallest amount of costs. There are also some other challenges that the training manager must face.

Inconsistent training

Along with globalization, many organisations expand their operations to foreign countries. Obviously, different countries with multiple trainers, there is no guarantee that the training program will be consistent. This is because the knowledge levels, teaching methods of the trainers may be different. This might result in inconsistency in the training provided (Yakaraju, 2015).

Flexible and mobile labour force

The increasing size of flexible human resources, workers working in shifts, and workers working on the field, is the next principal challenge (Yakaraju, 2015). Hence, it is difficult to hold a training program that all employees can take part in. As a result, it can create differences in the qualifications of staff.

Language problems

Another challenge arisen from globalization is the difference in the primary language of all workers (Yakaraju, 2015). As we all know, language is one of the most important tools to connect people in an organization. Therefore, differences in language can lead to misunderstanding and confusion. For instance, training courses in English will not be of great use to non-English speakers.

Meeting stipulated timelines

In today market, the quicker the better! Training, especially on product knowledge, processes and compliance, should be completed as soon as possible. For example, sales staff cannot wait

to get trained for months to be able to sell a new product. The training should be performed at the same time as launching such a new product (Yakaraju, 2015).

Appeal to newcomers

New employees, especially young staff, really like to do everything in their own manner, even though it is just a simple training course. They only want to access short training on their own devices and when they need it the most. So, it might lead to negative consequences if an organisation were to deliberately hold training sessions and force their personnel to attend just because they do not really cooperate (Yakaraju, 2015).

Training cost reduction

Holding offline training is irrefutably very effective. However, it incurs huge costs, including travelling and accommodation charges for both trainers and trainees. In addition to extrinsic costs such as time of both supervisors and employees during on-the-job training, instruction materials, equipment, etc., there are some kinds of implicit training costs for new staff like a loss of productivity until the new hire masters the job (Taylor, 2016).

Training updating

The other considerable challenge is to give human resources updated knowledge, especially when there are changes in the legislation, policies and working processes. Moreover, rapid changes in technology, corporate initiatives and programs make it difficult to adequately prepare training materials and deliver training before employees need information and new skills (Yakaraju, 2015).

2.6. The training process

In order to have an effective training program at the workplace, an organization needs to systematically follow the training process, which comprises four basic steps as depicted in the following figure.

Figure 2-1: Four basic steps of the Training Process

Source: Adapted from Stewart (1999)

Training needs analysis (TNA) could be identified through a diagnosis of present and future challenges and through a gap between the employee's actual performance and the expected performance.

Designing training programs encompass certain issues such as defining the objective, developing a training plan, choosing training methods and materials, selecting trainers and trainees, designing the training content, and considering other training requisites.

Delivering training program – The training programs are then officially informed, launched, promoted and conducted. During training, participant progress should be monitored to ensure that the program is effective. Employees should be encouraged to become involved in the training process by participating in the discussion, asking questions, contributing their

knowledge and expertise, learning through hands-on experiences, and even though role-playing exercises.

Training Evaluation a must for any training program because companies invest huge amounts in these sessions and must know their effectiveness in terms of money.

It is apparent that training does not simply refer to conducting classroom sessions and the training process is not an isolated activity. Indeed, the training process should be considered as a cyclical process (Bee and Bee, 1994) with distinct stages where the evaluation stage of this training is used to set out the new training process in the future (shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2-2: The training cycle

Source: Adopted from Bee and Bee (1994, p.36)

In the business context, training processes may vary from course to course, from department to department, from organization to organization, and from industry to industry. Some organizations add more steps to their training process, such as developing learning objectives, developing training plans, or designing training materials. It depends on the individual training

needs and organizational training needs that the training process is accordingly amended in the most pro-how to realize per manner.

2.7. Implementing a training program

Review of academic literature indicates that there exist two fundamental approaches to training program implementation; the first one is trainer centred wherein the trainer controls the learning or training content, while the second is learner/trainee centred, wherein the trainer takes up the guiding position and provides resources necessary for training. This particular approach supposes that if individuals in an organisation are eager to learn, it is necessary for the human resource management to arrange for appropriate materials, training modules, tools and equipment, and sophisticated technology such as ICT (Information and Communications Technology) to add value to the training programs (Snape and Redman, 2010). This method of training is most preferred in modern organisations because it is participatory in nature wherein the experiences of the trainees are shared, and participants are given adequate autonomy to learn at their own speed.

One of the important elements included in the training package follow-up support offered to the trainees and assessment of the training outcome. This kind of support is feasible to be incorporated in the training budget by way of supervision, mentoring, coaching, establishing a network support group, or basically providing a source of persistent information (Bulut and Culha, 2010). Follow-ups may be carried out in person however may be provided via digital communication such as email, or social media.

2.8. Training Strategies

Training strategies may suitable to the academic level of employees being trained or to the relevant resources available in the organisation that are feasible in terms of cost, and time.

Training managers need to ensure that the training costs are not wasteful and yield better returns in the form of improved employee behaviour, attitude, skills and competencies, and thereby performance. Training modules must not be outdated, obsolete, and include up-to-date training materials that are much in demand. For example, training on the use of a newly installed technology or software and its application may require redesigning the training modules and the course materials that incorporate the know-how of using the same.

Training programs also need to be feasible. The timing of the training sessions must not be too long or stretched enough to hamper work productivity (Porter and Spear, 2008). The duration of the training program must be in line with the training needs of the employees, for instance, off-the-job training for new recruits who require a comparatively lengthier time for training as compared to the experienced ones. The HRM must also ensure that the training time is optimal rather than over-stretched to increase the idle time and therefore loss of productive hours. Training assessments and performance checks of the trained employees help to understand whether the time, costs, and efforts invested in training programs have yielded positive benefits (Kontoghiorghes, 2016). Moreover, a feasible training program should also ensure that it brings a change in the behaviour of the employees in terms of taking initiatives, flexibly accepting any change, fostering team-work, and increased commitment to the organisation (Kumpikaitè, 2015). This requires the implementation of behavioural training programs to ensure that the trainees not only acquire knowledge and development skills but also feel motivated to work, accept the work-related challenge, low absenteeism, and less intention for turnover.

2.9. Pre-training arrangement process

A systematic and organized pre-training program is essential for any training program to succeed (Kumpikaitè, 2007). It is essential that the pre-training arrangements are appropriately planned and organised in sequential order. This process of training involves several factors

such as training needs identification (TNA), selecting the right employees who require training, and delivering training sessions with the implementation of appropriate technology, modules, and techniques (Ghufli, 2012). Thakore (2013) indicate that TNA and selection of suitable participants are the core elements of the planning part while the adoption of appropriate training methods is essential elements of the execution part.

The two parts of the process of pre-training are interlinked with the training co-ordinators (Smale, Bjorkman, and Sumelius, 2013). Any gaps or failure of any one part in the overall process may significantly affect the other part and the overall training program. Lazazzara and Bombelli (2011) argue that the acceptance and aptness of the training methods and its suitability also need to be evaluated by the trainees. In this context, it is feasible to seek feedback from the trainees or participants as well as the training coordinators. Feedback received from the trainees helps to make amendments in the overall training program and make it trainee-centric (Srivastava and Agarwal, 2012). TNA helps the human resource managers to identify the actual training needs of the employees based on their knowledge gaps and skill shortcomings. Falola, Osibanjo and Ojo (2014) explain that proper identification of the training needs helps to design 'objective-based training' programs ensuring that the resources and costs incurred in the training do not go waste.

According to Kumpikaitè (2007), training evaluation can be said to be a systematic process of data collection with regards to the effectiveness and success of training programs. The constructive evaluation takes place when the specific outcome measures are theoretically related to the proposed learning objectives. Evaluation is therefore carried out to find the answer to two alternative questions; whether the objectives of the training were accomplished (learning issues) and whether the achievement of these objectives results in increased performance on the job (issues related to transfer) (Hurn, 2014). While both questions are crucial, Kumpikaitè (2015) emphasizes that the most central issue of training evaluation is

whether the trainees have assimilated the knowledge covered in the training. Roughton and Crutchfield (2016) argued that evaluation needs to be carried out with the sole purpose to determine whether the training outcomes have been accomplished.

2.10. Impact of training on organisational needs

According to Arunkumar and Parimala (2012), fulfilment of the organisation's goals and objectives is one of the core needs of every organisation and effective training plays a key role towards this end. Obeng (2014) points out that employee as executors of the daily tasks are the main driving force for achieving organisational goals and objectives, provided they possess the requisite sets of skills and competencies, and know-how to deliver consistent, or superior performance. It is also essential that employees are trained on the existing policy and practices, work protocols, work culture, working with the required tools and technology, accepting change flexibly, and exhibiting the right attitude and behaviour (Yong and Mohd-Yusoff, 2016). Training contributes to the development of each of such competencies, although, employees can be made aware of these elements through induction programs, counselling, open house forums, or through self-learning materials available on the intranet (Wilson, 2014). However, training provides an interactive platform to the employees and they are superior to gain familiarity with these factors, get their doubts clarified, raise questions or objections if they do not agree with any organisational policy, and give suggestions for any alterations.

Kumpikaitė (2015) argues that training helps to meet the organisational needs, and more precise goals and objectives in two ways. Firstly, customer satisfaction is one of the major goals of any organisation by way of better service delivery and meeting their expectations. Well-trained employees equipped with sound knowledge, up-to-date skills and experience are more likely to deliver a better quality of services than the untrained ones. Moreover, well-trained staff is knowledgeable enough to respond to the customers' queries, issues and

problems and thereby provide assurance about the services (Roughton and Crutchfield, 2016). A well-trained staff is also equipped with the skill sets to resolve customers' issues to their satisfaction right in the very first attempt and thereby maintain service dependability (Georgiadis and Pitelis, 2016). Therefore, training programs help employees to meet the service quality dimensions necessary to maintain and deliver superior services to the customers and achieve higher customer satisfaction. Secondly, training helps to increase employee motivation skills improvement, involvement, and engagement. It also empowers employees by instilling confidence in them to remain committed to fulfilling the organisational goals and objectives.

2.11. Training and employee motivation

Training relates to up-to-date knowledge, special skills and abilities that are needed for employees in any organisation to perform their job effectively. Dent and Holton (2009) point out that post-training, performance measurement signifies the importance of training in better utilisation of resources when the employees are able to deliver superior performance and achieve individual as well as organisational goals. Khan (2012) considers that training in the form of continuous learning is the best way to motivate employees as they are able to upgrade their skills on an ongoing basis and ensuring that their existing skills and competencies do not become obsolete. This experience is motivating for the employees as they gain confidence in performing their daily tasks. However, motivation may be extrinsic or intrinsic and both are related to employee training and its outcomes. Eisele *et al.* (2013) indicate that training helps employees to acquire new skills and competencies to enhance performance and thereby gain higher rewards in the form of increased compensation, incentives, or bonuses. Intrinsic motivation is achieved in the form of verbal appreciation, job satisfaction, or an increase in self-esteem as a result of training programs that help to enhance performance.

According to Shahzadi *et al.* (2014), organisations in the current competitive business environment often measure actual organisational performance (AOP) and contrast it with the expected organisational performance (EOP). These authors further point out that if AOP is less than EOP, there is an apparent gap in the area of employee performance and needs to be overcome by imparting appropriate training to the employees and motivating them to deliver better performance. Training may motivate employees to either align AOP with EOP or even exceed expectations. Organisations and particularly the HRM implement training programs for a range of reasons (Vui-Yee, 2015), such as raising the skills and productivity of the workforce, enhancing employee's commitment to the organisation, enhancing labour productivity, facilitating the launch of new products and/or services, compliance with legal obligations, controlling labour turnover, rewarding employees, and most importantly, maintaining a motivated workforce.

Training and Employee motivation (explained using Maslow's hierarchy of needs)

The use of Maslow's hierarchy of needs as a human motivation model or tool can be used to explain how training is associated with employee motivation in an organisation (Sadri and Bowen, 2011). Going ahead of the need for survival, i.e. psychological need, training can be associated with the fulfilment of each of the needs relating to safety, belongingness, esteem needs and finally self-actualisation. In contemporary organisations it is mandatory for employers to provide training on 'health and safety' and hence employees are trained on the use of machinery, electrical equipment and gadgets, safe use of appliances, first aid and response during emergencies such as fire, or other natural hazards. Employees well trained in these aspects develop a sense of safety (Jerome, 2013).

Budhwar and Pawan (2015b) explain that the training needs of the employees are identified by the immediate supervisor or the HR personnel during performance appraisals, team huddles, or team meetings where interactive discussions between them may take place. Team

supervisors having a friendly relationship with the team-members, maintaining open communication and feedback sharing are in a better position to identify the employees' skill gaps and accordingly training needs (Delery and Gupta, 2015). Moreover, in the actual training sessions, the employees' as trainees are able to interact closely with the peers, co-workers, trainers, supervisors and the managers to share best practices, and discuss the learning gained. Interactive training sessions, therefore, provide adequate scope for mutual learning, sharing ideas, and developing a collaborative work environment through information exchange and knowledge development (Zide *et al.*, 2017).

Employees gain higher esteem through superior performance, job promotion, higher responsibilities, and leadership position. While training does not directly help to achieve the 'esteem needs', it often acts as a catalyst to help employees deliver better performance as desired by the employer, through improved knowledge, improved skills, and techniques and deserve a higher position in the organisation through promotion and increase in compensation and benefits packages. Finally, researchers such as Jusoh *et al.* (2011) indicate that training may not always be necessary for lower-level or operational level employees but also a requirement for managers, senior managers, and the top management. As a continuous learning program, training helps those at the 'esteem' level to add more value to their existing skills and position, gain empowerment, and the ability to make autonomous decisions (Smale *et al.*, 2013). However, it is essential that higher-order needs as depicted by Maslow can be achieved by combining training with developmental programs, primarily, training and development.

2.12. Overview of Evaluation

2.12.1. What is evaluation

There are many definitions of evaluation offered by various researchers over the years. Although each concept is slightly different from others, they all share vital commonalities. In the first place, evaluation is viewed as a systematic process which contains a clear plan and purposeful activity. Secondly, evaluation involves collecting data for issues or problems about society and companies or even specific programs in particular. Evaluation is also defined as a process of improving knowledge and decision making if the decisions are for enhancing or refining a program, process, product, system or the whole firm or for identifying if or not to continue or expand a program. Lastly, evaluation is concerned with asking questions about matters that arise out of everyday practice. It is an effective tool for achieving better comprehension of what we do and the influences of our actions in the situation of society and the working environment. Most importantly, evaluation is a state of mind, rather than a set of techniques (Preskill and Russ-Eft, 2005).

According to Kumpikaitė (2007), training evaluation can be said to be a systematic process of data collection with regards to the effectiveness and success of training programs. Teasley *et al.* (2008) explain that constructive evaluation takes place when the specific outcome measures are theoretically related to the proposed learning objectives. Evaluation is therefore carried out to find the answer to two alternative questions; whether the objectives of the training were accomplished (learning issues) and whether the achievement of these objectives results in increased performance on the job (issues related to transfer) (Hurn, 2014). While both questions are crucial, Kumpikaitė (2015) emphasises that the most central issue of training evaluation is whether the trainees have assimilated the knowledge covered in the training. Roughton and Crutchfield (2016) argued that evaluation needs to be carried out with the sole purpose to determine whether the training outcomes have been accomplished. However, existing literature studies do not offer any concrete conceptual framework to guide the

organisations about how to evaluate the learning effectiveness. After gaining a basic understanding of the concept of evaluation, the next section theoretically reviews the strategies associated with training evaluation.

2.12.2. Strategies associated with Training Evaluation

2.12.2.1. Cognitive Learning outcomes

Cognition relates to a set of variables linked to the extent and type of knowledge and the correlation between the knowledge dimensions. Repko and Arlington (2008) explain that an important aim of cognition is to create theoretical models or mechanisms that indicate how individuals' function. With regards to evaluation, a cognitive viewpoint emphasis not only on the static state of the trainees' knowledge development but also on the vibrant processes of acquiring knowledge, its organisation, and relevance.

Conventionally, acquisition of knowledge in the training domain has been evaluated by way of accomplishment tests undertaken at the end of the training session (Vidal-Salazar *et al.*, 2012). Herein, the trainees are given a series of questionnaires using closed-ended questions and few open-ended ones and are required to sign if each stimulus exists in their memory. For instance, aligning the phrase 'active listening' to the clause such as 'appropriate body language, understanding, empathy' would reveal knowledge of the conceptual ideas covered in a managerial skills training course. Fraser *et al.* (2012) point out that such formats are well suited for evaluating how trainees retain verbal or declarative knowledge.

On the contrary, research undertaken in other psychological domains draws attention to the complex and forceful nature of the knowledge acquisition process. Even though verbal knowledge acquisition serves the groundwork for cognitive skill development, verbal knowledge measures may not be able to differentiate among learners at increased levels of

cognitive development. (McInerney, 2013) Therefore, this literature discusses the three categories of cognitive learning objectives to propose the broad classification of evaluation measures based on cognition, namely, verbal knowledge, knowledge organisation, and cognitive strategies. Meanwhile, the outcomes may be valuable in evaluating trainees at any developmental level, by and large, the three are chronologically organised with regards to the expected changes in trainees. In this context, Riding and Rayner (2013) argue that verbal knowledge measures would be the most insightful for the trainees in their preliminary stages of basic skill acquisition, and measures based on strategic approach would be more useful for trainees undergoing advanced levels of skill acquisition.

2.12.2.2. Verbal knowledge

According to Moreno and Mayer (2007), verbal knowledge in an organisation may exist in various forms, together with declarative knowledge (information about how); strategic knowledge, or tacit knowledge (information relating to why, when, and which). Chan (2013) explains that most of the cognitive skill development theories agree that declarative knowledge development must go before higher-order development. Consequently, measuring the trainees' capability to retain declarative knowledge is most suitable in the preliminary stages of training. Nevertheless, it is worth noticing that building groundwork of verbal based, task-relevant knowledge is essential but not a satisfactory condition for higher-order skill development. Swift and Hwang (2013) pointed out that the latent abilities of a trainee that influence performance of tasks differs in accordance with the developmental stages. Explicitly, general intelligence aspects are found to be most crucial for determining individual performance on new tasks; competence of trainees while concluding relations or memorising the much-needed information will be successful in early stages of training (Nestojko *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, with persistent practice, task behaviour of the trainees tends to become internalised while levels of performance are influenced as much by psychomotor variances (for instance, the pace of

encoding information or responding) as they by means of general aptitudes or intellectual capabilities (Umanath and Marsh, 2014). Apparently, the concern is that whereas a usual pencil-and-paper test can be the most suitable measure for evaluating preliminary learning capabilities, the correlation between learning, skill development, and task accomplishment may be confounded by the general intelligence of the trainee (Bransford *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, if a conventional multiple-choice examination is conducted early in the training, it may be inappropriate to infer that higher scorers (trainees) are those who are most likely to get the most out of training, given that those who are most intellectual may possess an edge in declarative knowledge acquisition and in exhibiting it on a more conventional measure.

2.12.2.3. Measurement implications of verbal knowledge

Moreno and Mayer (2007) indicate that the extent of declarative knowledge acquisition can be evaluated using true-false, multiple-choice questions, or free-recall examinations. The declarative knowledge that trainees hold can be evaluated by using two different approaches, at another level. Speed tests help to evaluate the number of items answered in a specific time frame, or the response time trainees' take to answer any single item. Pineda (2010) explains that power tests evaluate the count of items correctly answered, given unlimited timeframe. Saks and Burke (2012) indicated that in similar situations, power tests and speed tests, in reality, measure different constructs, while Swift and Hwang (2013) argued that the choice of format must depend on the constructs that need to be measured. Power tests help to measure the precision of stored information; therefore, such tests should be implemented when recall exactness is valued or the outcomes of errors are high. Speed tests help to measure the speed at which trainees are able to access knowledge and are more suitable when the speed of recall is the focal learning outcome (Nidhra *et al.*, 2013).

The implication of the second measurement is more direct. In order to capitalize on the value of conventional measures of declarative knowledge, such tests must be given in the preliminary training period rather than the end. Umanath and Marsh (2014) give two reasons for this, firstly, as a feedback system, these tests in early period would help to recognise knowledge gaps that may be likely to obstruct the pace of subsequent (higher-level) learning. Secondly, from a psychometric viewpoint, differences among the trainees in declarative knowledge must be greater earlier rather than the end of the training. As a result, earlier assessment scores would have the greatest use for envisaging other learning outcomes.

2.12.2.4. Knowledge organisation

With the advancement in skill learning beyond the preliminary acquisition stages, various interrelated changes in processing take place as a function of persistent practices (Kumbhar, 2012). Initially, learners emphasise minimally on declarative knowledge and more on procedural knowledge. Simultaneously with enhancement in procedural knowledge is the growth of evocative structures for knowledge organisation (Hecker, 2012).

Researchers, such as DeChurch and Mesmer-Magnus (2010), use the term ‘mental model’ to explain how individuals organise knowledge in their mind. The models work as mechanisms used by trainees to illustrate the forms and functions of tasks, describe and observe task integration, and predict the future task requirements (DeChurch and Mesmer-Magnus, 2010). However, the mental model resembles other phrases such as cognitive maps, knowledge structures, or task schemata. It is believed that the incumbents have separate models for manifold functions on the job. For instance, distinct mental models can be held by a military pilot for multiple functions, such as pre-flight briefings, take-offs, tactical involvement, landing, and coordinating aircrew. Paulin and Suneson (2012) argue that mental models offer

an environment for the interpretation of different objects and events, organise current information as well as affect the acquirement of new knowledge.

A key characteristic of a mental model is the form or complexity of the stored aspects. Studies relating to expert/novice differences indicate that while novices generate different mental models for defining problems and strategies for a solution, experts form more complicated knowledge frameworks that encompass both problem definition nodes and solution nodes (Batey *et al.*, 2012). Fazey *et al.* (2014) explain that the advantage of this model is that having recognised the problem, individuals can quickly access a solution strategy as the strategy is intimately linked (in memory) to the problem node.

Another important characteristic of a mental model is the inter-relationship or organisation among the model dimensions. Research conducted by Kennett (2013), on expert/novice differences, signifies that the knowledge base of experts is typified by hierarchical storage and strong routes between critical elements. Hierarchical storage relates to the manner in which novel information is integrated and the manner in which existing knowledge is organised. In addition, through experience, routes between diagnostic nodes and solution nodes are solidified, increasing the speed of solution.

2.12.2.5. Measurement Implications of Knowledge organisation

A direct insinuation of the above discussion is that the trainees' familiarity with the course material can be best evaluated by measuring their supportive cognitive frameworks (Fazey *et al.*, 2014). Several strategies exist for directly measuring the structures. The model technique necessitates verdicts of similarity or proximity among a formerly defined set of core elements. This is followed by mapping the elements either by allowing the learners or trainees to physically arrange the elements by making use of free-sort task contained by a problem-space

or by submitting the verdicts to a cluster or scaling algorithm (Algezai and Filieri, 2014). The latter strategy is known as a structured evaluation.

2.12.2.6. Cognitive Strategies

The last category of cognitive measures focuses on the development and relevance of cognitive strategies. Riding and Sadler-Smith (1997) assert that individual variances exist in the degree to which knowledge can be evaluated or applied more rapidly or fluidly. With regards to training, Holman *et al.* (2012) consider skill development to be an incessant process, and as knowledge and procedures persistently compile, more elegant task-related strategies tend to emerge. Included in cognitive strategies is the term meta-cognition that relates to the familiarity of one's own cognition. Meta-cognition skills comprise planning, monitoring, evaluating, and designing goal-specific behaviour (Riding and Rayner, 2013) or understanding the association between task demands and complexities, and one's individual capabilities (McInerney, 2013). Meta-cognition also involves skills required to regulate or induce appropriate strategies (Fraser *et al.*, 2012), wherein strategies imply a wide range of psychological activities that facilitate the acquisition of knowledge and its application.

2.12.3. Different types of evaluation

The organization usually carries out an evaluation to obtain information before a program's development to enhance and refine such a program; or to make judgments about a future program. There are some common types of evaluation as described in the following sections.

Formative evaluation

It serves as a guarantee that a program or activity is feasible, suitable and acceptable based on the company goals and objectives before it is fully conducted. The company usually

implements this kind of evaluation when a new program or activity is being developed or when an existing one is being adapted or modified.

Process evaluation or implementation evaluation

This kind of evaluation identifies if program activities have been taken place as intended and led to specific outputs. The enterprises may carry out implementation evaluation periodically during the operation of the existing programs and begin by reviewing the activities and output components. This evaluation type is quite useful since it gives an early warning for any problems that may happen to the company. Moreover, it allows the programs to control how well their program plans and activities are working.

Outcome evaluation or effectiveness evaluation

Outcome evaluation or effectiveness evaluation measures the effect of the program in the target population by evaluating the progress in the outcomes or outcome goals that the program plans to gain. This is obviously conducted after the program has completed to know if such a program is being effective in fulfilling its goals.

Impact evaluation

Impact evaluation assesses the effectiveness of the program in obtaining its final objectives. It can be implemented during the program operation at appropriate intervals or at the end of the program in order to give evidence for use in policy and funding decisions.

Summative evaluation

Summative evaluation is taken place for the purpose of determining the merit, worth or value of the evaluation in a manner that results in making a final evaluation judgment or “summary” judgment. It is usually conducted after a program’s completion (Preskill and Russ-Eft, 2005).

2.12.4. The purposes and benefits of evaluation

In terms of the purposes of evaluation, there are three key purposes below. First, evaluation is designed to give feedback on the effectiveness of the training activities. Second, it aims to provide control over the provision of training. Last but not least, the evaluation makes the power of intervention into the organizational processes that impact training.

As an effective tool for improving the training quality, evaluation brings a variety of benefits to the enterprises. These are several good points of evaluation:

- Enhancing the quality of training activities
- Enhancing the ability of the trainers to relate inputs to outputs
- Better discrimination of training activities between those that are worthy of support and those that should be dropped
- Better integration of training offered and on-the-job development
- Better cooperation between trainers and line managers in the development of human resources
- Proof of the contribution that training and development are making to the company

2.12.5. Evaluation process

The evaluation process consists of four steps, namely planning, implementation, completion, and dissemination and reporting. Each stage involves its own matters, methods and procedures to implement. This part will discuss each of these four phases.

2.12.5.1. Planning

The relevant tasks during planning and implementation of training evaluation are determining the feasibility of the evaluation, identifying stakeholders and specifying short term objectives as well as long term ones. For instance, does the program have clear goals or transparency in its methods required for evaluation? Or what criteria were used to ascertain the need for this program? In fact, defining and identifying stakeholders is a principal part of the planning phase just because stakeholders are individuals or organizations that are interested in or could be influenced by the program evaluation. In addition to building support for the evaluation, the engagement of stakeholders increases its credibility, giving a participatory approach, and providing the multiple perspectives of participants and partners. Stakeholders constitute a vital resource for specifying question one program evaluation should consider, choosing the methodology to be used, determining data sources, explaining findings as well as formulating recommendations. A crucial consideration when involving stakeholders in the evaluation, starting with its planning, is the necessity of comprehending and embracing cultural diversity as recognizing diversity can enhance the evaluation and make sure that vital constructs and concepts are measured (Principles of community engagement, 2011).

2.12.5.2. Implementation – formative and process evaluation

This step of evaluation may investigate if a program is successfully recruiting and retaining its intended participants, using training materials that reach standards for accuracy and clarity, keeping its forecasted timelines, coordinating effectively with other ongoing programs and activities, and reaching applicable legal standards. Evaluation implementation phase aims to announce mid-course corrections to program implementation (formative evaluation) or to shed light on implementation processes (process evaluation).

2.12.5.3. Completion – summative, outcome and impact evaluation

When the program completes, the evaluation may investigate its immediate outcomes or long-term effect or summarize its overall performance, including its efficiency and sustainability for instance. In this stage, evaluation plays a role in determining the extent to which a change in an outcome can be attributed to such a program. The outcome here can be defined as “*the state of the target population or the social conditions that a program is projected to have changed*” (Principles of community engagement, 2011).

2.12.5.4. Dissemination and reporting

For the purpose of disseminating and reporting the results to all essential audiences in a comprehensive and systematic way, the evaluators need to develop a dissemination plan during the planning step of the evaluation. This plan should comprise guidelines on who will present outcomes, which audiences will receive the outcomes, and who will be included as a co-author on manuscripts and presentations. Dissemination of the program outcomes requires sufficient resources like personnel, time and money. It may be used for building capacity among stakeholders.

When it comes to reporting, in spite of the fact that the content and format of reporting may change depending on the audience, the report should concentrate on full disclosure and a balanced assessment so that results can be used to strengthen the program.

2.12.6. Approaches to evaluation

This section gives information about two main evaluation approaches, namely participatory evaluation and empowerment evaluation, and their purposes as well as their features.

2.12.6.1. Participatory evaluation

In theory, the participatory approach can help enhance program performance in several ways. First, it involves primary stakeholders in evaluation design and decision-making. Second, participatory evaluation acknowledges and tackles with asymmetrical levels of power and voice among stakeholders. Third, it utilizes multiple and varied methods. Fourth, it has an action component so that evaluation findings are useful to the final users of the program. Lastly, the participatory approach explicitly aims to set up the evaluation capacity of stakeholders.

Below are some main features of this evaluation approach:

- It concentrates on participant ownership; the evaluation is oriented to the needs of the program stakeholders rather than the funding agency.
- Participants meet to communicate and make negotiation to achieve a common agreement on evaluation outcomes, face problems and plan to enhance the program.
- All participants seek and recognize the input
- The focus is on identifying lessons learned to facilitate program improvement and determine if goals were obtained
- The design of evaluation is flexible and determined during the process
- It relies on empirical data to identify an outside expert serving as a facilitator

2.12.6.2. Empowerment evaluation

Empowerment evaluation is a way to help guarantee program success by giving stakeholders with tools and skills to assess their program and guaranteeing that the evaluation is one portion of the planning and management of the program. The principal target of this approach is to transfer evaluation activities from an external evaluator to the stakeholders.

The characteristics of this evaluation approach are as follows:

- Assessing the enhancement or progress in employees, programs and companies to help them get results
- Comprising necessary participants from all levels of the program, funders and community
- Democratic participation and clear and open evaluation plans and methods
- Committing social justice and a fair allocation of resources, chances, obligations and bargaining power
- Building the capacity of program staff and participants to enhance their ability to implement their own assessments.

2.12.7. Evaluation methodology

The evaluators usually use three methods of evaluation; they are a quantitative method, qualitative method and the combination of these two methods.

2.12.7.1. Quantitative method

Quantitative data can be collected by questionnaires, pre-tests and post-tests, observation, or review of existing documents and databases or by gathering clinical data. Quantitative data measure the depth and breadth of an implementation. The company uses the quantitative data collected before and after an intervention to demonstrate its results and influence. The advantages of quantitative method for evaluation purposes consist of their generalizability when the sample represents the population, the ease of analysis and their consistency and accuracy if the data are collected reliably.

2.12.7.2. Qualitative method

Qualitative data are collected via direct or participant observation, interviews, specific groups and case studies and from written documents. Qualitative data can be analysed by examining, comparing and contrasting, and explaining patterns. After analysing qualitative data, the result provides contextual data to interpret complex matters. Nonetheless, qualitative data may be lack of generalizability, time-consuming and costly, and the difficulty and complexity of data analysis and explanation.

2.12.7.3. Mixed method (both qualitative and quantitative methods)

In some cases, mixed method of both qualitative and quantitative approach can be the best choice to solve the complicated problems. Nevertheless, the selection of methods should match the need for the evaluation, its time frame, and available resources.

2.13. Evaluation of training effectiveness

2.13.1. Training effectiveness

Training effectiveness can be defined as the “*extent to which training yields desired or relevant outcomes*”. Verification of training effectiveness is required by most of the frequently used management system standards. There is not a single, all-encompassing universally- accepted training effectiveness criterion, nor should there be. Different training programs have different goals and processes, and thus require different measures of training effectiveness.

2.13.2. Training evaluation

Huge investment in training activities requires evaluation to determine and ascertain the effectiveness of training programs (Bramley and Kitson, 1994; Cheng and Ho, 2001; Beardwell, 2004). Training evaluation can be described as systematic and impartial collection of data and analysing information for managers and all other interested parties about a training

programme which can be used to draw conclusions about the effectiveness of particular training measures as a way of achieving organizational objectives, implementing policy and promoting organizational learning (Raab *et al.*, 1991).

James and Roffe (2000:12) provide a simplified explanation of evaluation: “*comparing the actual and real with the predicted or promised*”. Sharing the same viewpoint, Saad and Mat (2011) see training evaluation as a measurement which indicates whether the cost incurred in design matches the associated benefits of implementing a training program.

While carrying out an evaluation, both judgmental and descriptive information may be collected, and the information is required in the development of human resources, especially HRD evaluation (Pineda, 2010). Few judgements are made by those taking part in the program while other judgments are made by those not directly involved in the training program. Evaluation also entails the systematic collection of data based on a pre-determined plan or methodical approach to make sure that appropriateness and usefulness of the information is maintained (Guerci and Vinante, 2011). Finally, evaluation is carried out to help managers, HRD personnel, and employees make an informed decision about specific programs and training methods. For instance, if a training program is not effective it may have to be modified or eliminated, or if any program is instrumental, it can be followed in different parts of the organisation. By way of emphasising on the training purpose and its outcomes, evaluators act as guides to the rationale behind the design of the training program, and potential improvements or changes in learners’ performances resulting out of training (Shenge, 2014). It may be expected that the training program is based on key organisational goals and development efforts. Nevertheless, the association must directly guide the training efforts if the outcomes of training need to be linked to organisational measures.

Training evaluation entails examining the training program, pre and post training. As demonstrated in figure 2-3, HR managers and evaluators consider training evaluation before the actual start of the training.

Figure 2-3: Process of training evaluation

Source: Guerci and Vinante, 2011,p.42

The process of training evaluation starts with the determination of the training needs and needs assessment makes it possible to identify the skills, knowledge, behavioural change or other learned capabilities need to be developed (Pineda, 2010). On identification of the learning capabilities, the subsequent steps in the training process are to determine the explicit, measurable training objectives to direct the training program. Dahiya and Jha (2011) explain that the more explicit and measurable the training objectives are, the convenient it is to acknowledge pertinent outcomes for the training evaluation. Analysing the work environment in an organisation to determine training transfer is useful to decide how training content will be used. On the basis of training objectives and analysis of training transfer, outcome measured can be developed to examine the level to which learning, and transfer have taken place (Tripathi, 2012). After identification of the training outcome, the subsequent step is to determine a strategy for evaluation. Elements such as the need for information, expertise,

organisational culture, potential for change should be recognised in selecting an organisational design. Planning and execution of training evaluation entails previewing the training program (formative evaluation) and obtaining details of training outcomes as per the evaluation design (Stufflebeam and Coryn, 2014). The outcomes of training evaluation are used to amend, market, or gain extra support for the training program. Subsequently, the assessment of each element of the training evaluation process, initiating with the development of outcome measures is undertaken.

2.13.3. Levels of Training Evaluation

Among all the frameworks or conceptual models developed to examine training evaluations, the first and most commonly referenced framework to date is the Kirkpatrick model (Bates, 2004). The Kirkpatrick model has been used in the design of training evaluations in business since the 1960s (Arthur *et al.*, 2003). It forms the basis of various theories in training evaluation and has had a profound impact on other evaluation models developed subsequently. These models may differ from each other in terms of approach, elements, and their application in business, but they share the main core levels. There are six core levels of training evaluation, which are defined as follows:

Level 1- Participant satisfaction

The first level of training evaluation is to determine the opinion of participants on the training received and their extent of satisfaction. The elements that conceive this evaluation level and on which the views of participants are sought include (i) the suitability of training regarding participants' needs and expectations, (ii) accomplishment of goals established by the training, (iii) content quality in terms of its aptness, depth, level, and association between theory and practice, (iv) quality of the training techniques and methods used in terms of variety, suitability, and enjoyment, (v) knowledge of the trainer, skills and competencies at a pedagogical level, (vi) quality of the pedagogical resources such as training documents, manuals, and audio visual

materials, (vii) group climate, prevailing culture and participation, (viii) quality of other resources in the form of training venue, classrooms, infrastructural setup, spaces (Guerci and Vinante, 2011). The scope for implementing knowledge and skills gained at the workplace, and their proposals and suggestions for further improvement.

This level is evaluated virtually by almost every organisation and conducted using questionnaires that participants need to complete post training. Nevertheless, participants' level of satisfaction may also ascertain during training with the aim of bringing in improvements during the training process as an outcome of participants' views (Chuang, 2013). Training assessors may also make use of other evaluation instruments both, during the training as well as post-training. These include spontaneous or informal evaluation by way of questioning the group or questioning few participants individually regarding the extent of their satisfaction about the aforementioned elements (Lee-Kelley and Blackman, 2012).

Cumulative evaluation, i.e. the application of group techniques through which participants are organised in small groups to discuss the pros and cons of the training undertaken. Cumulative evaluation can be undertaken by the trainer or member of the training department to facilitate accessing consenting views on the satisfaction level of the participants with the training (Ahmad and Ud Din, 2009). The trainer may also undertake 'participant observation' to evaluate training which helps to generate a report to be submitted to the training department. Other methods include interviews carried out by the training department with some of the selected participants chosen randomly by the trainer (Saks and Burke, 2012). However, training evaluation relating to this level has various limitations – (i) Firstly, there is need to emphasise the sensitivity of the outcomes to the climate that exist during the training, thereby, a significantly increased satisfaction level can be achieved with insufficient training activities that are, on the other hand, led by the trainer's superior communication and social skills. Secondly, this evaluation level provides the training views as expressed by the participants,

however, fails to report on the key learning gained by the participants or applying such learning gained at the actual workplace. Therefore, organisations following the practice of only evaluating participants' satisfaction do not, in actuality, evaluate training but simply replicate the viewpoint of its immediate clients (Shenge, 2014). The effectiveness of this depends on the way collected information is used and the way it is linked to the outcomes from other levels of evaluation.

Level 2: Learning gained by the participants

This is the second level of evaluation that emphasises understanding what participants, or trainees have learnt at the end. Evaluation at this level assumes that there exist measurable and operational training objectives, which work in the form of an evaluation reference (Saks and Burke, 2012). However, it is essential to acknowledge that training can lead to unexpected learning, which may not be replicated in the proposed goals. The system of evaluation must be designed to facilitate unpredictable learning, which may be tacit, and of significant value to the individuals as well as the organisation. Learning evaluation may take place fundamentally at three phases (Cormier and Hagman, 2014) – (a) at the beginning of the training for the purpose of determining the level of entrance of the participants. This diagnostic evaluation, if undertaken in advance, allows customising the entire training design to meet the actual needs of the participants, therefore, increasing training effectiveness, (b) during training, to identify the pace of participants' learning and bring in improvements to assist them to teach the anticipated level of learning, and finally (c) at the training end, in order to evaluate the results that participant achieve, especially the learning gained from the training session (Cormier and Hagman, 2014). This level of learning evaluation is indispensable as it allows for further assessment with regards to transfer of learning gained to the workplace, which consequently creates interest for the organisation.

Level 3: Pedagogical appropriateness

The third level of training evaluation emphasises on determining the level of interest consistency of the process of training from a pedagogical viewpoint (Pineda, 2010). It investigates the pedagogical aptness in both, training design and delivery so as to accomplish the objectives of the training effectively and efficiently. This level of evaluation is relevant to popular training evaluation models, such as the Kirkpatrick model, and offers an apparent pedagogical orientation, distinguishing it from other models of training evaluation (Praslova, 2010). Therefore, the elements assessed at this level are those associated with the design and implementation of training and its appropriateness for the target group, categorised as follows:

Training objectives - The relevance of training objectives is analysed in accordance to the predetermined needs or expected needs, their aptness at the level of the target group, and the quality and relevance of the training design.

Content - The relevance of content is determined in association to the objectives, its suitability, relevance, level of structuring and accuracy, and the balance between theoretical content and actual practice (AlYahya and Norsiah, 2013).

Methodology – The relevance of methodology is determined in connection to the objectives and the chosen content, the significance of the methods and techniques chosen as priority, appropriateness of the practical methods, and applicability of the methodology.

Human resources- The relevance of human resources is assessed to the training skills of the trainers that is evaluated. The evaluation is with regards to both, knowledge and practical experience of the trainer and other attributes such as group management and pedagogical skills (Aluko and Shonubi, 2014).

Material and functional resources - Their relevance, appropriateness, and spatial quality are evaluated, along with the infrastructure, pedagogical resources, communication equipment, timelines, and other training materials of key importance. The material and functional resources

include key elements, namely participants' questionnaires, trainers' interview, observation, and self-evaluation discussed below-

Participant Questionnaires – Questionnaire can be designed by the training department to collect the views of participants on the pedagogical consistency of the aspects discussed above, which may be conducted at the training end. Instead of formulating a specific questionnaire, various items about this evaluation level can be introduced in the questionnaire on participant satisfaction (Huber, 2011). However, it should be acknowledged that the information collected from the items only provides their views on the appropriateness of pedagogy and should be compared with the outcomes obtained from the use of other instruments.

Trainer interview – Interview is conducted with the trainer by the training department wherein the trainer reflects on the pedagogical appropriateness of the training design and delivery (Shenge, 2014). The interview is directed towards collecting information about the aspects discussed above, and hence occurs at various points, at the preliminary part of the training to administer and adapt the training design, during the training session to monitor training implementation, and post training to evaluate the sufficiency of the undertaken process (Dahiya and Jha, 2011). This type of interview gives useful information and helps in detecting any disparity or unevenness to improve the training.

Observation – Observation is generally undertaken during the course of the training and may be of varying types based on the agent conducting it. The trainer may carry out participant observation relating to the activities associated with training development on one hand, it can be observation of his/her self-performance on the other hand (Jones, Beynon, Pickernell and Packham 2013). The information gathered through such observation can be documented in the form of a report and can be taken up in the final interview with the department of training. The training department may also carry out a systematic observation of the training development which can be recorded electronically, for instance, video, checklist, followed by analysis of the

collected information. Davies and MacKay (2014) point out that given the costs and complexities associated with this kind of observation, is generally set aside for those training activities that necessitate a comprehensive evaluation of their pedagogical aptness.

Self-evaluation – Self-evaluation is conducted by the trainer with regards to training development including the trainer’s performance, which is replicated in a document to be subsequently evaluated by the training department.

These are the key options for assessing the pedagogical aptness and suitability of training. While designing its evaluation plan, the organisation must carefully choose the items of evaluation, tools and timing, agents, depending on its requirements and actual possibilities. This evaluation level provides useful information to the training department and assures the adaptation of the training design to fulfil the organisational needs. It also facilitates introducing key improvements during the process of training and optimises subsequent applications.

Level 4: Transfer

Level 4 emphasises the identifying changes that occur in the workplace as a training outcome. At level two, the learning gained by the trainees as participants is recognised, however, what actually matters to the organisation is not just learning, rather how learning is transferred to the workplace, i.e. how it translates into changing the behaviour of people in the workplace (Pineda, 2010). Evaluating transfer of training implies identifying whether the knowledge, skills and competencies that participant acquire through training can be applied at the workplace and whether it can be sustained with time. Although, all training activities need to pursue training transfer, accomplishing this goal may be difficult and often not guaranteed. However, Dawe, Pena and Windsor (2014) suggest that training need to be directed towards transfer of learning that is engendered and this must be revealed in both, training design as well as training implementation and monitoring. Therefore, training needs to be initiated with a

detailed knowledge of the organisational goals and needs and ingrained within the operational objectives of the firm (Cormier and Hagman, 2014).

Chuang (2013) argues that these objectives would facilitate a successive evaluation of changes evident in the working behaviour of people. In addition, training needs has to be implemented based on a methodology that is realistic, adaptable, aligned with the reality of actual work, and entails strategy to guide and facilitate subsequent transfer. Consequently, training has to examine the mechanisms that operate side by side with evaluation. Training design orientation towards knowledge transfer in this manner is the first requirement needed to achieve transfer of training (Aluko and Shonubi, 2014). However, this also necessitates dynamic involvement of other key agents apart from the trainer, such as the participants, supervisors, and superiors. These play an instrumental role in both, promoting transfer and its assessment, making sure that the learning gained is put to practice. It also helps to eradicate the potential hindrances and obtaining information that makes training evaluation smoother.

The evaluation of training transfer therefore entails various people who play an instrumental role in the execution. The trainers and training experts design the evaluation system, execute and monitor its implementation. Therefore, they seek cooperation from other agents and negotiate their involvement level in the evaluation of transfer (Curado and Martins Teixeira, 2014).

Key role is also played by the participants by way of self-evaluation of their transfer and evaluating the possible hindrances in their environment. The supervisor or line manager of the participants is the key agent who is aware of the participants' daily performances and can evaluate whether any changes have been achieved after training. The colleagues, co-workers and even customers can be important agents at this evaluation stage.

Level 5: Impact

The impact of training implies its effects on the organisation, in terms of meeting the training needs of the employees, problem-solving and contributing to the achievement of strategy business objectives that has been recognised by the organisation (Jones, Beynon, Pickernell and Packham, 2013). Therefore, training impact comprises of the changes taking place with the learning gained through training and how the transfer of knowledge into the workplace impacts the area or department of those trained and the organisation as a whole. The impact of training is acknowledged as the effects of training into the organisation, with the use of the skills and competencies that participants gain from training, and Davies and MacKay (2014) identify two types of effects, namely, (i) qualitative effects that are not translatable into economic/monetary terms, and (ii) quantitative effects that are translatable into monetary aspects.

The impact assessment emphasises on recognising the benefits and outcomes of training to the organisation (Saks and Burke, 2012). Benefits in this context imply the increase in the extent of welfare or usefulness linked with the extent of trainings imparted. The calculation or determination of the benefits emphasises on measuring the training effects by implementing impact indicators which is a measurement unit to recognise the tangible or concrete effects of training in the organisation.

These indicators facilitate the identification, development monitoring, and measuring the impact of training over a specific time period. Impact indicator can be conveyed in different terms (Davies and MacKay, 2014), for instance, (i) conveyed quantitatively as indices, or qualitatively as satisfaction, as period such as provision for service delivery, and as effects such as the use of human resources, materials used.

Level 6: Profitability

The translation of the impact of training into economic terms makes possible the development of a profitability index that can be obtained, and expressed in the form of return in monetary benefits engendered by investment made in the field of training, wherein two main procedures are followed, namely (a) calculation of the costs involved, and (b) calculation of the profitability (Passmore and Velez, 2014)

Calculation of cost is the first step towards carrying out an assessment of training impact and emphasises on recognising the costs involved in the process of training conducted by the organisation. There exists various kinds and categorisation of costs and are generally used in the area of training for organisations as (i) direct costs involving trainers, venue, materials; (ii) indirect costs such as communication, management, administration, design, additional equipment, and (iii) overheads such as general services in the form of asset depreciation, cleaning, and utilities (Passmore and Velez, 2014).

The above-mentioned costs are normally categorised into fixed and variables cost, and this process is extremely useful while designing the training budget, and effective while identifying the overall costs of the different training programs. These calculations help to obtain the overall costs and calculate the investment in training, and funds to be used to arrive at the profitability. Cost calculation is the simplest of all calculations involved in assessing profitability as it simply entails collecting data available in the organisation, generally available in the budgets and economic data linked to training and integrating them together in the needed categories.

Calculating profitability

Once the impact of training with regards to benefits and the training costs are obtained (level 5), profitability of the training program can be ascertained. There exist two procedures for the calculation of profitability, namely, (i) cost-benefit analysis, and (ii) return on investment (ROI). Both procedures intend to get a profitability figure and hence developed on the basis of a cost and benefits involved in the training. The cost-benefit analysis aims to achieve the net

benefit of the trainings, and therefore uses the formula: total benefit-total costs=net benefit. However, the ROI as explicated by Phillips (1994) measures profitability by illustrating the net profit gained on the amount invested in training, i.e. obtaining the profitability index using a specific formula: $ROI = \text{net benefits}/\text{cost} * 100$

According to Hassan (2016), the aforementioned methods for profitability calculation are formed on the basis of comparing costs and benefits, and even though these methods follow varying processes, they intend to ascertain the profitability gained from the training activities carried out. Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart and Wright (2017) consider these calculations are wholly economic, and hence the qualitative aspect is ignored, the significance of which was discussed earlier. Therefore, these outcomes must be added to the non-economic outcomes derived from the benefits calculation (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart and Wright, 2017). However, profitability calculation alone is enormously useful in making decision about the extent of investment to be made in training and provides valuable data.

Review of the extant literature acknowledges five levels of evaluation as discussed in the above paragraphs, however, based on critical analysis of the evaluation approaches. Guerci, Bartezzaghi and Solari (2010) put forward suggestions in the form of suggestive strategies to improve training evaluation in contemporary organisations. Pineda (2010) explains that evaluation imply comparison of results based on predetermined reference, and this reference signifies the situation that the organisation expects to achieve from training and usually laid down in the form of well-defined, measurable, and observable (SMART) objectives. Therefore, objectives need to be designed based on the SMART concept. Topno (2012) suggests that the training evaluation plan must be based on a comprehensive analysis of the existing training material and practical possibilities for its adoption. Therefore, the accessible information must be taken in account along with the resources and tools at hand, the costs involved, and time required. In addition, the evaluation plan needs to be viable and realistic. Devins and Smith

(2013) point out that the evaluation plan should be acknowledged and acceptable to each actor involved in the training evaluation, from participants, supervisors, trainers, and managers. If the agents involved in the evaluation plan do not show consensus with the proposed plan, the plan should be discarded, therefore, participation in the training evaluation is a guarantee for success (Chuang, 2013). Hence, it is feasible to develop a simple evaluation plan consented by everyone involved rather a complicated plan that fails to receive the approval of related others.

2.13.4. The benefits of evaluating training effectiveness

Training researchers and practitioners has widely recognised the essential role of training evaluation. The evaluation of training is necessary as it helps the organization justify (1) whether intended training objectives have been met (Topno, 2012); whether the knowledge and skills learnt during training are transferred in participants' job (Broad and Newstrom, 1992; Nagar, 2009); whether resources allocated for training are used effectively; to assess the value for money of training (Burkett, 2005; Goldwasser, 2001); to continuously improve training in workplace (Kirkpatrick, 1994); to recognise changes in training needs and other aspects of the training context (Reay, 1994); to prove the contribution of the training department to the organizational objectives and goals (Kirkpatrick, 1994)

Evaluation of training also important to trainees (participants) and the trainers (facilitators) as the benefits they receive from training evaluation are numerous. To the trainees, training evaluation helps them to give feedback to their trainers and have resultant adjustments accordingly. With these reflections on training, the trainees have an opportunity to actively engage in this particular training process, and also make further suggestions for future programs. To trainers, training evaluation generates data which are used as a performance indicator for the quality of their training delivery. Based on the feedback, trainers might amend

their training programs in terms of methods, content, and other arrangements in more optimised manner.

Overall, training evaluation plays as the critical link between current training and the future ones and help the organizational training process continuously improved. Training evaluation is considered far beyond an assessment of training effectiveness (Brinkerhoff, 2006). It should be seen as a strategic tool for development.

2.13.5. Challenges of training evaluation

Various research studies on training evaluation provide the evidence that although there are different methods to evaluate training, still training evaluation is the weakest and most under developed aspect of training (Iyer *et al.*, 2009). Indeed, evaluating the training outcomes is challenging task.

Dawson (1995) identified a range of reasons why organizations may not systematically carry out evaluations of their provision, including cost, lethargy, and fear of criticism and difficulty of measurement. Research on training evaluation shows that the main reasons for failure of evaluations are inadequate planning, lack of objectivity, evaluation errors of some sort, improper interpretation and inappropriate use of results. Other issues are failure to train the evaluators on the techniques of evaluation, inappropriate data gathering instrument and focus on unimportant details. The dilemmas around training evaluation are also the lack of evaluation methodology, lack of expertise, and “opaqueness in the measurement criteria” (James and Roffe, 2000:13). Training evaluation is also faced some challenges such as being ignored as it is a time-consuming process (Iyer *et al.*, 2009). People tend to assume the training will simply work, trainers feel threatened by the prospect of an objective evaluation of training and its outcome (Sims, 1993).

2.14. Training evaluation frameworks

In the literature, the model/framework to evaluate training is numerous. In business context, organization will choose appropriate training model to evaluate training effectiveness according to the nature and budgets of the business (Topno, 2012). Some commonly-used models of training evaluation are focused in this study and briefly reviewed in the next sections.

2.14.1. CIRO framework of evaluation

First proposed by Warr, Bird and Rackham in 1970, this framework focuses on four main aspects of training including Context, Input, Reaction, and Outcome (CIRO). Four main aspects are assessed in the following table.

Aspect of training evaluation	Focus
Context (C)	Factors such as the correct identification of training needs and the setting of objectives in relation to the organisation's culture and climate
Input (I)	The design and delivery of the training activity
Reaction (R)	The quality of trainees' experience
Outcome (O)	The achievement gained from the activity at three levels
	<i>Immediate evaluation:</i> individual changes in knowledge, skills & attitude before returning to work
	<i>Intermediate evaluation:</i> individual transferring changes to work
	<i>Ultimate evaluation:</i> departmental or organisational performance in terms of overall results

Table 2-3: CIRO Training evaluation framework

Source: Adapted from War, Bird, and Rackham (1970)

The main strength of the CIRO model is that the objectives (context) and the training equipment (input) are considered. Additionally, the measurements before and after training are also carried out. One criticism of this model is that it does not take behaviours into account, so it is specialized for the use of managerial focused training programmes rather than those for people working at lower levels in the organization (Tennant *et al.*,2002).

2.14.2. CIPP Model of Evaluation

Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (1985) proposed another approach to training evaluation in their book *Systematic Evaluation*. The model encompasses four main measurements including Context (C), Input (I), Process (P), and Product (P), as shown in figure 3.

Figure 2-4: CIPP Evaluation Model

Source: Adopted from Stufflebeam and Shinkfield (1985)

Context evaluation is similar to problem analysis in that it serves as the “planning” information, identifying problems, needs and opportunities in order to develop program objectives. *Input evaluation* provides information regarding the resources that are available and needed in order to achieve identified objectives. *Process evaluation* evaluates whether changes are needed within an organization’s work environment in order to implement, but also measures whether program elements are being implemented as intended. *Product evaluation* focuses on the outcomes of a program or activity and helps administrators determine whether to continue, terminate, modify or refocus (Guskey, 2000).

The CIPP model has the some strengths and limitations. The model was not designed with any specific program or solution in mind; thus, it can be easily applied to multiple evaluation situations. Its comprehensive approach to evaluation can be applied from program planning to program outcomes and fulfilment of core values. The model is well established and has a long history of applicability. However, the model could be said to blur the line between evaluation and other investigative processes such as needs assessment. It is not as widely known and applied in the performance improvement field as other models.

2.14.3. Kirkpatrick’s Model

By far the most widely studied model of training evaluation in contemporary research and commonly adapted in business context is Kirkpatrick’s model (Elliott *et. al*, 2009). This model is also used as fundamental model for the proposed framework of this research. Kirkpatrick (1977) designed a model with four learning outcomes: (1) Reactions; (2) Learning; (3) Behaviour; and (4) Results. The four stages are described in table 2-4.

Stage One – Reaction	How do the participants feel about the program they attended? To what extent are they ‘satisfied customers’?
Stage Two – Learning	To what extent have the trainees learned the information and skills? To what extent have their attitudes changed?
Stage Three – Behavior	To what extent has their job behavior changed as a result of attending the training program?
Stage Four - Results	To what extent have results been affected by the training program? (Results would include such factors as profits, return-on-investment, sales, production quality, quantity, schedules being met, costs, safety record, absenteeism, turnover, grievances and morale).

Table 2-4: Kirkpatrick’s Model of training evaluation

Source: Adopted from Kirkpatrick (1994, p.19)

The reason for the overwhelming popularity of Kirkpatrick’s model in both research and practical context is that it is simple and flexible. The model provides the systematic way and straightforward approach to training evaluation. It is also easily understood and adapted by Human Resource (HR) practitioners to get quick assessment of training effectiveness. Moreover, the four stages are closely correlated as each subsequent stage is predicated upon assessment results at previous stage. Evaluation at four stages together can generate the comprehensive picture of an organization and an individual after training from short-term to long-term; from individuals to organization; and from training environment to working environment; and from intangible to tangible results. The model therefore has been served as a useful fundamental model for training evaluators who germinate a number of other evaluation models (Alliger and Janak, 1989; Kaufman and Keller, 1994; Holton, 1996).

There are, however, some limitations associated with this model. First, the model is critiqued for the omission of main indicators and sufficient guidance on how the four stages can be achieved (Lee and Pershing, 2002). Second, the chain-type connection of four stages is often

broken in practice when stage three and stage four of this model are not often used by organizations. These two stages are not explained properly, and the organizations find it much simpler to focus on the first two levels (Cheng and Hampson, 2008). Third, the model oversimplified training effectiveness as it fails to take into account any intervening variables that impact training effectiveness before, during and after training, such as characteristics of the organization, characteristics of the individuals (Cannon-Bowers, Salas, and Tannenbaum, 1995); contextual factors such as the learning culture of the organization (Tracy, Tannenbaum and Kavanaugh, 1995); the nature of interpersonal support in the workplace (Bates, Holton, Seyler and Carvalho, 2000); the climate for learning transfer (Rouiller and Goldstein, 1993), etc.

According to O'Toole (2009), the Kirkpatrick model has been the most dominant training evaluation framework followed by for-profit organisations in the last three decades. The increasing popularity of this approach is traced to various factors; firstly, the Kirkpatrick model has been successful in addressing the need for training professionals to interpret evaluation in a systematic manner (Bates, 2004). It provides a straightforward mechanism for talking about training results and the types of information required to evaluate the extent to which training has accomplished its objectives. Second, Chuang (2013) claims that information about the outcomes of level four is possibly the most explanatory or valuable information about training that need to be collected. For training department this bottom-line information is perceived as a good fit with the competitive fit orientation of training sponsors. The four level frameworks also provide trainers to derive the outcomes of training in terms of organisational productivity and profitability. AlYahya and Norsiah (2013) argue that this model provides a straightforward, holistic guidance regarding the questionnaire types to be asked to the participants and the criteria that may be suitable. This model lessens the measurement demands for evaluation of training, since it emphasises on four categories of outcome data in four levels

that are usually gathered post training, the model eradicates the need for pre-course measures of learning (Hassan, 2016). Moreover, since inferences about training effectiveness is exclusively based on outcome measures, the four-level model helps to decrease the number of variables with which evaluators of the training program are concerned.

Limitations of the Kirkpatrick model

While the Kirkpatrick model is a dominant evaluation framework that is applicable in most industries and organisations worldwide, it is not free from criticisms. Rajeev, Madan and Jayarajan (2009) argue that the model provides an oversimplified view of training effectiveness that fails to consider individual influences or contextual/environmental influences in training evaluation. Research conducted on a wide-scale basis by researchers such as Kennedy, Chyung and Winiecki (2014) and Stufflebeam and Coryn (2014) have found the presence of a broad range of individual, organisational, and factors associated with training design and delivery that impact evaluation. These factors are largely ignored by the Kirkpatrick evaluation model and thereby its inclusiveness is meant to be questionable. For instance, contextual factors in the form of prevailing culture, behaviour and leadership of the organisation are hardly considered. Moreover, the nature of interpersonal support at the workplace, organisational goals and values, corporate mission, communication and scope for learning transfer are not considered in any level of the model (Reio, Rocco and Smith, 2017). The model unconditionally presumes that examination of these factors is not indispensable for effective training evaluation.

2.14.4. Phillips's ROI Model

In recent practice, the financial approach of training evaluation has been typically focused (Bates, 2004). Phillips (2002) introduced Return on Investment (ROI) as Stage Five to Kirkpatrick's four-stage model of evaluation. This stage focuses on the comparison of the monetary costs of the training programme's implementation with the monetary benefits of

programmes. It is done by collecting data from stage 4- Results, converting the data to monetary values, then comparing them to the cost of the program to represent the return on training investment. In order to calculate ROI, Phillips suggested a seven-step process as illustrated in figure 2-5.

Figure 2-5: Phillips's ROI process

Source: Reed Learning Website

By adding the ROI stage, this model makes Kirkpatrick's four-stage model more complete. However, in practice, organizations apply ROI formulate to assess training effectiveness for a few most popular programs only (Phillips *et al.*, 2001) as they have some potential limitations, which are summarized in the following table.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Strengths	Limitations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provide an elaborate methodology for estimating financial contributions and returns of programs ▪ Provide an additional dimension to Kirkpatrick's four basic categories of training success indicators-ROI ▪ Provide an evaluation approach familiar to many executives across different departments. ▪ Create primarily for training and development interventions, it may be perceived as a reliable approach to evaluation by training departments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intimidate trainers who are not used to dealing with such formulas ▪ Too time-consuming and expensive ▪ Not fully address all important indicator categories of performance improvement interventions in general. ▪ Heavy reliance on subjective estimations may lead to incorrect conclusions about program success.

Table 2-5: Strengths and Limitations of Phillips's ROI Model

Source: Adopted from Guerra- Lopez (2008)

2.14.5. Comparison of studied frameworks/models

The previous sections are dedicated to briefly review four frameworks of training evaluation that are mostly popularized in research and practice context. In an attempt to find the most appropriate model to base this research on, these models are put into comparison as illustrated overleaf.

Model/Framework		CIRO	CIPP	Kirkpatrick's	ROI
Year of propose		1970	1985	1959	1996
Author		Warr, Bird and Rackham	Stufflebeam and Shinkfield	Kirkpatrick	Phillips
Approach		System-based	System-based	Goal-based	Monetary-based
Main elements	<i>Context</i>	x	x		
	<i>Input</i>	x	x		
	<i>Reaction</i>	x		x	x
	<i>Outcome/Result/Product</i>	x	x	x	x

	<i>Process/Learning</i>		x	x	x
	<i>Behaviour</i>			x	x
	<i>ROI</i>				x
Application	Managerial focused training programs	Any training programs	Any training programs	Most popular programs, mainly in manufacturing sector.	
Main strength	Measurement before and after training are considered	Easily applied to multiple evaluation situations	Simple, systematic and straight forward method	An elaborate methodology for estimating financial contributions and returns of programs.	
Main limitation	Behavioural measurement is not considered	The line between evaluation and other investigative processes is blurred	Variables that impact training effectiveness are not considered	Time consuming and expensive process	

Table 2-6: Comparison of four training evaluation models

From the comparison of four models shown in table 2-6, Kirkpatrick's model seems to be the most suitable model for this research to base on as its similarity and flexibility. This model is also revisited and used as the guideline to develop the proposed model in the following chapter.

2.15. Current scenario of training evaluation in manufacturing sector in Vietnam

2.15.1. Overview of manufacturing sector in Vietnam

The systematic economic and political reform launched in 1986, called Doi Moi (Renovation), has transformed Vietnam from an extremely poor country with centrally-planned economy to

a middle- income country with a socialist market economy (World Bank, 2016). With national efforts to speed up the economy recovery and reconstruction over the last three decades, Vietnam’s economy has experienced exceptional growth at average rate of 6.72 percent in the period from 1986 to 2010 (Dang *et al.*, 2010). Vietnam has now become a new manufacturing hub in its region as well as an attractive destination for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows (Diez, 2016).

Among different economic sectors, manufacturing stands out as a dominant player inducing FDI flows into Vietnam. From 1988 to 2014, the manufacturing sector attracted 9,600 FDI projects with the value of \$USD 3,375, accounting for 56 percent of total registered FDI projects (Tran, 2014). The annual growth rate of manufacturing sector is also exceedingly higher than that of the entire economy, which is estimated about two times faster in the period of 1995-2010. The positive growth rate of manufacturing sector is the result of the constant growth of 22 manufacturing subsectors (industries), which are shown in the following table.

VSIC	Industry name	Growth rates (%)			Shares (%)		
		1995-2000	2000-2005	2005-2010	1995-2000	2000-2005	2005-2010
15	Food products and beverages	10.2	14.8	16.0	30.4	26.1	24.5
16	Tobacco products	7.9	15.3	6.1	4.2	3.7	2.5
17	Textiles	10.5	14.8	10.8	6.8	5.8	5.0
18	Wearing apparel	15.6	19.7	16.8	3.8	4.0	4.5
19	Leather, luggage, handbags and footwear	20.8	16.2	11.7	5.4	5.3	4.8
20	Wood and wood products	1.8	17.0	15.8	2.9	2.2	2.2
21	Paper and paper products	15.1	15.8	15.7	2.5	2.4	2.3
22	Publishing, printing and media products	8.7	15.1	12.7	1.6	1.3	1.2
23	Coke, refined petroleum products	10.3	20.5	13.9	0.2	0.2	0.5
24	Chemicals and chemical products	17.0	16.3	17.1	6.7	6.7	6.7
25	Rubber and plastics products	23.3	22.5	15.5	3.4	4.6	5.1
26	Other non-metallic mineral products	14.9	16.6	14.4	11.1	11.5	9.9
27	Basic metals	12.0	18.8	16.6	3.9	3.9	3.8
28	Fabricated metal products	19.9	23.4	22.7	3.4	4.2	5.6
29	Machinery and equipment n.e.c.	15.8	17.2	13.7	1.6	1.8	1.5
30	Office, accounting and computing machinery	232.9	16.9	34.4	0.4	0.7	1.3
31	Electrical machinery and apparatus n.e.c.	27.4	26.7	20.0	1.8	2.9	3.8
32	Radio, television and communication equipment	17.3	14.9	15.5	2.9	2.8	2.5
33	Medical, precision and optical instruments	18.0	11.6	17.5	0.3	0.2	0.2
34	Motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	20.2	33.9	17.8	1.6	2.7	2.8
35	Other transport equipment	31.6	23.4	22.2	2.7	4.1	5.3
36	Furniture; manufacturing n.e.c.	14.9	25.9	17.7	2.4	3.0	4.0
	Total	13.7	17.6	16.3	100	100	100

Table 2-7: Growth rates and shares of manufacturing sub-sectors in Vietnam from 1995 to 2010 *Source: Tran, 2014*

Manufacturing sector is believed to have a sustained growth in the years to come in response of the expansion of international trade.

After Doi Moi (Renovation) reform, manufacturing sector has undergone a significant change in terms of structure and ownership (Tran, 2014).

Regarding to structure, there are rapid growth rate and increased output share of some light consumer industries and durable goods industry such as leather, luggage, handbags and footwear; office, accounting and machinery; other transport equipment, to name a few. From Table 2-7, it is apparent that food products and beverage dominated the manufacturing industry regardless of decrease in share percentage. Meanwhile, some sub-sectors, namely rubber and plastic products, electrical machinery and apparatus, and transport equipment have flourished with nearly double percentage in share value.

Regarding to ownership, there are two significant trends happening in manufacturing sector after Doi Moi reform in 1986. The state-sector suffered from a downward trend while the non-state and FDI sectors had upward trends in their output shares, which depicted figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6: Manufacturing output by ownership from 1995 to 2014

Source: Tran, 2014

It is clear from figure 2-6 that the share of state sector decreased rapidly from 52.1 percent to 15.7 percent in 1995 and 2014 respectively. In contrast, the non-state sector and FDI sector witnessed the upward increase. Significantly, FDI sector made a big increase of output share from 18.1 percent in 1995 to 50.8 percent in 2014. These trends reflect the direct impact of Renovation policy in order to develop a socialist market economy.

2.15.2. Training evaluation in manufacturing sector in Vietnam

One of the critical reasons for the significant growth of Vietnam's economy as well as manufacturing sector after Renovation policy is its human capital. The 90 million Vietnamese are young, with 65% of the population being less than 40 years old. This youthful population is motivated to work and eager to learn and develop professional skills. Furthermore, Vietnam is now in a period known as the *golden population structure*, which means that there is one dependent person for every two working-people. Hence, these demographic conditions create an abundance of labour force.

Some recent research shows that Vietnamese employers clearly value training and appreciate the impact that training can have for their enterprise. Training programmes are offered staff regardless of positions and the training needs are also defined clearly according to the organizational and individual objectives. However, the training evaluation process is mostly ignored or under-developed. The training programs at workplace are assumed to bring positive impacts to the organization. The research carried out by Anh Phan (2008) has examined the training evaluation process in several companies in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam's economic centre. From her research and the author's personal experience as HR Executive in a manufacturing company, there are some significant issues in training evaluation in Vietnamese manufacturing enterprises.

- Focus on training activities only, lack of post-training awareness

- Do not apply consistent and adequate training evaluation system
- Lack of sufficient investment on training evaluation
- Immature skills in the management of training
- Lack of evaluation expertise
- Training executives find training evaluation to be a time consuming and costly process
- Lack of support from management and local authorities

2.16. Summary of Literature review

Training in workplace is important as it benefits both the organization and the employee when training is conducted properly. It is apparent that training does not simply refer to conducting classroom sessions. Indeed, training process should be considered as a cyclical process (Bee and Bee, 1994) with distinct stages. Training evaluation, the final step in the training process, is critical to an organization because it ascertains the effectiveness of training programs and provides indicators for further development. The models/frameworks of training evaluation are numerous. In the limitation of this research, four significant models are examined, namely CIRO framework, CIPP model, Kirkpatrick's four- stage model, and Phillips's ROI model. Based on the comparison of these models, Kirkpatrick's model is chosen to be the fundamental one for this research due to its simplicity and flexibility.

In Vietnam- one of South East Asia's fastest-growing economies - the awareness of training evaluation still remains limited in both academic and business context (Zhu, 2002). The manufacturing sector, the dominant player in the country's economy, also suffers from the same situation. Training evaluation in manufacturing organizations does not receive adequate awareness and support. Inadequate planning, lack of objectivity, improper interpretation and

inappropriate use of results, lack of training expertise are some main challenges facing evaluation process. Therefore, this research is necessary as it not only raises awareness of training evaluation in work place, but also provides the strategic framework for practical application in the context of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam.

The following chapter, research methodology, outlines the key philosophical viewpoint, research approaches and methods of data collection including sampling techniques to select the research subjects to take part in the study.

CHAPTER 3:

RESEARCH

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

The current chapter carries out a brief discussion of the various research methodologies that can be followed to conduct the research and justifies the choice of the most appropriate ones. Included in the discussions are the various philosophical viewpoints that are contrasting in nature, research approaches, and types of investigation. The approaches include discussion of inductive and deductive approaches, and explaining the types of enquiries conducted by exploratory, explanatory and descriptive research. The importance of research methods and design, particularly quantitative and qualitative data collection methods are also discussed with the relative advantages and disadvantages of each. The chapter provides brief discussion of the various data collection strategies and instruments that could be relevant to the current study. However, the selection of the most appropriate data collection methods, sampling, instrument for data collection, and analysis technique is discussed with specific justification.

The research onion designed by Saunders *et al.* (2009) is followed to get step- by- step guidance to choose the relevant elements in the methodology designed for this research. Peeling and unfolding each layer of the onion starting from the outermost layer helps to reach the innermost layer of the onion ‘data collection and analyses’ based on which the findings and consequent conclusions can be given.

Figure 3-1: Research Onion

Source: Saunders *et al.* (2009)

3.2. Research Philosophy

Philosophy is shown in the outermost layer in the research onion. Philosophy in a research reflects the beliefs, values and mind-set of the researcher who has different worldviews about phenomena (Morgan, 2007). The key philosophical standpoints discussed in the current research are pragmatism, positivism, Interpretivism and realism wherein each has its own assumptions and beliefs.

3.2.1. Pragmatism

From a pragmatist viewpoint, researchers aim at employing ‘what works’ using a range of approaches and methods, discarding that a particular approach is necessary to conduct research to resolve the research problems. Pragmatism gives key importance to the research problems and questions to be answered and giving value to both objective and subjective knowledge (Bridges, 2010).

The followers of pragmatism choose to implement theories and methods that are appropriate in explicit contexts (for instance, finding specific answer to practical problems) rather than those that signify underlying truths about the nature of reality (Uddin and Hamiduzzaman, (2009). They oppose the positivist viewpoint, and/or the assumptions made by scientific realists who suppose that there exists objective truth and that the world is unhindered by the socio-cultural influence and subjective biases (Peters, 2012).

Pragmatic researchers also acknowledge that scientific investigation is contextual in nature and that the past, historical and present situations strongly influence the research process. Bridges (2010) argues that pragmatic researchers assess the research findings on the basis of their social, practical, and ethical outcomes and their behaviour on the human situation. The problems to be investigated or analysed and finding concrete answers to the research questions are considered to be more important than following a specific mind-set based on the philosophical assumptions and beliefs (Kuipers, 2013). Therefore, pragmatist researchers characteristically consider two or more research methods that may be suitable to the explicit research questions being asked while at the same time considering the consequences of such enquiry (Rubadeau, 2015).

3.2.2. Positivism

Positivism is a philosophical approach to social research that tends to follow the natural science method to enquiry about any social phenomena and events relating to the social world (Neuman, 2003). Investigation using natural science and scientific principles are considered appropriate to study the social world around (Morgan, 2007). This philosophy assumes that trends, patterns, methods, generalisations, procedures, cause-and-effect as followed in natural science are also relevant for social sciences (Bridges, 2010). The followers of positivism also

consider that the objects of social science, such as 'people' are suitable to adopt scientific methods to investigate about social phenomena.

According to Saunders *et al.* (2009) researchers following a positivist approach prefer to work with social realities that are observable, and such research studies can generate generalisations which are analogous to the generalisations generated by natural scientists. The followers of positivism also assume that objective realities are external to the individual experiences of people with its own cause-and-effect relationships.

Researchers following the positivist viewpoint consider appropriate to espouse a distant, isolated, non-interactive and neutral position (Saunders *et al.* 2009). Such position also makes it possible for the researcher to accept the role of an objective analyst, thereby making isolated explanation about the ideas that are obtained in an evidently value-free manner (Uddin and Hamiduzzaman, 2009). This is the reason why positivist researchers prefer a methodical interpretation of numerical data. Positivism also assumes that knowledge that is valid can only be generated based on direct observation by human senses, and this would entail that ability of the researcher to evaluate and confirm what can be perceived as knowledge (Kuipers, 2013). In this context, observation implies embracing only empirical evidences to be valid and valid evidence is generated through the sense of smell, sight, taste, touch and hearing. This clearly indicates that there exists no place for any phenomena that may not be subject to observation, either directly through experiences or by way of observation, or indirectly using instruments (Saunders *et al.*, 2015). The followers of this philosophy mainly carry out quantitative research to test theoretical assumptions based on statistical data testing.

3.2.3. Realism

Realism as a philosophical assumption generally integrates the values of positivism and interpretivism (Peters, 2012). The concept of realism embraces the existence of reality, which

is not dependent on human mind, beliefs and behaviour. Nevertheless, it concedes that gaining an understanding of people and their behaviour necessitates recognising the subjectivity that is inherent in people (Kuipers, 2013). From the perspective of realism, the existence of social processes is not within the control of people and this affect human beliefs and behaviour (Rubadeau, 2015). These processes usually operate at the macro-level (that is, the level of individuals) and subjective analysis of reality is imperative for understanding what actually is happening.

Harwell (2011) explains the social world in association with three inter-related philosophical beliefs that support the different paradigms, namely, epistemology (the science related to knowledge); ontology (what humans believe); and, methodology (the science of enquiry). Thomas (2010) argues that researchers, who perceive their world realistically, usually embrace the fundamental doctrines of natural sciences and social sciences to be identical. Empirical substantiation serves as the evidence for valid knowledge, however, in itself is not adequate.

Saunders *et al.* (2015) verify that the main objective of this philosophical viewpoint is to go beyond the explanation of relationships and to ascertain how such relationships came into existence. The followers of realism also suppose and assert that the social world needs to be understood in its entirety. This implies that all the aspects of social world are affected by the realities of the other parts. With regards to collecting data, Neuman (2014) suggests the use of in-depth interviews and focus groups to obtain valid and reliable data that align with the ideology of realism.

3.2.4. Interpretivism

Interpretivism is opposed to positivism and aims to understand the viewpoints and perceptions of individuals relating to phenomena (Neuman, 2003). It is also known as phenomenological approach to research. The philosophy of Interpretivism emphasises the exploration of the

complexities of social events in order to gain a holistic understanding of the phenomenon being studied (Bridges, 2010). The followers of Interpretivism aim to understand and interpret daily events, experiences, happenings, and social structures, and the values that individuals attach to events (Uddin and Hamiduzzaman, 2009). The followers of this ideology consider social reality to be nuanced and subjective in nature as it is shaped by human participants, and the aims and values of the researcher (Kuipers, 2013).

According to Bryman and Bell (2011), Interpretivism is directed on the understandings and meanings of the social interactions between humans. As a result, the human mind interprets the events and experiences and builds meaning from them. Supporting the interpretivist viewpoint, Harwell (2011) rejects the assumption that the use of social science and its principles should be implementable for social research to produce objective based outcomes. Interpretivists also assume that understanding of the social world is not possible by implementing research doctrines espoused natural sciences. The philosophy of interpretivism entails three basic principles (Saunders *et al.*, 2015); that the social world is constructed, and individuals give subjective meaning to its existence. Interpretivism also considers that human being as research subjects possess consciousness, and human behaviour is influenced by knowledge they possess about the social world that exist in association with human beings. Interpretivism assumes that research is driven by human interests and the researcher undertaking the study is a part of what needs to be observed.

Interpretivist researchers also point out that simple fundamental laws and assumptions cannot be applied to explain the complexities involved in social phenomena (Kuipers, 2013). Interpretivists also assert that objective observation of the social world is not possible as its meanings are for human beings only and is built with the help of intentional behaviour and actions (Rubadeau, 2015). Interpretivists view the social world as something that can be produced or reproduced on an everyday basis by individuals and their understanding. As

opposed to the positivist viewpoint of observing through senses, the followers of Interpretivism try to make sense of what is happening or occurring in a social context (Rubadeau, 2015). They make attempts to interpret subjective realities and put forward explanations that of meaning to the research participants.

3.2.5. Justification for the paradigms and methodology

After evaluating several philosophical standpoints, pragmatism was considered suitable for the current study because it undertakes mixed methods to data collection by combining quantitative and qualitative data. Pragmatism helped to follow a practical approach to resolving the research problems by discarding the differences between two opposing worldviews, namely positivism and interpretivism (Neuman, 2014). Following the philosophical standpoint of pragmatism helped the researcher to maintain a holistic approach to data collection and collect in-depth information that underpins the research problems. The researcher in this study maintained a pragmatist worldview to build upon the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative data, and eliminate the weaknesses of each (Cresswell, 2014). With a pragmatist mind-set the researcher collected quantitative data from the employees of a few manufacturing firms in Vietnam by conducting an online survey while qualitative data was collected by interviewing the human resource managers of the same companies.

3.3. Research Approach (Deductive versus inductive approach)

Research approach is the subsequent layer in the **research onion** after philosophy, as designed by Saunders *et al.* (2009).

3.3.1. Inductive approach

Creswell (2002) explains that in case of inductive reasoning, the research who acts as an observer should not be biased, and should honestly record what is observed. Based on these

observations, laws and theories can be constructed in order to build the scientific knowledge. Researchers following the inductive research also assume that one can rationally generalise the observations into comprehensive rules and verify the scientific assumptions (Kothari, 2004).

The inductive approach is usually followed by researchers with an interpretivist mind-set who look for developing patterns based on key observations and developing theories for the identified patterns through hypothesis (Peffer *et al.*, 2007). In case of inductive reasoning, it is not necessary to use theoretical assumptions in the beginning of the study and the researcher follows an information investigation to decide the course of action (Bricki and Green, 2007). The use of observation is made by the researcher to develop an abstract or explain the circumstances or events being studied. Inductive approach is suitable for conducting exploratory studies where very little is known about the research problems and the use of qualitative methods is used to further investigate using deeper analysis into the problems. However, Kothari (2012) criticise inductive approach because the results of such studies are often influenced by researcher's bias, context of the study, and the subjective data shared by the human subjects.

3.3.2. Deductive approach

The deductive approach, as opposed to the inductive process, involves developing an assumption on the basis of existing theories to form a research plan to test such assumption (Ketchen *et al.*, 2008). In case of deductive approach, results are deduced from the outcome of the study which is objective in nature. Applying the deductive approach in a research study helps the researcher to design a set of hypotheses that require testing, followed by the use of appropriate methodology to test the hypothesis (Jansen, 2010). The deductive approach includes definite characteristics to be understood. Based on the hypothesis accepted in the research key conclusions are arrived at after testing theory. The aim of theory testing in deductive approach is to examine whether a particular theory is applicable in a particular

situation or circumstance being studied (Peffer *et al.*, 2007). Deductive approach is usually followed by researchers having a positivist mind-set intending to test theoretical assumptions through statistical data testing using a scientific approach (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Argumentation in case of deductive approach initiates with theoretical underpinnings and leads to new assumptions, which is tested by way of comparison with the observation and eventually accepted or rejected (Cresswell, 2014). Moreover, deductive arguments may also be explained as moving from general to specific process.

3.3.3. Justification for choosing inductive approach

This research starts with the literature review of training evaluation concepts and related issues. These valuable academic resources provide the better understanding of the research topic before examining the real business context. The inductive approach was suitable for the current research because the scope for theory testing was limited in the current and the requirement was to develop new knowledge in an unknown context. For instance, it was necessary to determine the most effective training and evaluation framework for manufacturing sector in Vietnam, after identifying the existing human resource problems, gaps in the training and evaluation policies and practices, and training programs. This area was not adequately researched earlier and hence the research problems were unknown. Hence, an exploratory research was undertaken to identify the background of the problem and ‘inductive approach’ was the key to collect extensive data to study the background, understand the data pattern, form the research questions, and develop new theory (Bricki and Green, 2007).

The research followed the inductive approach and initiated it with detailed observation and review of the underpinning theories relating to training and evaluation, followed by collecting empirical data to identify the training and evaluation methods, types, and strategies in Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, study the patterns of data to analyse whether training and evaluation is appropriate, and then suggest a conceptual effective training and evaluation

framework. Therefore, the inductive approach helped to generate meanings from the collected data set to understand patterns and relationships, and finally develop a theory.

Follow the above structure, the inductive reasoning is the most appropriate approach to achieve the research objectives. The inductive approach is illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 3-2: Inductive approach

Source: Adopted from Saunders et al. (2007, p.21)

According to the inductive approach, the final outcome and proposed theory/framework is presented after the picture of a phenomenon is being studied (Lodico *et al.*, 2010).

3.4. Strategies

The next layer in the research onion includes the ‘strategies’ such as survey, experiments, case study, action research, ethnography which help to collect data. These are discussed in the following section.

3.4.1. Documentary materials

These comprise both primary documents from the companies under research and training providers directly related to the firms’ training activities, but also the secondary ones from various sources like Vietnam General Statistical Office, Department of Planning and Investment, industry reports, and legal documents relating to the last 2-3 years. These documents provide valuable information and knowledge about the socio-economic, business and legal context in general as well as the operating environment of the firms in particular.

Besides, they can provide evidence of firm performance and individual trainees' productivity. The training related activities and the learning transfer process will be examined in light of those collected documents.

3.4.2. Observation

Another important data collection method is from observation which refers to direct access to the research context. In this research, observation method will be taken before, during and after the training programs are delivered. This method is necessary to gain the straightforward viewpoint in some cases such as how the training is delivered and evaluated and what the participants' changes after training. However, observation sometimes generates biased data as the presence of the observer affects the final outcomes. However, it was not possible to conduct observation in this research as permission for the same was not allowed.

3.4.3. Questionnaires

Questionnaires are also useful method to gain a wealth of descriptive data in a comparable format. This method is believed to enable the researcher to obtain the foundation of the business context as well as training outcomes. When possible, quantitative data are collected within a case by questionnaires administered to the trainees, peers and direct supervisors. A wealth of descriptive data in comparable format from this instrument may enable the researcher to obtain a foundation of the business context (e.g. level of supervisor-trainee communication about a pilot project to apply new skills) as well as training outcomes (e.g. number of attempts to apply new skills). Within a case, given a rather common business environment, when information is needed on perceived values of training or rating the difficulties in learning transfer, questionnaires may provide quantitative data appropriate for analysing and identifying issues of concern from the trainees' perspective.

3.4.4. Survey

Survey is a data collection strategy mainly used in exploratory research to collect comprehensive data from a relatively large sample size. However, Lodico, Spaulding and Voegtle (2010) consider survey as a data collection method equally relevant for both exploratory and descriptive methods. Moreover, survey can be implemented to collect both, quantitative and qualitative data, using different patterns of questionnaires. For instance, the use of structured and close-ended questionnaires is usually made in surveys involving quantitative data collection while structured or semi-structured, open-ended questionnaires are suitable for surveys involving qualitative data collection (Choy, 2014).

Survey in quantitative research fulfils dual purpose of describing the explicit characteristics of population being interrogated and using the data to reach measurable or objective based results. Survey is flexible in nature, as it can be conducted both online and offline, and helps to collect large volumes of data from a large sample size. Survey can also be conducted from samples scattered across wide geographical locations using online techniques such as emails, or distribution of survey forms using social media. The following are the advantages and disadvantages of conducting survey.

Advantages	Disadvantages
Easy to conduct, cost effective	Low response rate
Data collection in large volume	Difficult to collect subjective data, especially when structured surveys are undertaken
Offers flexibility to collect data either offline or online or using both methods	Researcher cannot interact closely with the respondents to build rapport

Table 3-1: Advantages and disadvantages of conducting survey

Source: Choy (2014)

3.4.5. Interview (Qualitative data collection method)

Interview is a feasible method in an attempt to get an in-depth understanding of the business context. Interviewing is particularly popular with qualitative researchers to obtain the treasured qualitative data (Allwood, 2012). Interviews will be used extensively as the major data collection method for this research. Along with the case study methodology, interviews are of an open-ended nature (Yin, 2014) as the nature allows the interviewees to mention freely what they consider succinct and relevant to the concerned issues rather than confine themselves into limited answering options. Besides what is discussed, the attitudes and non-verbal signals of the respondents are also captured and can reveal substantial information for judgment of the importance of the issues. This is considered useful and essential in the Vietnamese high-context communication culture. By using face-to-face interviews, the exploratory and descriptive aspects of all four research questions will be addressed.

In this research, semi-structured interviews and in-depth interviews with senior managers were employed. To preserve the open nature of interview and to retain the focus of the research issues at the same time, semi-structured group interviews are conducted for both trainers and trainees to find out their personal opinions of training, training evaluation, and any concerned issues. While such interviews let the interviewees expand upon their answers, they also allow the interviewers to probe for more information at crucial points, to ensure the total aspects of an issue or sub-unit are covered, and to maintain uniform structure across cases.

In-depth interviews are conducted in hope of getting the managerial viewpoint in terms of their current HR policies, training procedures, training evaluation method if applicable, and their willingness for applying new training evaluation tool.

A blend of data collection methods employed in this research is believed to generate the most accurate and comprehensive quantitative and qualitative data. These two methods of collecting

data are convinced to expand the scope of research and to offset the weaknesses of either approach alone (Blake, 1989; Roseman and Wilson, 1991).

The following are the advantages and disadvantages of interview.

Advantages	Disadvantages
High response rate	Time consuming, often expensive
Helps to collect rich, in-depth, subjective information	High complexity involved in analysing subjective data through coding
Researcher as interviewer can directly participate, interact, build rapport, and clarify doubts	Chances of inclusion of researcher's bias is high

Table 3-2: Advantages and disadvantages of conducting interview

Source: Roseman and Wilson (1991); Yin (2014)

3.5. Choices (Research Methods)

After the Strategies layer, the next layer includes the choices comprising of different methods to collect data.

3.5.1. Qualitative versus Quantitative methods

According to Bryman (2006), research methods relate to a strategy of investigation that moves from the basic assumptions to research design, and then data collection. Even though there exist several distinctions in the area of research methods, the most common categorisation is quantitative and qualitative. On a specific level, quantitative and qualitative method relates to the differences regarding the nature of knowledge; how each approach interprets the world and the eventual purpose of each (Newman and Benz, 1998). However, on a different level of discussion, qualitative and quantitative methods refer to opposing modes of research, in the

way data is collected and interpreted, and the nature of generalisations drawn from the data (Peffer *et al.*, 2007).

Sale *et al.* (2002) explain that quantitative methods are used in the field of natural sciences to study and interpret natural phenomena. On the other hand, qualitative methods are followed by researchers in the field of social science to help researchers understand social and cultural phenomena. Both methods find their application in research relating to education, however Ketchen *et al.* (2008) considers neither of them to be intrinsically superior to the other; and the appropriateness of which depends on the context, nature and purpose of the study. Qualitative research takes place in natural settings and attempts to study the daily life, behaviour and attitude of individuals, groups, communities, and the society at large (Saunders *et al.*, 2009).

According to Allwood (2012) qualitative methods were in the beginning developed in the field of natural science to examine natural phenomena. Qualitative research is mainly conducted by researchers following an interpretivist worldview and an inductive process to knowledge creation as a research outcome. It is mainly undertaken in social research to discover by exploring the issues in hand, especially when the researcher has very limited knowledge about the problems in question. Qualitative studies are undertaken by researchers to ensure they gain an in-depth understanding of the research subjects, views, opinions, and perceptions in their natural setting.

Quantitative method is mainly deductive in nature (Cresswell, 2014). The researcher in a quantitative research is mainly an objective observer who neither takes part in the study nor influences the phenomena being studied. Quantitative methods provide numerical information or data that is usually collected using predesigned or pretested instruments.

Quantitative research is generally undertaken to measure variables and test concepts and assumptions on a sample of subjects (Cresswell, 2014). It also helps to convey the relationship

between a set of variables by making use of statistical underpinnings such as relative frequencies, correlations, or differences between the means, with the main objective of testing theory. Researchers conducting quantitative research are usually follow a positivist viewpoint of observing social realities through senses, conduct testing using predetermined instruments, and arrive at measurable outcomes that are objective (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). The research process is also deductive, implying that the research starts with theoretical studies, hypothesis building, data collection and testing, and eventually theory confirmation/rejection. The method to collect quantitative data is survey and the justification for choosing this method is discussed in point 3.7. However, a range of data collection methods is discussed in the following section.

3.5.2. Mixed methods

3.5.2.1. Practical use of 'mixed methods' in exploratory design

In the current exploratory research, the use of mixed methods for data collection was made in a scientific manner. As Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) suggest, mixed methods' exploratory research follows should entail two distinct phases to collect empirical data, namely, (i) phase one includes the collection of quantitative data using surveys or questionnaires designed on the basis of variables and concepts studied in conceptual review, and (ii) phase two involves collection of rich, in-depth information to carry out subjective inferences of the meanings that the subjects attach to events, or phenomena. Qualitative information obtained from the managerial interviews from the manufacturing organizations (Vard Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam) were used to back-up, cross-verify and therefore triangulate the figurative data obtained from the employee surveys.

In spite of, characteristically stressing on the qualitative element, including the quantitative component in an exploratory design contributes to better identification of research problems, data validation, and new knowledge development. However, mixed methods are not free from

constraints; collection of qualitative data followed by quantitative lead to increased complexity, expense, and requires considerable time.

3.5.2.2. Justification for implementing mixed methods

The use of mixed methods was used in this thesis for data collection, i.e. by integrating two distinct methods, quantitative and qualitative. Researchers following the pragmatist worldview generally discard the differences between any two approaches, such as inductive or deductive, or data collection methods (Schensul, 2011). The rationale for using mixed methods is that it helps to generate broader and deeper insights, enhance the implication of data interpretations, and strengthen the collaboration and convergence of the findings, and gain deeper clarification into underlying logic (Creswell, 2007). The advocates of mixed methods in a social research such as Harwell (2011) suggest that blending quantitative and qualitative data strengthens the process of triangulation of empirical data. This integration also makes possible better interpretation of the correlation between the variables; and combining qualitative and quantitative data facilitates cross verification and validation of data obtained from each method.

The main purpose of combining qualitative and quantitative data in a single research in context of the current thesis is to:

- (i) Enhance the research validity by congregating both methods, as mixed methods help in better triangulation of empirical data.
- (ii) Broaden the research scope requires using mixed methods to enhance both the range and breadth of the study
- (iii) Harmonise different dimensions of the research investigation due to the overlapping that take place between the various methods (Choy, 2014)

3.6. Time Horizon

This layer talks about the timelines of the project, which may be cross-sectional or horizontal.

Cross-sectional research - In case of a cross-sectional research a particular phenomenon is examined at a specific time period. In case of cross-sectional study, a sample of population is studied at a particular time rather than the study extended over a prolonged period.

Longitudinal research- In case of a longitudinal research a particular phenomenon is examined in different phases of time. The study may be on the same sample on different samples of a population over an extended period of time. This helps to identify the changes in the perceptions of the participants that may occur with time.

3.7. Data collection and Analysis

This is the last layer of the research onion, which reflects the final stage of the methodology. This layer focuses on the actual data collection by implementing strategies meant to collect quantitative data, qualitative data or mixed methods.

In this study, the mixed method was implemented. Therefore, quantitative data was collected by implementing survey as the strategy while qualitative data was collected by interviewing the managers of the chosen companies. The justification for data collection using survey and interviews are discussed in the subsequent section.

3.7.1. Justification for quantitative data collection (survey)

Quantitative data was collected in order to seek the attitudes, beliefs, and awareness of the employees with regards to the training approaches, evaluation frameworks, types of evaluation and its benefits. The operational level employees were mainly the ones who received training that were evaluated, and feedback was given accordingly. Quantitative data helped to test the

theoretical underpinnings, mainly the concepts and variables studied in the literature review. The figurative data obtained from the survey helped to measure the significance of each variable in context of the chosen organisation chosen for case study.

Survey was the most feasible strategy to reach a large sample size (Lodico *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, survey was conducted from 372 employees of three different manufacturing companies chosen as case study organisations. Survey helped to collect voluminous data from using questionnaires as the instrument. Survey was found to be inexpensive as well as suitable to collect high volumes of data in a limited period of time.

The questionnaire designed for the survey involved structured and closed ended questions. Most of the questionnaires were designed using five-point Likert scale to capture the beliefs and attitudes of employees on a fixed range of scale (Brown, 2011). The survey forms were distributed using online tools such as Google forms to reach the participants in different locations in Vietnam. Regular reminders on a weekly basis were given to send the surveys back after filling up the questionnaires. The surveys were received back from the respondents in different time periods and collected in a dedicated folder in a password protected computer. The questionnaires were designed by the researcher based on the research problems, objectives/ research questions formulated in the first chapter.

3.7.2. Justification for Qualitative data collection (Interview)

This research followed the inductive approach to theory building and the type of enquiry was exploratory, which made it feasible to collect qualitative data that is subjective in nature. Qualitative data provides elaborate, narrative information reflecting the views, insights, and perceptions of human subjects, and this was necessary to understand the existing HRM policies and practices relating to training and evaluation in the chosen context - Vietnamese manufacturing organisations.

Interviewing is a socially accepted and natural way of collecting data, and a tool used in social science to facilitate direct interaction with the human subjects. As compared to other qualitative data collection strategies such as focus group, observation, and ethnography, interview is inexpensive, easier to conduct, and helps to collect comprehensive data from a relatively small sample size (Harwell, 2011). The response rate is higher in interview and helps the researcher to build rapport with the participants, probe deeper into the research problems, cross-question and get the emerging doubts cleared, and exchange information.

In this research, interview was scheduled with six (06) human resource managers and supervisors of three chosen companies (VARD Vung Tau, BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam). Two HR managers and supervisors working within human resource department from each Vietnamese manufacturing organisation were targeted for interview. The interview questions were open-ended, semi-structured questions and seek to understand the HR policies and policies associated with the training and evaluation programs in the organisation. The interview questions were about the types of training programs, frequency of training, and evaluation programs associated with such training, the benefits, and practical challenges faced. Interview allowed the participants to express their views, and experiences, support their claims with examples, and respond to open ended questions in an overt manner. After sending emails and several calls to book an appointment with the managers, three of them could not arrange the meetings. One was on a long business trip oversea, the others had urgent meetings on the date so they cancelled the appointments with the promise to reschedule the meetings. However, due to their busy schedule, the interview with them was not conducted. Luckily, three managers, one from each company, successfully attended the interviews and they did have wonderful time sharing their experience and opinions. They are all experienced HR managers who have been working for their companies for 5-10 years and played a

significant role in developing their organisational human resource in general and training in particular.

A total of 7-8 questions were asked in the interview, and it is expected that each interview will last for approximately 30-40 minutes. Recording of the conversation during the interview was not be allowed, and hence the transcripts were prepared to document the responses provided by the participants. The interview questions were designed by the researcher based on the research objectives and questions formulated in the first chapter to conduct the investigation. Few interview questions were similar to the questions asked in the survey to ensure that the findings from both, survey and interview can be cross- examined and verified.

To avoid possible bias in the information provided by three HR managers attending the interviews for their opinions on how effective the evaluation models they had employed were, 10 short calls were conducted privately and randomly among their employees. These calls were valuable in providing additional conformation of their HR managers' viewpoints upon the company's training evaluation effectiveness. The employees who answered the phone had no ideas of being interviewed and that was the moments of truths. They were contacted out of working time so they were not influenced by the others. The questions were simple and mostly YES/NO question so they did not find it hard to answer. They were also promised to keep their answer anonymous so they did not hesitate to share their opinions.

3.8. Population and Sampling

A research population is generally a large collection of individuals or objects sharing similar characteristics and acts as the main focus of a scientific query (Krieger, 2012). In this research, the population is all employees in three research companies VARD Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam which is 3,640 employees (Company websites, 2018)

Sampling is a systematic process that includes the selection of specific subset of a target population to generate statistical or non-statistical inferences from them and understand the characteristics of the entire population. Sampling in case of research studies involve probability and non-probability sampling, in which the former include selection based on chance, and the possibility for each individual in a given population to be selected is known (Sminia, 2009). In case of non-probability sampling, the possibility that each individual will be selected is not known as potential bias. Main classifications of probability sampling include simple random, stratified random, systematic random, multistage sampling, and cluster sampling (Sminia, 2009). Meanwhile, non-probability sampling includes various techniques such as quota sampling, convenience sampling, purposive sampling and snowball sampling.

Also termed as representative sampling, probability sampling is appropriate for survey- based study which necessitates researches to make conclusions from a specified sample (Mamabolo, 2009). Probability sampling processes generally initiate with acknowledging a proper sample frame, discern the correct sample size, choose the relevant sampling process. To ensure that the chosen sample is proper representative of the target population, the following criteria are taken into concern:

- Age: above 20 years old (when they are mature enough to give their own opinions)
- Year of service: more than 1 year (to make sure that they have undergone different types of training within a year)
- Education: qualified with training centre/college/university degrees (they all have adequate knowledge about the nature of training)
- Departments: from all departments and expertise
- Advice from HR and other managers (to eliminate the inappropriate participants who do not meet all the above criteria)

These criteria were followed to allow equal opportunity and unbiased selection on a random basis. A good maximum sample size is usually around 10 percent of the population and as long as it does not exceed 1,000 (Suresh and Chandrashekara, 2012). The population of this research is 3,640 employees so the targeted sample size is about 364 employees.

The chosen sample size is 400 employees with the estimation of errors. This sample size is considered as a good one as it closes to the targeted one. 400 questionnaires were sent to the participants in the targeted sample in 3 days. 372 participants sent their answered questionnaires back correctly. The response rate is quite high, about 93 percent.

The sampling process to choose six (06) human resource managers, two (02) from each manufacturing organization to take part in the interview was non-probability, purposive sampling. This allowed the researcher to intentionally choose the managers working in HR department in each manufacturing organisation for at least 3 years. This is to ensure that the managers are familiar with the HR policies and practices related to training and evaluation, having knowledgeable about it, and they are willing to answer the questions during the interview.

3.9. Pilot study

According to Creswell (2002) pilot study is an initial, small scale research undertaken by the researcher to examine the appropriateness of the actual primary research to be carried out at a future date. It also helps to identify the potential flaws and deficiencies in the existing design of the proposed field research and do the rectifications before conducting the actual study (Ketchen *et al.*, 2008). Pilot testing facilitates the researcher to detect any short comings in the design of the questionnaire prepared for the survey or interview in terms of its layout, sequence, and use of phrases, understand ability, and the time taken to complete the exercise (Cooper *et al.*, 2006). On the basis of the given feedback, the questionnaires can be edited, and re-edited,

the structure and layout of the questionnaires can be changed and re-designed to arrive at the final draft.

Pilot study in the current research was carried out by distributing the questionnaires prepared for the survey to at least 65 employees of the manufacturing firms in Vietnam who were part of the actual sample to be surveyed. However, out of these 65 employees 42 returned the questionnaires fully completed with their comments, suggestions, and feedback on the amendments that were required. Based on the results of the pilot testing major improvements were made in the wordings of the questionnaires, removal of difficult words and jargons, and overall length to ensure that the survey was not very lengthy and could be completed in a limited time.

One of the main advantages of pilot study is that it makes it possible to maintain the research validity. By removing the flaws and shortcomings of the questionnaire design it ensures that the participants have complete understanding of the questionnaires and give appropriate response according to their knowledge and perceptions. This in turn eliminates the possibility of inappropriate responses shared by the participants, increases the strength and quality of the findings and thereby enhance its validity. Therefore, the likelihood of measuring what the research actually intended to measure was more and hence the validity. From a broader perspective, pilot study also helps to remove the ambiguity that the participants or the researcher has in relation to the questionnaires set and design and therefore evading any risks associated with project failure. It also helps to understand whether the planned statistical tests to be carried out (if any) on the overall data will be feasible in terms of its application. Therefore, pilot testing of the questionnaires helps to decrease the extent of any unexpected problems that can arise, much before the actual enquiry and enhance the chances of project success

3.10. Delimitations of the study

Delimitations are the elements that define the research boundaries and constrain the scope of the research undertaken (Choy, 2014). However, delimitations are within the researcher's control. It incorporates the choices that a researcher makes with regards to the theoretical underpinnings, conceptual models to be reviewed, and variables of interest, location and population to be studied, and the formulation of research questions to be answered. Often the primary delimitation is the choice of the topic/theme itself surrounded by the research problems. In this research, the delimitations were the selective use of training evaluation models for critical review such as the CIPP model, CIRO model, Phillips ROI model, Kirkpatrick model while other evaluation models were excluded. For primary research, three big manufacturing organisations in the Vietnamese context were selected, thereby excluding small and medium companies.

3.11. Ethical Considerations

Some of the interviewees and people participating in questionnaires used to be the researcher's previous employers and colleagues so they are willing to support the researcher during her research. The survey and interviews therefore will be more approachable and receive a truly empathy from the people involved. However, the other organizations who do not know the researcher before can refuse to provide their organizational information, especially HR related issues, to the people outside the organization (Kamoche, 2001). The observation method of collecting data may face some challenges. First, the researcher might not be welcomed to observe the training programs and daily working activities of an organisation as this observation will affect their learning and working outcomes. Second, the observation method is critiqued for its time-consuming nature.

Advices of the supervisor as well as clearly explanation to organization's key persons are appropriated for further development of this research method. Questionnaire has its advantage in terms of time however the outcome can be biased as the result of filling questionnaire without thoroughly reading and understanding the questions. Interview is really the challenging task in collecting data. Some of chosen managers at management board was not available for interview due to their busy working schedule or business travel.

Ethical considerations in an academic research are essential to protect human rights, get informed consent, maintain anonymity of the subjects/participants, confidentiality of data, protection from any emotional or physical injury, respect for the participants, and their rights to withdraw from the research. However, the current research complied with a range of ethical considerations. Firstly, informed consent was taken in this research to ensure from the 'gatekeeper' and the participation of the employees without any coercion or persuasion. The participants took part in the research took informed decisions indicating that they voluntarily agreed to take part in the study after knowing the potential risks that they were exposed to. Informed consent ensures that the research participants knowingly, consciously, and voluntarily agree to participate in the data collection process and give their responses without any form of external pressure (Creswell, 2002). Secondly, the names of the participants were kept anonymous and pseudo names were used against their real names. Participants' anonymity is maintained by not linking their responses with their personal details.

Thirdly, maintaining confidentiality of data obtained from the participants is of utmost importance to prevent misuse of information. In order to ensure that confidentiality of data is maintained the researcher stored the data in a password protected computer to avoid any unauthorised access to data. Fourthly, the participants were made aware that they had full rights to withdraw from the research anytime and even decline to take part in the empirical data

collection. This ensured that the participants were not forced to participate and had full flexibility in terms of taking part or leaving the research midway.

3.12. Conclusion

The chapter outlines the methodological choices made with regards to the philosophical standpoint, i.e. pragmatism including the inductive approach, and the exploratory research design. Combining the mixed methods (qualitative and quantitative) helped to collect extensive data to find answer to the research questions. The chapter also explains the data collection strategy to collect quantitative data from the employees while conducting interviews to collect qualitative information from the human resource managers. The process of sampling the participants to take part in the primary research and the ethical considerations are also discussed in the chapter.

CHAPTER 4:

INTRODUCTION TO THE CASES

4.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a basic business overview of the chosen case study companies including a brief outline of their human resource management. The HRM approach to training, training overview and the approach to training evaluation is given in brief. Information is taken from the company websites, annual reports and published data available from secondary sources.

4.2. Overview of Parent companies

Case study research may feature single cases or multiple cases (often two to four) (Stake, 1995). Three chosen companies are Vard Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam Limited. These companies are all operated in manufacturing sector for more than 10 years, have more than 1,000 employees in Vietnamese site; and well-known for their success in Vietnam and their parent company over the world. The following review of the parent companies are necessary to have a quick glance of these companies.

Category	VARD	BLUESCOPE	BAKER HUGHES
Established year	1780	1885	1908
Headquarter	Norway	Australia	Texas, USA
Website	www.vard.com	www.bluscope.com	www.Bakerhughes.com
Scale	9 sites 5 countries	162 sites 18 countries	203 sites 120 countries
Number of employees	8,500	14,000	55,000
Specialisation	Shipbuilding, offshore and specialised vessels	Steel building and materials, metal coating and painting	Energy technology, oil and gas service and equipment
Total capital	\$223 million	\$5.9 billion	\$20.7 billion
Year entering Vietnam	02/2007	05/1993	09/1998

Number of employees in Vietnam	850	1,300	1,490
---------------------------------------	-----	-------	-------

Table 4-2: Overview of VARD, BlueScope and Baker Hughes

Source: www.vard.com , www.bluescope.com, www.bakerhughes.com

All these companies in Vietnam are big companies as their employees exceeds 500. The reason to choose these companies are explained as follows:

- They are large-scale companies so their HR departments are well-organized with adequate budget for training.
- The training courses are updated and operated throughout a year.
- They have Parent companies oversea so that they could access training courses both locally, nationally and internationally.
- Their Parent companies are all leading giant in their sub-sector for more than 100 years with exceptional growth rate (Tran, 2014) so they could represent their subsectors and could be considered as good representatives for the manufacturing sector.
- The companies in Vietnam are supportive and willing to share their practical experience in training evaluation.

4.3. CASE 1: VARD VUNG TAU LTD. COMPANY

4.3.1. Business Overview

VARD Vung Tau Limited (known as VARD) is an investment holding organization that is specialised in designing and building specialised vessels and other offshore support vessels. VARD also offers support services to its subsidiaries and also maintains provision for performance and guarantee of repayment on the construction contracts. With the help of its

subsidiaries the company designs power and automation systems, equipment for deck handling, and vessel accommodation solution. It also provides engineering services and design to maritime global industry.

The organization is also involved in training and design, shipbuilding, piping system and electrical installation for building and construction projects. VARD also designs and develops tug supply vessels meant for anchor handling, offshore patrol vessels, offshore subsea construction vessel, stern trawlers, and special vessels such as those meant for coast guard and research, icebreakers and seismic vessels etc. The company is known for its innovative capabilities and has been awarded several times for its innovative and sustainable product designs that involve tailor made solution to the client requirements. The company has its own in-house design that delivers custom- made designs from standardised vessels as well as highly sophisticated vessels that have adaptations according to the customer specifications. VARD as a heavy-industry enterprise has strong inclination towards environmental protection and preservation of natural resources. Its corporate mission, values, and goals also incorporate regulations associated with water and air quality, strong quality checks on the discharge of pollutants and setting up key standards for the storage, treatment, and dumping of hazardous and toxic waste.

4.3.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights

VARD has 850 employees in its Vietnamese shipyard. The employees are both hired from local and international destinations in order to build a strong pool of human resources with diverse capabilities. The employees after being hired are given appropriate induction training in order to make them aware of the organisational mission and vision, goals and objectives and the HR policies and practices that need to be complied with. VARD maintains a dedicated team of professionals for its different functional areas and departments working under the supervision of experienced managers with strong leadership capabilities.

4.3.3. Training overview

The HR policy and practices at VARD include the basic guidelines and standards for employee training and development across several levels. Training is provided to the newly hired recruits on a regular basis while the existing employees get trained on skills required to work on specialised projects given by the global clients. The company has a dedicated team of trainers who are experienced members of the organisation having spent a long tenure and capable of imparting training to the participants. However, as per requirement, the training team from the headquarters based in Norway and the U.S. visits the shipbuilding facilities and locations in Vietnam to deliver the training sessions.

Trainings are mainly delivered on periodical basis to update the employees about any new change in technology, design, work process and procedures. However, employees feel free to communicate with their supervisor/team leader or the line human resource manager to get enrolled for getting trained on any aspects depending on their interest area. Such trainings are provided on an 'ad-hoc' basis in small groups to employees belonging to different departments. Ad-hoc trainings are not 'process specific' and generally relate to enhancing the behavioural competencies such as communication skills, interpersonal skills, client handling skills, and negotiation skills.

4.3.4. Training Evaluation

Training Evaluation at VARD is mainly carried out for scheduled training program rather than adhoc-trainings that are imparted to the employees during emergent situations. The training evaluation process used by the HRM at the company is 'Happy Sheets' which are distributed after the training is complete to seek the responses of those being trained, even though it is not a comprehensive method of training evaluation. However, the use of Kirkpatrick model is made for extensive training programs at the manufacturing organisation.

After training, the evaluators of the training program often asked question as to whether the trainees could learn what was aimed to be taught, and whether they gained new knowledge and skills in the form of learning to be implemented at the workplace. Behaviour evaluation raised questions as to whether the trained employees put their learning into effect while working and how far the knowledge was used. At this stage the HR managers identify whether there were any measurable changes in the behaviour and performances of the employees when back to their job roles. While the Kirkpatrick model was the main evaluative framework used, there were other models such Phillips evaluation approach that was used by the human resource department specially to measure the ROI post training. Using this model made it easier for the evaluators to measure ROI from both, the perspectives of human performance and business outcomes. Overall, VARD as a manufacturing company in Vietnam uses simple techniques to identify employee feedback of the training program while the dominant evaluation frameworks were rarely used.

4.4. CASE 2: BlueScope Vietnam Company

4.4.1. Business Overview

BlueScope is a major global supplier of steel products, painted steel building products, metal coated products and supplier of engineered building solutions (EBS) to the industrial and commercial segments. The company dates back to 1885 with its headquarters based in Melbourne, Australia. It quickly expands its operations in 162 locations in 18 different countries including Vietnam. The company has evolved as a result of integration from three leading companies in the steel industry in Australia – Broken Hill Proprietary Ltd (BHP), Australian Iron and Steel Ltd (AIS), and John Lysaght Australia Pty Ltd and the acquisitions of Butler Manufacturing, New Zealand Steel, and IMSA Group of Companies. The business strength of BlueScope is built upon the mechanism of global partnerships, strong global brands

and global networks. The partnerships and networks are built on the company's great product brands such as clean Colorbond and Zinalume Steels, Butler and Lysaght Steel building products.

In Vietnam site which was established in 1993, the major products include 'Roofing and Walling' and 'Framing and Truss'. Roofing and Walling include the use of steel for projects relating to commercial and industrial business such as warehousing, iconic buildings, factory premises, office complexes. Framing and Truss involve the use of aluminium alloy or zinc for house framing, wall and roof frames that are fire resistant, corrosion resistant, light weight yet strong, and a reliable solution for residential built to last longer.

BlueScope Vietnam maintains its core beliefs in what they value and how they behave which are embedded in 'Our Bond' and 'Guide to Business Conduct' (www.bluescope.com.vn/about/sustainability-en/). 'Our Bond' reflects the statement of commitment meant for four stakeholders – employees, customers, shareholders and communities. 'Our Guide to Business Conduct' establishes the principles that administer the way employees must behave while conducting business operations. This also helps to govern the employee's behaviour, attitude, and conduct while complying with sustainability standards, health and safety, fair trade, and environment protection.

4.4.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights

BlueScope Vietnam considers the workforce of 1,300 employees as its core strength and one of the main sources of competitive advantage. It has a human resource management (HRM) department that is responsible to execute the HR functions associated with people management. The HRM emphasises on maintaining a safe and supportive work environment for its employees and an appropriate work life balance. The HRM department manage employees in different departments that include engineering, Information Technology,

Operations, sales and marketing, finance and accounting, customer services, health and safety, supply chain, logistics and research and development.

The HRM department also ensures that the work environment is free from any kind of discrimination, abuse, bullying or harassment, disrespect for others, violence or threat. Training programs are therefore designed to make people aware of the workplace norms and values, culture and elements of organisational behaviour. Being a company of an international repute, BlueScope Vietnam recruits people from different countries, especially from location where it operates.

4.3.3. Training overview

At BlueScope Vietnam, training is considered to be an integral part of the human resource function and imparted after careful planning. Training includes a combination of 'On- the- Job' and 'Off-the-job' training and imparted according to the requirements. For new recruits, induction training is provided to educate them about the organisational policies, values, goals and objectives, and HR policies associated with employee management. After gaining basic knowledge, these employees are given off the job training also known as 1st level training to give them preliminary knowledge of the work responsibilities, work processes, operations and quality, health and safety, compliance, and conceptual understanding of overall work procedures and context. The use of in-house seminars, lectures, and workshops is organised during training sessions to help where employees clarify their doubts and gain confidence. Subsequently on the job training is provided where the employees get the opportunity to apply in actual practice all what has been learnt during off the job training. Therefore, training design at this manufacturing company in Vietnam includes on the job and off the job training designed for new recruits as well as existing employees.

4.4.4. Training Evaluation

At BlueScope Vietnam, formal training evaluations are conducted after every training across the various levels of the organisation. The training evaluation frameworks are different for the trainings provided at different levels to the employees. As evaluation was conducted before, during, and after the training the use of a systematic evaluation mechanism is maintained. At this company, training evaluation comprises of methodical stages such as evaluation of the training context, input evaluation, and process evaluation. At the initial phase, the Training and development needs analysis (TNA) is determined in association with objective formulation to recognise the extent to which the training goals are in alignment with the organisational needs. Subsequently, input evaluation is designed to assess the extent to which the training strategies, activities, and procedures support the objectives formulated in the first stage of training evaluation. This stage also helps to lay down the detailed procedures to ensure it is the best approach with regards to the evaluated needs. At BlueScope Vietnam, evaluation of the training also includes monitoring of the training program to get deeper insights into the training and identify whether the training has been a success or failure.

As regards to the training evaluation model, review of its HR policy and information gained from the managerial interview indicate that the organisation uses similar model as the CIPP framework mainly for the employees. However, other evaluation frameworks are used to evaluate the results of the training meant for those holding managerial position. The use of a well-tailored-four-step approach helped to measure pre and post training outcomes. This is directed towards Kaufman's 5 level evaluation frameworks to measure the impact of training in terms of its benefits to the organisation as well as the society it serves. Overall the company ensures that training evaluation frameworks are different for operational level employees and managerial level employees respectively.

4.5. CASE 3: BAKER HUGHES VIETNAM LIMITED

4.5.1. Business Overview

Baker Hughes is a GE (General Electric) organization established in 1908, and the world's first and only organization to provide integrated oilfield products and services, including digital solution. The organization believes in harnessing and the experiences and passion of its social assets, i.e., employees in order to enhance productivity throughout its oil and gas value chain. The organization is backed by the digital capabilities of GE, and therefore integrates men, machine and the cloud to dismantle silos, foster efficiency in operations, eliminate risks and reduce waste. It currently operates in 203 different locations in more than 120 countries. Its full stream assortment of products and services helps to produce and deliver unmatched levels of industrial yield through technology, value- based services, and well-integrated offerings. Baker Hughes integrates capabilities from upstream activities to midstream to downstream and thereby offers full stream oil and gas services. Its business model and portfolio generate novel sources of value, enhance overall productivity, and value provided to clients through well integrated equipment and services. Baker Hughes' global scale combined with local knowledge and strong dedication towards serving customers makes it a well-known brand with international repute. Baker Hughes Vietnam started its operation in Vietnam since 1998. Until now, with the workforce of 1,490 employees, the company has gained significant success and dominates the energy technology market in Vietnam.

4.5.2. Organizational Human Resources highlights

Baker Hughes Vietnam has a dedicated human resource department with a team of professionals working towards employee development in every country where it operates. In Vietnam, the company maintains a human resource team inclined towards human resource development (HRD) by adapting best practices for talent management. Right from the HR planning stage, i.e. forecasting demand and supply of human resources to estimating gaps in

manpower requirements, designing action plan for recruitment and selection, training, career development and retention, the HRM at Baker Hughes Vietnam is commitment to manage its existing talent and acquire fresh talent. As a part of its overall talent management strategy, employee training and development is carried out in alignment with the human resource policies and goals. The key human resource highlights of the company are that it follows a strategic approach to human resource management and employee development. This implies that the strategic HRM (SHRM) is followed and hence the organisational goals and objectives are in line with the HR goals. The HR managers work as strategic partners with the operational level managers thereby carry out the human resource planning, training and development, and overall talent management with shared goals. The HRM follows the competency-based approach to human resource/ workforce management and according employee skills and competencies are enhanced through systematic training, and a culture of continuous learning.

4.5.3. Training overview

The strategic approach to human resource management ensures that employee training is a strategic business practice at Baker Hughes Vietnam. The company operates in a competitive business environment marked with changing consumer demands, influx of new technology, increasing globalisation and likelihood of economic uncertainties. The SHRM approach of Baker Hughes Vietnam understands that it is important to incessantly improve their business propositions and fortify valued customer relationships. Therefore, successful training function at the company is meant to support the organisational vision by ensuring workforce preparedness for sustaining in the competitive industry. Employee training is at the core of its HRD and consequently organisational development. The company considers training as a learning exercise, which should be on-going, multidirectional and incorporate formal sessions along with capability building. The training team at Baker Hughes Vietnam link training with

employee motivation and consider it crucial for human resource development and talent retention.

4.5.4. Training Evaluation

Evaluation of training programs is considered crucial and linked with the strategic approach of HRM. While evaluating the effectiveness of any training program the organisation considers it important to seek employee feedback, particularly those taking part in the training irrespective of their department, functional area, tenure, or level. The use of a systematic framework for training evaluation is aligned with the Kilpatrick's model which is in line with most of training programs being held in the organisation. Use of a systematic evaluation helps to capture the reactions of trainees and understand the extent to which their experience in training is valuable, whether they felt the training was pertinent, and whether they felt engaged. Feedback collected from the employees taking part in the training helps to assess the outcome of training sessions by way of understanding participants' perceptions, and whether there exists any need for improvements. Subsequently, evaluating the extent to which trainees were able to acquire the much-needed knowledge, skills and attitude is considered crucial to examine whether the training objectives were met. Therefore, training evaluation is conducted by the human resource managers acting as strategic partners to other departments, aiming to identify the loopholes in the existing training programs and take strategic steps for improvement.

4.6. Conclusion

The chapter provides basic information about the companies chosen to conduct the primary research. The information gained from secondary sources provides background information about the manufacturing companies. Further enquiry into their training strategies and approaches to training evaluation is conducted by undertaking primary research. The next

chapter presents and analyses the data obtained by conducting employee survey and managerial interviews thereby adding value to the overall findings obtained from secondary research.

CHAPTER 5:

DATA ANALYSIS AND

FINDINGS

5.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the findings obtained from the primary research in two phases. The first phase involved the distribution of questionnaires to the employees of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam, in a survey. A total of 372 valid surveys were included for data analysis. The second phase involved carrying out interviews from three HR managers of the researched companies. The results obtained from the survey are presented with the help of visual aids such as tables and graphs while the in-depth and subjective information obtained from the interviews are discussed separately under specific themes that underpin the research problems.

5.2. Quantitative data analysis collection

Questionnaires were distributed to 372 employees and the results are presented in the following part of this chapter. Tabular and graphical representation makes it easier to explain the findings in triangulation with the theoretical studies carried out in the literature review. Data analysis is carried out using simple Microsoft Excel software wherein the data is stored, filtered and the overall responses are converted into percentage using inbuilt Excel formulae.

Q1) What is your gender?

Majority of the employees taking part in the online survey were males (85%) while the remaining 15% were females. The result indicates that female employees are comparatively lesser than their male counterparts.

Gender	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Male	85%	316	372
Female	15%	56	372
Transsexual	-	0	372

Table 5-1: Gender

Figure 5-1: Gender

Q2) Which age group do you belong to?

Most of the employees taking part in the survey (27%) belonged to the age group between 36 and 40 years, followed by those between 41 and 45 (21%). There were no employees below 20

years of age while those between 20 and 25 years of age were only 5%. Similarly, only 9% of the employees were above 50 years of age. Overall data signifies that the employees working in Vietnamese manufacturing companies belong to different age groups, however, the number of participants below 25 years of age and above 50 are fairly less than other age groups.

Age group	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Below 20	-	0	372
Between 20-25	5%	18	372
Between 26-30	13%	48	372
Between 31-35	10%	38	372
Between 36-40	27%	102	372
Between 41-45	21%	78	372
Between 46-50	15%	56	372
Above 50	9%	32	372

Table 5-2: Age Group

Figure 5-2: Age Group

Q3) For how long have you been working with the organisation?

Table 5-3: Tenure in the organisation

Tenure in the organisation	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Less than 1 year	-	0	372

Between 1-3 years	11%	42	372
Between 3-5 years	30%	111	372
Between 5-7 years	36%	134	372
Between 7-10 years	13%	48	372
More than 10 years	10%	37	372

Figure 5-3: Tenure in the organisation

As indicated in the above graphics, 36 percent of the employees taking part in the survey had been working with the organisation between 5-7 years, followed by 30 percent who were employed with the company for around 3-5 years. Only 10 percent of the participants had tenure of more than 10 years in Vietnamese manufacturing organisations. Overall data indicates that the employees taking part in the survey had spent a good tenure with the manufacturing organisations and are likely to possess adequate knowledge about the nature of training imparted by the organisation.

Q4) Which department do you work with?

The employees of Vietnamese manufacturing companies taking part in the survey belonged to different departments such as production (26%), purchase (19%), Accounting and Finance (18%), research and development (9%), and marketing (6%). 22% of the participants belonged to some other departments. Therefore, the employees belonged to different departments and

areas of expertise and it is likely that they may have undergone different types of training programs.

Department	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Production	26%	48	372
Research and Development	9%	16	372
Purchase	19%	35	372
Marketing	6%	12	372
Accounting and Finance	18%	33	372
Others	22%	42	372

Table 4: Department/area of work

Figure 5-4: Department/area of work

Q5) What is the frequency of training program implemented in your organisation?

Most of the employees in the survey (29%) reveal the training sessions are held in the organisation every quarter, implying that training takes place once in every three months. 20% of the participants indicated that training frequency is based on needs, i.e., training is imparted as and when required. Therefore, training is imparted on a needs basis is such manufacturing

organisations. 19% signify that training is held once in every six months while 15% of the participants reveal that it is held 5-6 times in a year.

Overall data indicates that the training sessions are imparted in the manufacturing organisation in different time periods; however, very few employees indicated that it is need based.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Once a year	-	0	372
Twice a year	-	0	372
5-6 times a year	15%	54	372
Once in six months	19%	72	372
Twice in six months	11%	42	372
Every quarter	29%	108	372
Every month	6%	22	372
Anytime, according to need	20%	74	372

Table 5-5: Frequency of training program

Figure 5-5: Frequency of training program

Q6) Which training did you attend recently?

The above question was open-ended; however, the participants were required to disclose the type of training they had recently attended. Overall response from a total of 372 participants was extensive; however, most of the responses were congruent with the others. Most of the employees had attended the '**Systems training**' that includes comprehensive training on handling machines and equipment, work processes and flows; manage the operational aspects of manufacturing. Employees had also attended '**Lean, six sigma and quality trainings**' that includes a wide range of quality management tools and techniques to increase productivity, control idle time, waste control, maximise yield, and increase overall efficiency. Employees had also attended **Product training and Process training** organised recently to update workers on new product development, use of newly-installed technology, and better utilisation of machines. However, these trainings were specially designed for employees in the production department.

Employees were also trained in basic **computer literacy, and ICT** (Information and communications technology), and internet as preliminary skills, and **advanced software training** that were specific to the manufacturing firm.

Employees also attended **cross-cultural training**, and training on soft skills, **interpersonal skills**, and **communication and negotiation skills** training. These training sessions were mandatory and specially designed for those who worked with expatriate projects and were required to visit various other countries to work with foreign clients or partners. Apart from these, employees were also trained on the essentials of compliance, working on expatriate projects, and client handling. A few employees, especially the ones working with marketing and sales department (B2B), had recently attended **training on customer service skills, CRM (customer relationship management), and customer retention**.

Few employees had recently attended ad-hoc training given to selected employees who demonstrated extraordinary performance, and behaviour, took higher initiatives, and showed

leadership capabilities. These employees were given promotional training to make them fit for taking the next level after being promoted.

Findings indicate that the employees have attended a range of training programs recently that vary from systems training, 'lean, six sigma and quality trainings, Product training and Process trainings, computer literacy, and ICT, project management training, cross-cultural training, communication and negotiation skills training, customer service skills, and CRM trainings. Although, the chosen companies are manufacturing firms, the trainings are not strictly related to manufacturing but help employees to gain multiple skills and empower them.

Q7) When did the training take place?

As per the response of the employees, most of the training relating to the production department had taken place in the previous one to three months from the date of the survey. For other training, it had been around a year that the training had been held and employees had attended the same. The responses indicate that the frequency of training was fair.

Q8) Who led the training?

The participants who answered the above two questions, mentioned that the training sessions were led by a dedicated training team comprising of internal trainers, as well as external vendors hired as trainers for short-term training on contractual basis. The human resource department comprising HR managers were the ones who identified the training needs of different employees across different functions, departments, and areas. The HR managers in coordination with the line HR organised the training sessions, fixed up the venue, notified the training dates to the employees, ensured minimum attendance of the participants was there, and examined the progress of the training.

As regards to training given to employees in the production department the training was led by internal trainers who were permanent employees of the organisation, on company payroll. These training included product and process training, quality trainings, and compliance.

Trainings with regards to computer literacy, and ICT, advanced software training were led by the company’s own trainers. However, for behavioural training, customer services (B2B) and CRM, the training sessions were led by external vendors with specialisation in their area of training.

Training to employees in the manufacturing organisations is delivered by internal training team as well as external trainers, as vendors hired for a limited time period according to need. This is because the in-house training department does not possess all the necessary skills and knowledge required to be transferred to the employees and training is outsourced from external providers/vendors.

Q9) What was the primary reason you participated in this training?

The primary reason to take part in the recent training, as responded by most of the employees (29%) was the implementation of new technology. Therefore, training was provided in terms of getting familiar with technology, its practical application, and operating it to yield the best results. The main reason to participate in training was also to get acquainted with new procedures and work processes, and better ways of working in the manufacturing industry. Therefore, the primary reason for attending training were mainly related to the production department wherein employees were supposed to be trained on new technology, new procedures. Such training sessions were part of the ‘systems training’, ‘process training’ and ‘quality training’ which were attended by employees working with the production department.

Table 5-6: Primary reason to participate in training

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
New procedure	21%	78	372
New technology	29%	108	372
New to the Company	9%	34	372

Personal development	17%	62	372
Other (Please specify)	24%	90	372

Figure 5-6: Primary reason to participate in training

‘New technology’ is one of the core areas and primary reason for training as indicated in the survey. It is likely that the manufacturing firms continuously upgrade their technology that requires them to train their employees to get acquainted with new technology. Similarly, training for new procedure implies that the work procedures are likely to change with change in technology and hence this becomes the primary (main) reason for training.

Q10) What type of training is mostly imparted by your organisation?

The majority (55%) of the employees taking part in the survey reveal that the manufacturing companies provide both ‘On-the-job’ and ‘Off-the-job’ training while 20% indicate that mostly ‘On-the-job’ trainings are provided. Comparatively, 16% of the participants reveal that ‘Off-the-job training’ is mostly provided to the employees. Overall data indicates that a combination of On-the-job’ and ‘Off-the-job’ training is provided in most of the manufacturing companies.

Table 5-7: Type of training mostly imparted

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
On the job training	20%	76	372

Off the job training	16%	58	372
Both (On and Off the job)	55%	206	372
Others	9%	32	372

Figure 5-7: Type of training mostly imparted

A comprehensive training program is maintained by the manufacturing firms being surveyed as identified in the survey. The combination of on the job and off the job training implies that employees are given hands on/practical training along with theoretical sessions. For instance, product knowledge (off the job) is associated with process (on the job) training while allows employees to apply their knowledge and learning in the actual work processes and activities. Off the job training in the form of lectures, simulation, grid training, role-plays and conferences are backed up with on the job, practical training sessions such as soft-launch, coaching, job rotation which are related to production. However, it is not clear whether on the job and off the job trainings are provided simultaneously or one precedes the other.

Q11) The use of appropriate technology such as ICT (information and communications technology) is used to impart training?

Major percentage of the respondents in the survey 56% (20% strongly agree and 36% Agree) that Information and Communications technology (ICT) is increasingly used while imparting

training. Contrary to this, negative response was shared by 34% (20% disagree and 14% strongly disagree). Ten percent of the participants preferred to remain neutral.

Table 5-8: Whether use of appropriate ICT is made in training

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	20%	74	372
Agree	36%	134	372
Neither agree nor disagree	10%	36	372
Disagree	20%	76	372
Strongly Disagree	14%	52	372

Figure 5-8: Whether use of appropriate ICT is made in training

Q12) Before designing the training program the HR managers/training department conducts an appropriate training need analysis (TNA)

The majority (64%) of the employees taking part in the survey share an affirmative response that the HR managers/training department conducts an appropriate training needs analysis (TNA) before designing the training program. Meanwhile a comparatively lower, 27% (17% disagree and 10% strongly disagree) of participants had an opposite response. According to them, no TNA were conducted before training programs were designed.

As discussed in the literature review, TNA is a crucial part of the overall training program and helps the HR managers to identify the knowledge gaps, skill deficiencies and shortcomings in the employee competencies that need to be fulfilled. TNA provides valuable and significant input into the nature and type of training to be imparted to the employees to ensure that their knowledge, skills and competencies are upgraded and made up to date.

Table 5-9: Whether training needs analysis (TNA) is conducted

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	36%	134	372
Agree	28%	104	372
Neither agree nor disagree	9%	34	372
Disagree	17%	62	372
Strongly Disagree	10%	38	372

Figure 5-9: Whether training needs analysis (TNA) is conducted

While TNA helps to make the training more relevant and effective, there are certain limitations associated with such practices. TNA may be time consuming in terms of developing surveys and assessments and rolling out the needs analysis, collecting the feedback and implementing the same in the actual training design. TNA may also be costly and requires a certain amount of budget to be set aside as an important part of overall training. There may also be a possibility that the business needs have changed by the time TNA has been completed and hence new set of trainings have to be imparted to the employees. Moreover, it is likely that the employees feel reluctant to disclose where they lack competence and hence the purpose of TNA may not be fulfilled.

Q13) The objectives of the training were clearly defined?

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Circle the number that best characterises how you feel about the statement, where 1=Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total

Strongly Agree (5)	22%	82	372
Agree (4)	37%	136	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	10%	38	372
Disagree (2)	19%	70	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	12%	46	372

Table 5-10: The objectives of training were clearly defined

Figure 5-10: The objectives of training were clearly defined

The majority, 59 percent of participants (22% strongly agree and 37% agree) shared a positive response about the objectives of the training being met. In contrast, 31 percent (19% disagree and 12% strongly disagreed) disagreed to the question.

Training objectives signify the purpose of the training, its implications and outcome. The objectives of any training program need to be defined clearly and accordingly training should be imparted. It should be understandable by those designing the training sessions, trainers, and the trainees. In case of Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, it is noteworthy that major percentage of employees taking part in the survey found that the training objectives were met.

The importance of SMART objectives lies in the fact that the objectives are specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time bound. Even though, majority of the employees in the survey indicate that the objectives of the training program are well defined, it is not clear

whether the objectives designed by the training team/HR department are SMART. Moreover, it is likely that there are different objectives formulated for different types of trainings and common training objectives cannot be generalised for all.

Q14) Participation and interaction were encouraged

As regards to participation and interaction in the training, a significantly higher percentage of response was on the negative side. 62 percent of participants (39% strongly disagreed and 23% disagreed) show their positive response to the idea that the HR department/ Training team encouraged employees’ participation, while only 20 percent (9% strongly agreed and 11% agreed) to the fact. It was also notable that 18% preferred to remain neutral.

Participation and inclusion allow employees to have a say in the training program, and they are likely to feel a sense of belongingness. It is not considered a good practice leaving employees in isolation, and preparing the training sessions without including their interests, competency gaps that requirement refinement, and skill requirements.

Table 5-11: Whether participation and interaction are encouraged

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	9%	34	372
Agree (4)	11%	42	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	18%	66	372
Disagree (2)	39%	144	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	23%	86	372

Figure 5-11: Whether participation and interaction are encouraged

The fact that majority denied the presence of interaction in the training implies that there is lack of information exchange between the trainer and the trainees (employees). It is likely that lack of interaction could make the training session monotonous and makes it difficult for the trainees to raise their voice to clarify their doubts. Employee participation is not encouraged in training, implying that the trainees/participants may not be given assignments or projects to work in groups.

Q15) The content was organized and easy to follow

Most of the participants (38%) strongly agreed and shared an affirmative response that the content of the training they attended was organised and easy to follow, while 23% supported the idea. Meanwhile, 29 percent of participants (12% strongly disagree and 17% disagreed) shared a negative response.

Organised content of the training program ensures that the training is imparted in a scientific and orderly manner, and the trainees follows the training conveniently. It should be designed

in a haphazard, disorganised manner that flows unsystematically and participants find it difficult to follow. This could make it difficult to achieve goals of the training sessions.

Table 5-12: The content was organised and easy to follow

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	38%	142	372
Agree (4)	23%	88	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	10%	36	372
Disagree (2)	17%	62	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	12%	44	372

Figure 5-12: The content was organised and easy to follow

Training content includes the modules, literature, manuscripts and readings relating to what would be imparted in the training session. Precise, relevant, and easy to follow content ensures that the trainees are clear with what needs to be learnt, how it is to be learnt, and how the learning is to be applied in actual work. A standard training content is most desirable; however, it is likely that all employees taking part in the training find it appealing.

Q16) The training materials distributed were helpful.

As indicated in the survey, 66 percent of participants (32% strongly agree and 34% agree) shared a positive response that the training materials distributed to the participants were helpful. Comparatively, 23 percent of them (14% disagree and 9% strongly disagreed) disagreed with the question.

Training materials being helpful implies that its design and content is worth being applied in practical scenario. Employees as trainees must find the training material worthy of being followed while being trained, easy to understand, and apply the learning while being trained as well as while working.

Table 5-13: Whether the training modules distributed were helpful

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	32%	118	372
Agree (4)	34%	126	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	11%	41	372
Disagree (2)	14%	52	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	9%	36	372

Figure 5-13: Whether the training modules distributed were helpful

The response to this question corroborates with the findings obtained from Q15, which relates to the appropriateness of the training content. Precise and easy to follow training content adds value to the training module by making it relevant, appropriate and helpful. Even though most of the employees are in consensus that the training modules distributed during the training sessions were helpful, a proportion of employees denied. Hence, areas of improvement still lie in the design of training modules to ensure that it considered helpful by every participant of the training session.

Q17) The training I received is applicable to my work.

57 percent of employees (31% strongly agree and 26% agree) shared a positive response that the training they received was applicable to their work. At the same time, 33% (18% disagree and 15% strongly disagree) shared unfavourable response to the idea.

Training modules prepared for the training need to be appropriate in terms of their applicability to work. It should be practical and relevant to the work processes, and daily work activities being undertaken by the employees on a daily basis.

Table 5-14: Application of training to work

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	31%	114	372
Agree (4)	26%	98	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	10%	34	372
Disagree (2)	18%	66	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	15%	56	372

Figure 5-14: Application of training to work

The percentage of employees considering lack of applicability of training in actual work raises questions as regards to the effectiveness of the training sessions. It is likely that there exists scope for improvement in the training design, its content, and modules distributed to the employees. Lack of applicability of the training to work may also be due to the fact that trainings are not interactive, neither participative, and employees get little, or no scope to clarify their doubts.

Q18) The trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics.

A substantial 69 percent of participants (45% strongly agree and 24% agree) shared a favourable response that the trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics. On the contrary, 23 percent (16% disagree and 7% strongly disagree) responded negatively to the question.

The skills of a trainer are crucial in terms of imparting knowledge, answering the questions raised, and clarifying doubts of the trainees being trained. The trainer's knowledge must be sound, up-to-date and relevant to the training session being delivered. Inadequate knowledge

may not only result in employee feeling disinterested but also lose confidence in the training program.

Table 5-15: Whether the trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	45%	167	372
Agree (4)	24%	89	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	8%	60	372
Disagree (2)	16%	58	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	7%	26	372

Figure 5-15: Whether the trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics

Trainers' knowledge makes a significant difference to the training environment, presence and interest level of the trainees. However, apart from knowledge, it is also necessary that the trainer encourages interactive learning, exchange of information and clarification of doubts

throughout the training session. Trainer also needs to possess effective communication, presentation and interactive skills to keep the audiences engaged in the training session.

Q19) The trainer was well-prepared.

Table 5-16: The trainer was well-prepared

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	52%	192	372
Agree (4)	28%	104	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	4%	14	372
Disagree (2)	10%	38	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	6%	24	372

Figure 5-16: The trainer was well-prepared

As depicted in the above visuals, it is clear that a substantial 80 percent of participants (52% strongly agree and 28% agree) shared an affirmative response that the trainer was well-

prepared. Contrarily a negligible, 16 percent (10% disagree and 6% strongly disagree) responded negatively to the question.

Preparedness of the trainer while delivering training is crucial to the effectiveness and success of training. The trainer should not only be equipped with the necessary knowledge, aptitude and skills but also be mentally and emotionally prepared

This question supplements the previous question (Q18), which stressed on trainer’s knowledge, and equally important is trainer’s preparedness. The trainer needs to possess the right temperament and behaviour to interact with the audiences while training, and must not demonstrate negative behaviour such as anger or frustration

Q20) The training objectives were met

A mixed response was obtained with regards to whether the training objectives were met. 29 percent agreed to the question while 18 percent strongly agreed. Meanwhile, 22 percent disagreed, and 20 percent disagreed. It was notable 11 percent remained neutral.

Table 5-17: The training objectives were met

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	18%	66	372
Agree (4)	29%	108	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	11%	42	372
Disagree (2)	22%	82	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	20%	74	372

Figure 5-17: The training objectives were met

Objectives of training could vary between training programs and may depend on the type of training being imparted, its scope and purpose. A systematic training program is likely to incorporate objectives that focus on employees’ skill improvement, behavioural development, increased satisfaction, motivation, and performance improvement. However, the extent to which objectives are achieved depend on the extent to which each employee finds the training program to be fruitful. Accordingly, the participants shared their response in the above question.

Q21) The time allotted for the training is sufficient.

51 percent of participants (20% strongly agree and 31% agree) of the respondents taking part in the survey shared an affirmative response that the time allotted for training program is sufficient. Comparatively, 42 percent of participants denied, and shared a negative response.

Table 5-18: The time allotted for the training is sufficient

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	20%	74	372
Agree (4)	31%	114	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	7%	28	372
Disagree (2)	25%	92	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	17%	64	372

Figure 5-18: The time allotted for the training is sufficient

One of the key requirements for a successful training program is the allotment of sufficient time that provides ample time for learning, clarifying doubts, giving feedback, and overall evaluation of the training session. Inadequate time may hinder the training program in the sense that it may not allow trainees time to practice, get doubts clarified, and understand the practical aspects of learning. It is important to mention that quality of time is more important in a training/learning session relative to the quantity of extent of time spent.

Q22) The training room and facilities were adequate and comfortable

The majority, 66 percent (43% strongly agree and 23% agree) shared a positive response that the training room and facilities were adequate and comfortable. Comparatively, 25 percent (16% disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed) shared an unfavourable response.

One of the pre-requisites of a successful training program is that the training venue/room and facilities need to be adequate to accommodate the audiences, deliver the training sessions, and encourage a learning environment. The floor space, seating arrangements, audio-visuals, lighting, and ventilation should be appropriate to ensure smooth progress of the training. In

absence of adequate facilities and uncomfortable environment is likely to distract trainees/participants and hinder the learning process.

Table 5-19: Whether the training rooms and facilities are adequate and comfortable

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	43%	158	372
Agree (4)	23%	86	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	9%	34	372
Disagree (2)	16%	60	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	9%	34	372

Figure 5-19: Whether the training rooms and facilities are adequate and comfortable

Q23) I feel comfortable sharing what I learned with co-workers.

As regards to feeling comfortable to share with co-workers what has been learnt in the training, a substantial 80% (59% strongly agree + 21% agree) shared an affirmative response. Meanwhile, 18% (10% disagree + 8% strongly disagree) responded negatively to the question.

Table 5-20: Sharing the learning with co-workers

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree (5)	59%	219	372
Agree (4)	21%	80	372
Neither agree nor disagree (3)	2%	8	372
Disagree (2)	10%	36	372
Strongly Disagree (1)	8%	30	372

Figure 5-20: Sharing the learning with co-workers

Sharing the learning with co-workers implies knowledge transfer and makes others aware of any new updates, or changes. It also implies sharing best practices and upgrading the knowledge level of others to increase their capabilities and skills. However, employees attending the training program must themselves be clear about the learning gained so as to be able to transfer learning by way of communication and discussion with co-workers.

Q24) The training you received has been effective in terms of knowledge enhancement and improving your skills and competencies?

A significant 60 percent of participants (22% strongly agree and 38% agree) of the participants shared a positive response that the training received so far has been effective in terms of knowledge enhancement and improving their skills and competencies. On the contrary, only 29 percent (19% disagree and 10% strongly disagree) shared a negative response about the appropriateness of the training sessions to improve their knowledge and skills.

As regards to the effectiveness of training in terms of knowledge enhancement and improvement in skills and competencies, Khan (2012) considers training to be a form of continuous learning that helps trainees as employees to upgrade their skills on an on-going basis. Yong and Mohd-Yusoff (2016) add that training helps employees to gain knowledge /awareness about existing policies and practices, tools and technology, and learn how to demonstrate the right behaviour. Emphasising on cognitive strategies, Holman *et al.* (2012) emphasise on the impact of training in terms of skills development as a never-ending process. Therefore, review of the extant literature indicates that there exists a direct relationship between ‘training’ on one side and ‘knowledge and skills development’ on the other.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	22%	81	372
Agree	38%	142	372
Neither agree nor disagree	11%	42	372
Disagree	19%	69	372
Strongly Disagree	10%	38	372

Table 5-21: Training for knowledge enhancement and skills improvement

Figure 5-21: Training for knowledge enhancement and skills improvement

Q25) Have you experienced improvement in your work performance after getting the necessary training?

The majority 62 percent of participants (23% strongly agree and 39% agree) shared a positive response by affirming that they have experienced improvement in work performance after getting the necessary training. Meanwhile, 31 percent of participants (14% disagree and 17% strongly disagree) responded that training has not resulted in any performance improvement.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	23%	86	372
Agree	39%	144	372
Neither agree nor disagree	7%	28	372
Disagree	14%	52	372
Strongly Disagree	17%	62	372

Table 5-22: Training and improvement in work performance

Figure 5-22: Training and improvement in work performance

This question is an extension of the previous one, as it is likely that improvement in knowledge and skills lead to performance improvement, to which majority of the participants agreed. The findings correspond to the theoretical claims made by authors in the literature review, for instance, Dent and Holton (2009) performance measurement post training should indicate that employees able to better utilise the organisational resources, deliver superior performance, and contribute towards achievement of organisational goals. Therefore, successful training is one that helps employees to improve performance after gaining knowledge, skills and competencies in their area of work/responsibilities.

Q26) Do you feel motivated each time after undergoing training session in the organisation?

A mixed response was obtained with regards to whether the employees felt motivated each time after undergoing a training session in the organisation, as 50 percent of participants (19% strongly agree and 31% agree) were optimistic about the idea. On the other hand, 33 percent (18% disagree and 15% strongly disagree) shared a negative response with regards to being motivated after undergoing training sessions. It was also noticeable that 17 percent of participants remained neutral, therefore neither agreeing nor disagreeing to the question.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	19%	36	372
Agree	31%	57	372
Neither agree nor disagree	17%	31	372
Disagree	18%	34	372
Strongly Disagree	15%	28	372

Table 5-23: Training and employee motivation

Figure 5-23: Training and employee motivation

Review of the academic literature confirm that the outcome of training is increased employee motivation and explained using conceptual models such as Maslow’s hierarchy of needs (Sadri and Bowen, 2011). Appropriate training helps employees to improve job performance and this is a key factor for human motivation. In addition, well trained employees are in a better position to deliver better performance, exhibit improved behaviour and likely to gain high position in the organisation through job promotion, managerial/leadership positions, superior compensation and benefits, thereby increasing the level of motivation (Zide *et al.*, 2017).

Training acts as a catalyst to help employees gain higher position in the organisation and fulfil their esteem needs and is a key dimension of higher level human motivation.

Q27) Would you recommend this training to others?

A substantially higher (85%) of the participants shared an optimistic response that they would recommend the training (they attended) to others. Meanwhile only 15 percent said that they would not recommend the training to others.

Table 5-24: Recommending to training to others

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Yes	85%	316	372
No	15%	56	372

Figure 5-24: Recommending to training to others

Q28) How do you feel you will implement this knowledge when returning to work?

- This training will directly help me with my work in the immediate future.
- This training will help me with my work but probably not for some time.
- This training will have no bearing on my work in the foreseeable future.

As shown in the above visuals, majority of the employees who recently attended a training session in their respective manufacturing organisations, reported that training would directly help them with their work in the immediate future (68%). These employees were therefore optimistic about the training programs held in the organisation and indicated that it would bring favourable outcomes to their daily work. 21 percent of participants felt that the training would help them with their work but probably not for some time, implying that they may still require some more training sessions to come up the learning curve. At the same time, a minority (11 percent) of the participants did not share a favourable response indicating that the training would have no bearing on their work in the foreseeable future.

Table 5-25: Feeling on implementing knowledge to work

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
This training will directly help me with my work in the immediate future.	254	68%	372
This training will help me with my work but probably not for some time.	76	21%	372
This training will have no bearing on my work in the foreseeable future.	42	11%	372

Figure 5-25: Feeling on implementing knowledge to work

Overall responses indicate that the different employees have different perceptions and standpoints as regards to the trainings being attended. Moreover, what the employees get from the training and how they implement their knowledge to actual work, are different from each other. However, the fact that majority of the trainees (68%) feel that training could be implemented favourably in near future, signifies that the trainings are likely to be fruitful and worth the time and cost being invested.

Q29) The organisation follows a systematic approach to training (SAT) to ensure that the participants/trainees get the best out of each training session?

As regards to whether the organisation follows a systematic approach to training (SAT), 52% share a positive perception while 35% (19% disagree + 16% strongly disagree) do not affirm to the idea.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	19%	72	372
Agree	33%	122	372
Neither agree nor disagree	13%	48	372
Disagree	19%	72	372
Strongly Disagree	16%	58	372

Table 5-26: Whether systematic approach to training (SAT) is followed

Figure 5-26: Whether systematic approach to training (SAT) is followed

The importance of SAT is discussed by authors such as Aguinis and Kraiger (2009), Guest (2011) and Gelens *et al.* (2014) in academic literature, who emphasise it from different angles. Aguinis and Kraiger (2009) explained SAT as a series of stages that helps in the knowledge, attitude and skills development of employees making them fit to undertake well-defined roles and responsibilities, while Guest (2011) emphasises it in terms of meeting the performance objectives. Meanwhile, Gelens *et al.* (2014) focus on the importance of SAT in order to identify the employees' training needs using various training analysis methods. SAT is a scientific approach.

Q30) The HR managers/training co-ordinators seek feedback from the trainees/participating employees regarding the appropriateness of training after every training session? (Evaluation)

As regards to whether the managers/training co-ordinators seek feedback from the trainees/participating employees regarding the appropriateness of training after every training session, majority 52 percent of participants (31% disagree and 21% strongly disagree) share a

negative response while 21% preferred to remain neutral. On the other hand, 27 percent (12% strongly agree and 15% agree) affirmed to the question.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	12%	46	372
Agree	15%	56	372
Neither agree nor disagree	21%	78	372
Disagree	31%	116	372
Strongly Disagree	21%	72	372

Table 5-27: Seeking employee feedback with regards to training effectiveness

Figure 5-27: Seeking employee feedback with regards to training effectiveness

The fact that majority deny that the feedback of trainees’ after each training session is not taken, clearly indicates gaps in the training evaluation approach of Vietnamese manufacturing organisations. Lack of employee consultation leaves little scope to identify the pros and cons of the training sessions being delivered and evaluate the effectiveness of employee training.

Even though in Q15 and Q16, the trainer’s knowledge and preparedness were found to be appropriate, the responses receive here raises questions on the trainer’s capabilities.

Q31) The feedback of the training program shared by the trainees/participants is valued and implemented in the subsequent training sessions for improvement? (Evaluation)

As an extension of the previous question, the current question intended to ask whether the feedback of the training program shared by the trainees/participants is valued and implemented in the subsequent training sessions for improvement, to which 48 percent (33% disagreed and 15% strongly disagreed). 23 percent neither agreed nor disagreed to the question, and 29 percent (19% agreed and 15% strongly agreed) shared an affirmative response.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	10%	38	372
Agree	19%	72	372
Neither agree nor disagree	23%	86	372
Disagree	33%	122	372
Strongly Disagree	15%	54	372

Table 5-28: Whether employee feedback is valued and implemented

Figure 5-28: Whether employee feedback is valued and implemented

Findings indicate that any feedback shared by the trainees with regards to the training session, post training is not valued by the training managers or coordinators, and this indicates gaps in the training evaluation framework. Employees taking part in the training sessions are in a better position to identify the loopholes, shortcomings, issues, or gaps and offer suggestions for improvement based on which corrective actions can be taken. Moreover, training sessions can be better customised in accordance to the feedback shared by those attending the training.

Q32) You feel that the HR managers follow a participatory approach to training evaluation?

Majority, 51 percent of participants (25% disagree and 26% strongly disagree) shared a negative response that the HR managers follow a participatory approach to training evaluation, while only 25 percent (9% strongly agree and 16% agree) confirm to the idea.

As an outcome of the previous two questions, findings with respect to the current question rightly indicate that the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations fail to follow a participatory approach to training evaluation. While evaluating the effectiveness of the training programs,

the participation of employees' as trainees is not given much importance to, signifying the lack of a participatory approach.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	9%	34	372
Agree	16%	58	372
Neither agree nor disagree	24%	88	372
Disagree	25%	94	372
Strongly Disagree	26%	98	372

Table 5-29: Participatory approach to training evaluation

Figure 5-29: Participatory approach to training evaluation

As discussed in the literature review, (Participatory evaluation) participatory approach to training evaluation helps to enhance the program performance by including ‘stakeholders’ (employees in this case) in the evaluation design, and decision- making (Bedwell and Salas, 2010). It also encourages employee voice and say in the evaluation framework and makes the training useful for the final users (employees) of the training program. While a range of benefits for participatory training evaluation is discussed in extant literature, findings indicate that Vietnamese manufacturing organisations have largely failed to implement a participatory approach and yet to utilise its benefits.

Q33) You feel empowered after evaluation of the training programs takes place?

Despite the fact that employee inclusion/participation in the training programs is not given much importance to in the organisation, a certain section of employees feels empowered after training evaluation sessions, as indicated by 43% (18% strongly agree + 25% agree) of the participants. At the same time, 38% (disagree 21% + strongly disagree 17%) believe that they do not feel empowered.

Table 5-30: Feeling empowered after training evaluation

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Strongly Agree	18%	66	372
Agree	25%	94	372
Neither agree nor disagree	19%	70	372
Disagree	21%	78	372
Strongly Disagree	17%	62	372

Figure 5-30: Feeling empowered after training evaluation

Review of the underpinning literature indicates that empowerment evaluation helps to guarantee the success of a training program by empowering employees with tools and skills to assess the effectiveness of the same (Topno, 2012). Empowered employees are in a better position to take their own decisions, exhibit higher accountability, and remain committed to the organisational goals after being included in the training evaluation program. However, in real-life Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, the scope of employee empowerment is restricted to a certain section of employees who feel empowered, while others do not experience being empowered.

Q34) What did you like most about this training?

The above question is not only open ended, but subjective and encourages employees to convey their feelings and insights about the training they attended. The participants shared different views, however, the most dominant views are included, and analysed here. It was found that the employees were convinced with the knowledge, and training skills of the trainer, phrased as *“trainer’s attributes – knowledge and skills”* which was praised by most of the employees. One of the employees commented: *“The trainers are excellent, no doubt”*. Another one added *‘The trainer’s skills were fantastic as he explained the new systems proactively’*.

Responses shared by the participants also indicated that they liked the way training programs were organised since the very beginning of the training. Few employees were in consensus with regards to the training approach, which was systematic. A participant mentioned *“trainings are consistent and systematic with emphasis on every minute detail start from the employees training needs, duration, completion and feedback”*. Therefore, employees liked the fact that trainings were systematically designed and imparted to the employees based on their training requirements. A participant mentioned: *“The line HR personally visited our team and asked whether anyone needed any specific training based on interests or career plans”*. Others also shared similar response and claimed that the training needs of the employees in each

department are identified by the immediate boss, or supervisor and the requirements are forwarded to the HRD team. One of the participants shared: *“what I liked most about the training was that my supervisor enquired about my training needs and I insisted to be a part of advanced software training and was given”*.

Most of the employees also liked the fact that the training they attended was ‘on the job’ and practical, and this helps to gain work experience along with knowledge. A participant wrote *“I liked the practical, hands-on training given while being theoretically briefed about systems and processes”*. Similar responses were given by many who felt that that hands-on, on the job training helped them to directly implement their learning at work, at machines, and equipment.

Others liked the intervention of the HR managers with regards to seeking employee feedback about the training session, which was part of the evaluation programme. Employees also mentioned that they liked the overall duration of the training program, including small recess (tea breaks) given during trainings to cut down the monotony involved.

Q35) What aspects of training could be improved?

In contrast to the previous question, the current question enquired about the training sessions that still needed improvement. One of the key facts that came up in the overall responses was that the employees felt the **requirement for formal feedback session** after each training session, as currently only verbal feedback was taken. The comments given by employees with regards to feedback sharing were *“I feel that verbal feedback does no good”*, as mentioned by one of the respondents. Similar responses by others were *“I expect proper feedback sessions in pen and paper”*, *“I want feedback system to be improved with a list of questions to be asked seeking training effectiveness”* and so on. Therefore, summing up the responses, it becomes clear that employees want improvement in feedback mechanisms.

On similar grounds, employees were not convinced whether verbal feedback taken from employees were valued, and followed by training department, and implemented for training improvements. Therefore, improvement was supposed to be brought in terms of **valuing trainees’ feedback given post training**. Employees also expected that the training department encouraged more **employee participation** in the training aspects in terms of customising the training module or package according to employee requirements.

Another aspect of training that required improvement was **lack of online training** as experienced by the employees. The participants felt that the training program could be made available online so that employees could access it at any point of time. Extensive of technology for training purposes was also area of improvement as suggested by the employees.

Q36) Please rate your overall level of satisfaction with the trainer.

Majority of the participants in the survey, 72 percent (39% satisfied and 33% very satisfied) shared a positive response as regards to the level of satisfaction with the trainer, wherein 33 percent were very satisfied while 39 percent were satisfied. Comparatively, a lesser 14 percent were dissatisfied and 4 percent very dissatisfied. Overall response indicates that the employees were extremely satisfied with the trainer in terms of his/her training style, knowledge, and skills.

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Very dissatisfied	4%	14	372
Dissatisfied	14%	52	372
Neutral	10%	36	372
Satisfied	39%	144	372
Very satisfied	33%	122	372

Table 5-31: Level of satisfaction with the trainer

Figure 5-31: Level of satisfaction with the trainer

This question examines the level of satisfaction that trainees (employees) have with their trainer. It is likely that the response is a cumulative outcome of (Q15 and Q16) which emphasises on the attributes of the trainer in terms of knowledge, preparedness, and interactivity. Although majority are satisfied, few participants are dissatisfied with the trainer implying that there lies scope for improvement.

Q37) Please rate your overall level of satisfaction with the training program.

Regards to the level of satisfaction with the training program, 41 percent of participants were satisfied while 25 percent were very satisfied. Meanwhile, 17 percent were dissatisfied, and 9 percent were very dissatisfied with the training program. Therefore, not all employees/participants who took part in the training were satisfied with the training, indicating that there was scope for training improvement.

Table 5-32: Level of satisfaction with the training program

Options	Responses (frequency)	Responses (numbers)	Total
Very dissatisfied	9%	34	372
Dissatisfied	17%	62	372
Neutral	8%	31	372
Satisfied	41%	154	372
Very satisfied	25%	93	372

Figure 5-32: Level of satisfaction with the training program

The overall response of the participants with regards to the trainings and evaluation methods in the Vietnamese manufacturing firms is inclined towards the positive side, however, a part of respondents denies. Review of extant literature indicates that a systematic approach to training is satisfactory when it is systematic, well-planned and organised. It is directed towards the accomplishment of training goals and meeting the performance objectives, and therefore is satisfactory (Guest, 2011). Trainings are considered satisfactory by employees (trainees) when it involves sequential steps including identification of knowledge/skill gaps, job analysis, training schedule, timelines, venue selection, duration and training delivery. While designing a systematic training program is an initiative undertaken by the HRM its implications influence the trainees' learning capabilities to learn, and satisfaction with the training program.

5.3. Qualitative data analysis

This part of the chapter presents the responses and findings obtained from the managerial interviews conducted from the three manufacturing organisations. In this research, interview was scheduled with six (06) human resource managers and supervisors of three chosen

companies (Vard Vung Tau, BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam). Two HR managers and supervisors working within human resource department from each Vietnamese manufacturing organisation were targeted for interview. After sending emails and several calls to book an appointment with the managers, three of them could not arrange the meetings. One was on a long business trip overseas, the others had urgent meetings on the date so they cancelled the appointments with the promise to reschedule the meetings. However, due to their busy schedule, the interview with them was not conducted. Luckily, three managers, one from each company, successfully attended the interviews and they did have wonderful time sharing their experience and opinions. They are all experienced HR managers who have been working for their companies for 5-10 years and played a significant role in developing their organisational human resource in general and training in particular.

The interview questions were open-ended, semi-structured questions and seek to understand the HR policies and policies associated with the training and evaluation programs in the organisation. The interview questions were about the types of training programs, frequency of training, and evaluation programs associated with such training, the benefits, and practical challenges faced. Interview allowed the participants to express their views, and experiences, support their claims with examples, and respond to open-ended questions in an overt manner. The elaborate responses obtained from the open-ended questions are illustrated individually for each manager, and similar and dissimilar responses are categorically presented. While analysing the qualitative data, direct quotes obtained from the managerial interviews are included in the discussion to back-up and support the claims made by the managers.

Organisations	Interviewees (HR managers)
VARD Vung Tau Ltd. Company	Manager 1 (M1)
BlueScope Vietnam Company	Manager 2 (M2)

Baker Hughes Vietnam Limited Company	Manager 3 (M3)
--------------------------------------	----------------

Table 5-33: Interviewees participating this research

Q1) What are the current HR policies and practices associated with training programs in the organisation? Does the company carry out training needs analysis (TNA), if yes, how? Please elaborate.

M1 (Vard Vung Tau) the HR manager indicated that the company followed the ‘competency-based training’ as the policy that focuses upon specific skills and competencies. M1 explained that it is different from traditional training approaches, as competency-based training allows the training to be broken down into much smaller units emphasising on a particular skill. M1 commented “*in competency-based training the trainees are able to show their mastery in a particular skill before going for various other skills training*”. All skills are incorporated into modules and at the end of the training session the trainees are entitled to the necessary certification specifying the level of mastery gained in a particular skill. As regards to conducting TNA, the manager disclosed that it is an essential part of the competency training approach as the specific training needs are easily identified. Elaborating on the TNA framework associated with competency-based training the manager disclosed that it involved fourfold benefits namely, it is user-directed, allows better time management, cost effective, flexible, allows personalisation, and allows better workplace integration. In terms of better time management, the training module is broken down into smaller skills and each training is less time consuming. There exists no need to commit to a longer training program and an optimal time can be fit into their busy work schedule. This allows employees to attend small training sessions that help them to take some time off their daily work schedules as a ‘breather’ and learn something new. M1 also disclosed that training modules designed based on the

competency-based approach are often self-paced implying that such learning can be gained at the user's discretion. This also allows better flexibility in terms of training an entire team on a specific skill without the necessity to include an entire big time at once.

M2 (BlueScope Vietnam) the manager revealed that employee training and development was an inherent part of the HRM function and there was a dedicated human resource development (HRD) team to examine the same. M2 remarked *“the training policy is simple and systematically designed based on the training requirements of employees at different levels in the organisation as the training needs and requirements for different level employees are different”*. M2 further commented *“as a part of HR policy, training is linked to employee motivation and overall talent management, training motivates our people, makes them feel confident, skilful and competent in their respective area”*. M2 explained that training was motivating and empowered most of the employees in terms of being able to take their own decisions at the workplace. M2 also affirmed to the fact that TNA was an essential part of the overall training session and this helped to eliminate any irrelevant training that resulted in waste of time and costs. TNA is conducted in different periods of time, especially during performance appraisal where the employees' performances are assessed, knowledge gaps and skill shortages are identified, employees' areas of expertise explored, and accordingly an action plan prepared for training and career development. Therefore, TNA was systematically undertaken as a part of the performance appraisal as well as during 'one-to-one' feedback sessions between the employee and the immediate skip (reporting authority).

M3 (Baker Hughes Vietnam) the manager stressed on need based training that was associated with the organisational goals and objectives and specific to the interests of individual workers, and groups. M3 disclosed that the company did not have a rigid, predetermined policy in place, and this allowed flexibility in customising the training program according to the requirements. M3 commented *“We do not follow a one-size-fits-all approach to training because predesigned*

training sessions meant for an entire year may not align with the requirements of a diverse employee base. We leave adequate scope for ad hoc training so that any urgent requirement for training can be accommodated at any time when required". The manager emphasised on induction training, behavioural trainings, process related trainings, and competency trainings were compulsory for employees at the operational level as included in the HR policies, even though higher level members such as midlevel managers were free to join these training sessions, if they required refresher training. As regards to conducting TNA, the manager explained that it was the very first step of designing a training program, and the TNA policy included employee consultation during usual 'team leader/manager – employee' meet held every week, monthly or quarterly held according to departments.

Q2) What type of training is given to the employees across different levels? How does it contribute to organisational development? Please elaborate

M1 (Vard) stated that the company mainly deals with B2B clients worldwide and hence the training programs are designed accordingly. The trainings to the frontline staff directly interacting with the customers comprise of training on soft-skills and culture. Soft skills trains employees on communicating with clients effectively, build and nurture relationship with clients. Cross-cultural trainings are mainly provided to employees responsible to handle expatriate assignments or overseas projects. These employees need to interact with clients, suppliers, business partners and similar other stakeholders belonging to different cultural groups, customs, ethnicity, values and beliefs, manners and etiquettes. M1 remarked "*Cross-cultural training provides awareness about different types of culture and it becomes easier for expatriates to work with overseas clients without any hesitation or resistance. Therefore, special emphasis is paid on cross cultural training*".

M1 disclosed that mandatory trainings are provided to employees on health and safety across vertical and horizontal levels of the organisation. M1 remarked "*the key legislation on*

occupational health and safety and Duty of Care makes it necessary for Vietnamese corporations to provide training on minimising hazards, accidents, and diseases". Training on health and safety aspects not only train employees on how to remain safe, work safely, but also the use of first aid, safe evacuation during catastrophic situations such as fire, earthquake etc. *"The motive behind such training is to ensure workers feel safe while working with equipment, dangerous equipment, hazardous elements, and so on"*. M1 also disclosed about other trainings imparted to the employees, particularly those working with operations and quality processes which included training on lean aspects and six-sigma. M1 commented *"Vard is a manufacturing company operated in a competitive global market and hence the need for continuous improvement is necessary and this required training on lean, 5S (the 8 wastes), and SIX-SIGMA certification especially belt training...we consider human resource training as a form of continuous learning and continuous improvement and this is deep rooted in our culture"*. Therefore, M1 associated the different types of training with the organisational culture at Vard. M1 mentioned that training exercises contributed towards organisational development in some form either in terms of improving employee behaviour, performance, teamwork, better co-ordination or collaboration. Employees trained on every aspect of manufacturing felt empowered, exhibited leadership skills such as taking appropriate decisions, remaining accountable, and maintaining close relationship with the management.

M2 (BlueScope Vietnam) pointed out an extensive range of training programs were meant for employees at BlueScope Steel at different levels. It is a blend of On the Job and Off the Job training that are imparted according to the requirements. For new joiners, induction training involves making them aware of the organisational policies, goals and objectives, values and vision that are crucial elements they should be aware of. These employees then undergo off the job training also known as 1st level training to give them preliminary knowledge of the work processes, work flows, operations and quality, health and safety, compliance, and theoretical

understanding of overall work procedures and context. This mainly through in-house seminars, lectures, and workshops where employees' doubts are clarified and make them clear about the fundamentals of the business. This involves online written tests to test the extent to which employees have been able to grasp and retain the knowledge. This is followed by off the job training where the employees get the opportunity to apply in actual practice all what has been learnt during the off the job training.

M2 commented *“The employees get hands-on experience through off the job training and understand the importance of integrating time, cost, efficiency with output. Employees as trainees are given soft targets to fulfil, in terms of their work production and under-performers are re-trained”*. The manager pointed out that employee training helped to instil confidence in them, increase their work productivity, minimise errors, and enhance overall profitability of the organisation. Online training modules are well organised and embedded into the intranet to which all employees are given access to. Employees intending to be trained can put their unique staff id and reach the **‘master training manager’** section which is a comprehensive virtual site for employees to access any type of training they desire. It is user friendly site and easily navigable that facilitates employees to download training modules as per need and go through the literature that is drafted in easy language.

M3 (Baker Hughes Vietnam) *“Yes, employee training is at the core of our human resource development and consequently organisational development”*. M2 stated *“We can boast of being the world’s top and only provider of integrated oilfield products and services, and hence intense training is necessary to retain our position hence we require our employees to master the art of business”*. The manager further illustrated that both on and off the job training were part of the overall training curricula in their manufacturing set up. Job training included employees were skilful in handling machine and equipment, running operations and productions process, demonstrate teamwork, and improve efficiency. Safety training was

compulsory to be attended by everyone to minimise damage to machinery and control accidents and use safety devices in a conscious manner.

M3 commented “*Employees are our greatest assets who drive innovation and training acts as a catalyst to this*”. The manager also disclosed that operational level workers were given behavioural training, and training in soft-skills, interpersonal skills and specific professional skills that were required in day-to-day working. The manager illustrated the importance of acquiring communication skills, presentation skills, technical skills, analytical skills, negotiation skills, critical thinking and problem-solving skills, including maintaining the right behaviour and attitude at work. In addition, trainings on cultural awareness were given to employees working with foreign clients. Employees were also offered special training sessions such as promotional trainings that involved training to tenured members to enable them to perform higher level jobs, take higher responsibilities, change management, and leadership skills. These employees were usually the ones who received higher ratings during performance appraisals and deserved superior position in the organisation. *M3 narrated “Look! special trainings for deserving employees, particularly promotional trainings were given to make them ready for higher position and thereby ensure they were fit for leadership positions. Such employees by virtue of their leadership skills fostered innovation, achieved difficult milestones, and set examples for others to follow”*. **Promotional training** is meant to strengthen the leadership capabilities of existing employees who deserve to be promoted to take higher responsibilities and lead the teams.

M3 insisted “*At Baker Hughes Vietnam, we also offer **internship training** through external agencies to fresh engineering graduates which range from six months to even two years and absorb the bright ones*”. The manager elaborated that internship training helped the organisation to find the right talent and recruit potential employees in a cost- effective manner.

Q3) Is evaluation undertaken after every training? How often is training evaluation undertaken in the organisation? Please elaborate.

In response to whether training evaluation is carried out after every training M1 (Vard) disclosed that the evaluation was undertaken for the scheduled training program and not for ad-hoc training that was provided to the employees during emergent situations. M1 commented *“Quick training was often given on an ad-hoc basis to employees in various departments such as design and assembly for building vessels that require customisation just before order delivery while these trainings are as important as the scheduled ones, evaluation is not conducted due to lack of time and budget. However, those attending training are verbally asked about how fruitful that training has been”*. M1 elaborated that in case of ad-hoc training, the trainees were randomly picked to share their opinion about the training, otherwise for scheduled training held almost every quarter; the need for training evaluation was not felt.

M2 (BlueScope Vietnam) the manager disclosed that evaluation of the training programs was conducted formally after every training across the various levels of the organisation. M2 commented *“Training evaluation at BlueScope is conducted not only after the training is delivered, but before, during the implementation, and after the completion of the training program”*. Before training, the HR managers see whether the training and development designed for the respective level will result in their knowledge development and skills necessary to perform the role effectively and whether the training method align with the employees’ learning styles and preferences. During training implementation or while the training is on-going, the evaluator checks whether the trainees are enthusiastically participating in the training activities, whether the training is interactive, and whether the participants are coming late or leaving early. M2 took a deep breath and remarked *“It is too surprising to see how people often arrive late at a training while few give excuses to leave the workshop before its complete and then the training objectives are far from being achieved”*. M2 explained that

once training is complete, a short test is usually taken wherein employees are asked questions about the learning gained, rate the trainer, training activities etc.

M3 (Baker Hughes Vietnam) pointed out that the Line HR managers are committed towards training evaluation, however, not every training need to be evaluated. Small training sessions that were held occasionally were just an extension of the team huddles organised by the team supervisor and conducted during working hours, on-demand. These trainings were usual affairs wherein necessary downloads (updates about recent changes in organisational policies, client demands, working with new technology, or minor changes in work processes did not require evaluation, although these were formal sessions. M3 disclosed that training sessions that exceeded at least 40 minutes were supposed to be evaluated, while usual short training sessions could not be evaluated because cost and time were constraints. M3 remarked *“Evaluation was mainly for those training programs that were planned in advance of the delivery, had a long-term purpose, involved higher budget and it was necessary to calculate its return on investment. These were scheduled training programs where employees’ attendance was compulsory and evaluating the returns on training investment was imperative”*.

Q4) What models are used for evaluating the training program? Please elaborate.

M1 remarked *“we do not depend on a single training evaluation model, but several evaluation frameworks are followed according to situation”*. M1 disclosed that **Kirkpatrick’s four levels** are dominantly used in the organisation as evaluative frameworks for most of the training programs. Elaborating on the process the manager shared that in the reaction stage the delegates (trainees) were enquired as answer *“Do they consider the training relevant?”*, *“Did they enjoy the training?”* and *“Did they like the venue, duration, and trainers’ style of training?”*.

Often, 'Happy Sheets' and post-training surveys were distributed to the delegates in this stage. In the learning stage the evaluators asked questions as to whether the trainees could learn what was aimed to be taught, and whether they gained new knowledge and skills in the form of learning to be implemented at the workplace. Behaviour evaluation raised questions as to whether the trained employees put their learning into effect while working and how far the knowledge was used. M1 stated that it was necessary at this stage to identify whether there were any measurable changes in the behaviour and performances of the employees when back to their job roles. M1 commented "*the use of observation and even interview is made to analyse the change in employee behaviour and how sustainable the change has been. Sometimes it is useful to use 360- degree feedback after training to get feedback about employee behaviour after attending the training, also assessments are designed around pertinent performance settings and explicit KPI's (key performance indicators) are used*". The manager gave especial emphasis on this stage and also disclosed that online assessments were difficult to implement, and these were fruitful when integrated with existing management protocols. The manager explained that in the case of results evaluation, as the final stage, "*it is the Acid-Test*". It helped to measure the effect of the overall training on business environment as an outcome of improved performance from trained employees. The measures included KPIs such as volumes, return on investments, and other quantifiable elements such as quality ratings, number of customer complaints, staff attrition, and retention. M1 stated that a tailored approach to training evaluation was followed and this helped to maintain flexibility in the choice of evaluation frameworks. While the Kirkpatrick model was the main evaluative framework used, there were other models such as Phillips evaluation approach that was used by the human resource department, especially to measure the ROI post training. Using this model made it easier for the evaluators to measure ROI from both, the perspectives of human performance and business outcomes. Emphasising on the Phillips model the manager explained that the ROI was used as a quantitative measure and expressed in the form of a cost-benefit ratio.

M2 responded the training evaluation frameworks were different for the trainings provided at different levels to the employees. As evaluation was conducted before, during, and after the training the use of an orderly evaluation mechanism was necessary. Therefore, training evaluation involved orderly stages, such as evaluation of the context of training, input evaluation, process evaluation, and product evaluation. At the preliminary stage the T and D needs analysis was determined along with the formulation of objectives to identify the extent to which the training goals and objectives aligned with the organisational needs. This was followed by input evaluation that was designed to evaluate the extent to which the training strategies, activities, and procedures supported the objectives identified in the first stage of evaluation. This stage helps to stipulate the specific activities, procedures and activities to make sure it is the best approach with regards to the assessed needs, goals and objectives. At BlueScope Vietnam this stage includes the evaluation of training policies, schedules, budgets, practices and procedures for the training program.

The stage of process evaluation involves an on-going and scientific monitoring of the training program that gives key information to be used to guide the execution of the training program strategies, activities and procedures, and also recognise the success and failures. M2 commented *“At BlueScope Vietnam, this stage is given much importance to as it provides the much-needed feedback with regards to the extent to which training activities and schedule are conducted as per planning, and time, cost, and resources are efficiently utilised”*. Finally, product evaluation entails interpreting and measuring the achieving of training objectives. In simple words it implies that the purpose of this stage is to interpret, measure, and examine the extent to which the organisation has accomplished its short term and long-term goals associated with the training. Therefore, M2 refers to the **CIPP model** of training evaluation. The manager added that there other training evaluation model used to specifically evaluate the outcome of the training programs meant for managerial level employees. The use of a well-tailored four-

step approach helped to measure pre and post training outcomes and helped to measure the objectives, i.e. context and training equipment, i.e. input.

M2 elaborated that while the regularly used evaluation models were useful, few models like that of Kaufman's evaluation framework was also used according to need. M2 stated "*Here at BlueScope Vietnam we use **Kaufman's 5 level evaluation framework** to assess the impact of training with regards to how it benefits the organisation as well as the society it serves*". M2 elaborated that the evaluation levels started with 'enabling' which included evaluating quality input availability such as physical, human, and financial resources, followed by 'reaction' to involve means, methods, and processes efficiency. The next stage 'acquisition' involved areas to identify the extent of individual and group level competencies and excellence at work while 'application' helped to measure the extent of individual and group level mastery within the organisation. Finally, Kaufman's model included evaluating the 'organisational output' to evaluate the payoff to the organisation and 'societal outcomes' to evaluate the extent of payoff to the society within which the organisation conducted its operations.

M3 pointed out "*Not really a specific model is used in every training rather the models were training specific, however most departments followed the **Kirkpatrick model** and it aligned with almost every type of training*". The manager further mentioned the Kirkpatrick model was very systematic and involved every stakeholder in the evaluation process. Start from the very beginning the reaction of the training participants was necessary to understand the extent to which their experience in training was valuable, whether they felt the training was relevant, and whether they felt engaged. The feedback helps to evaluate the outcome of training sessions by way of understanding participants' perceptions and need for improvements. Next, evaluating the extent to which people acquired the necessary knowledge, skills and attitude is also important to understand whether the training objectives are met. The manager put forward 'Equally important is the third level which aims at evaluating the extent to which behavioural

development has been brought as a result of training and understanding whether the necessary knowledge and skills can be applied on the job. This feedback was like a reflection of whether the employees taking part actually learned what was supposed to be learnt. However, if the behaviour of the employees has not changed, it does not mean that the employees have not learnt anything.

Finally, it is important to know the results which are aimed at determining the tangible outcomes such improvement in employee performance, cost minimisation, reduction in error and wastage, and superior quality, employee motivation and reduced turnover intention. M3 pointed out ‘such benchmarks may be difficult to quantify, however, using these parameters help us to measure the return on investments, and produce concrete results of the training program.

Q5) What are the apparent benefits of undertaking the training evaluation? Which evaluative model is the most effective in terms of achieving such benefits? Please elaborate.

With regards to the benefits of training evaluation, M1 came up with a prompt response *“The potential benefits of using evaluation models for the scheduled training program are many and I will demonstrate the most important ones that relate to our company. Most importantly, it helps to determine whether the training program has achieved its objectives. For instance, by measuring the changes in employee behaviour, increased productivity, reduced absenteeism, performance improvements, and consequently higher client satisfaction are few parameters that indicate employee performance”*. The manager elaborated that training evaluation also helped to determine what business impact training programs led to, measure the cost-benefit ratio, and consequently the return on investment for the training programs. Evaluation of the training program helps to determine whether the cost incurred in training worth providing a significant learning experience to the employees, bring in positive behavioural changes, and increased performance resulting in higher business contracts. It helps to measure the bottom-

line value of the training program's impact on the organisation. The manager also pointed out that evaluation of the training program also helps to validate the training needs assessment, instructional strategies, delivery method, target audience (for training), and course content. The manager narrated "*Evaluation is used to assess whether the instructional strategies used in training were effective, for instance, the strategies such as job trainings, case studies, simulation, and other instructional strategies are relevant to the course content and link the training objectives with the course*". The manager also explained that training evaluation helps to understand whether the training strategy is in alignment with the organisational culture.

As regards to the most effective model, the Kirkpatrick four level approach is the most effective one as it provides a holistic framework to measure the success of any training program from multiple dimensions. M1 remarked, "*It is a more inclusive model, a tool that focuses on measuring the outcome of training program from an objective as well as subjective viewpoint, benefits that can be measured in quantitative terms such as ROI and benefits that require qualitative evaluation such as improvement in employee behaviour and attitude*". Therefore, the manager considered the Kirkpatrick model as the best model for evaluating training in a manufacturing organisation.

M2 disclosed that the objectives of the training program at BlueScope Vietnam are designed using the SMART (Specific, measurable, achievable, reliable, and time-bound) approach, and training evaluation helps to identify whether each objective has been achieved, and the extent to which it is achieved. As an assessment tool, evaluation also helps to determine whether the training objectives are achievable, and if not, do the objectives need to be re-framed. M2 narrated "*Evaluation helps to identify if there exist any dysfunctional processes and bring improvement in it*". Training evaluation identified whether the needs assessment is undertaken appropriately and align the training program with the needs and objectives of the organisation. It also helps to examine whether managerial interventions are required in areas other than T

and D (training and development). M2 explained *“It is often found that employee training programs are introduced to resolve complex issues that may require non-training solution and an effective evaluation mechanism can recognise these situations for the overall benefit of the organisation. Moreover, evaluation can be used to identify supportive work environment that facilitate appropriate transfer of knowledge and learning”*.

M2 asserted *“Any evaluative framework cannot be ranked to be superior to the other as all models have their respective strengths and the downside’ while I agree that the Kirkpatrick’s model is widely used in contemporary manufacturing organisations, the use of other models such as Kaufman’s 5 level evaluation framework and the Phillips Evaluation model are excellent in their own ways”*.

M3 commented *“In my opinion, as far as evaluation is used by our human resource team, it is used as a monitoring to examine whether training has been successful in filling the competency gaps in a cost- effective manner. As we (Baker Hughes Vietnam) are a global company we strive to cut down costs and expand in unexploited overseas markets for which both, training and evaluation needs to be of a global standard while ensuring cost-effectiveness. Training evaluation ensures accountability”*. Elaborating on this point the manager elaborated that evaluation check that the training program is in compliance with the competency gaps and that is no compromise on the deliverables. It also assesses the effectiveness of training programs in terms of improvement in employee behaviour, enhancement in knowledge, skills and expertise, superiority of the work quality etc within a specified budget. M3 narrated that *“Evaluation is the only mechanism that provides feedback to the trainer/facilitator, or the training coordinator and this helps to identify the shortcomings of the training session with regards to venue, duration of training session, use of technology, trainer’s knowledge and skills, course content, and methods of training delivery”*. Therefore, evaluation of the training program acts as a mechanism for feedback to identify the loopholes in the entire training process, thereby

taking corrective actions to map the gaps without any delay and ensure that objectives of the training programs are achieved.

Q6) What are the challenges faced by the organisation in undertaking training evaluation?

Please elaborate.

M1 commented *“after the training program the distribution of Happy Sheets reaction survey takes place to seek the level of satisfaction gained by the employees undertaking the training program, however, this does not seem to be the best measure of training effectiveness. It fails to signify whether the participants have acquired the necessary learning that is relevant to their area of work and can transfer the same into improved performances”*. M1 added that the training department often relied upon ‘Happy Sheets’ for evaluating the effectiveness of training and this failed to give a holistic view of the overall program effectiveness. These simple tools are followed to save time and cost of lengthy evaluation process that interfere with the usual working hours. The manager remarked *“although happy sheets is the initial step of the evaluation framework such as Kirkpatrick’s, sometimes it is not feasible to undertake the following steps due to time constraints”*.

M2 responded, *“there are no apparent challenges in our training evaluation and things seem to be going very smooth meanwhile, there is always a scope for improvement in the evaluation frameworks, not in the proposed models but the manner in which it is implemented in organisations”*. M2 commented *“we largely follow the CIPP model after most of the training session and sometimes it seems as it is not in fit with the type of training being delivered”*. The manager also elaborated that the subjective feedback obtained from the employees taking part in training cannot always be relied upon completely as their feedbacks can contain potential bias.

5.4. Conclusion

The overall findings obtained from the employee survey and interviewing the human resource managers are analysed in the chapter. Findings obtained from primary, first-hand information help to understand the training policy and practices and training evaluation followed by the HRM in the chosen Vietnamese organisations in real life scenario. Integrating the findings obtained from each of approaches, quantitative data from the employee survey and descriptive information obtained through qualitative research, the following chapter conducts extensive discussions. The discussions are carried out in context of the theoretical debates undertaken in the literature review.

CHAPTER 6:

DISCUSSION

6.1. Introduction

The discussion chapter interprets and analyses the overall findings obtained from the research and the significance of such findings with respect to the research problems being investigated. The discussions also include the new insights and understanding of the problems being considered for research and investigated using quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, i.e. survey and interviews respectively. The findings obtained from the research are also compared and contrasted with the theoretical discussions carried out in the literature review. This helps to triangulate the empirical findings with the underpinning theories and conceptual models reviewed in the literature.

Major discussions are carried out under specific themes that underpin the research objectives and questions based on which the primary research was conducted. The themes are grouped under demographic information of the participants taking part in the research, followed by themes that underpin the nature and type of trainings imparted by the manufacturing companies in Vietnam, and the effectiveness of such training programs. The subsequent themes emphasise on the training evaluation approach followed by the manufacturing organisations and how effective the evaluation methods are in terms of comprehensiveness, adaptability to organizations, and effectiveness in identifying training gaps and opportunities for improvement. The outcomes of the discussions lead to identification of a proposed training evaluation framework that can be implemented by Vietnamese manufacturing organizations to derive the best possible outcomes of any training program.

6.2. Discussion about demography of the participants

As regards to the demographic profile of the participants comprising of the employees of Vietnamese manufacturing organizations- Vard Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam Limited, it was found that most of employees were males (85%) and

only a small percentage (15%) were females. This implies that the manufacturing companies are mainly male dominated while the recruitment of female employees is very limited. The next demographic factor 'age-group' indicates that a workforce belonging to a diverse age group exist mainly belonging to 36-40 and 41-45 years. The employees had spent a good tenure in the organisations and mainly worked for more than 5 years (i.e. between 3-7 years) and mostly dedicated to the production department, purchase department, finance and accounting, and other departments.

6.3. Nature and type of training in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations

As regards to the type of trainings that the participants had recently attended the most popular ones were product and process trainings, systems training, lean, six-sigma and quality trainings, trainings relating to computer literacy and information and communications technology (ICT). In addition, the employees were trained on software used by the manufacturing company for its business operations and specific to the firm. Employees had also attended different types of trainings associated with personal and professional development and training on enhancement of the behaviour skills. These included training on communication skills, interpersonal skills, negotiation skills, and training on cross-culture that was especially provided to those aspiring to take up expatriate projects. The manufacturing companies chosen for the case studies have international presence and operate in global environment. Therefore, this requires employees to deal with international clients worldwide and hence the knowledge of their culture, etiquettes, and to some extent language becomes necessary. This also helps them to feel confident and comfortable while interacting with foreign clients and carry out negotiations related to business deals. In addition to these trainings, function specific or department related trainings were also provided to the employees, for instance, employees in marketing and sales department and those directly dealing with clients/customers were trained on customer relationship management, client handling, and customer retention strategies.

The type of training included both 'On-the-job' and 'Off-the-job' implying that the Vietnamese manufacturing companies followed a holistic training design. Off the job training programs included employee induction for the new recruits who joined the company, and training on theoretical aspects of the operational processes in different areas and functions. Off the job trainings were given in the form of in-house trainings mainly theoretical in nature briefing employees about the basics of the work, protocols to be followed, key performance indicators to be maintained and how to comply with quality norms, and business ethics and legislations. These included product and process trainings, software trainings etc and imparted through lectures, briefings, and workshops. The employees attended different types of trainings mainly to gain acquaintance with new software launch, or working with new technology at the manufacturing unit, awareness about new work procedures, and personal development.

On-the-job trainings include giving hands-on, practical training at the workplace under the guidance of dedicated trainers, and senior employees acting as mentors to observe the performance of those being trained. This was mainly for those employees newly recruited by the organisation. However, on-the-job trainings are also given to existing employees who required training on new technology, new process, or working with new protocols.

6.4. Preparation for training program in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations

Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is conducted by the human resource department. HR manager and department managers will identify what kind of training their employees need. TNA is done before designing or launching any training program provides valuable input into the nature and type of training that should be imparted to the employees to fulfil their skill gaps that are evident. Theoretically, TNA involves identification of the current training needs of the

employees based upon the knowledge gaps and shortcomings in their skills (Steward, 1999). TNA also helps to ascertain the gap between employees' actual performance and the expected performance at present and in future respectively. It is the foremost step in the training process that helps the HR managers to identify the relevant training needs of employees and accordingly design the training program. Careful design of the training program ensures that the training is relevant and helps to upgrade the knowledge, skills and competencies of the employees while ensuring that their existing skills do not become obsolete.

The manufacturing organizations in the UK follow a systematic approach to training (SAT) to make sure that the employees get the best out of each training program as found in the employee responses from the survey (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009). This aligns with the theoretical discussions carried out in the literature review, which indicates that SAT includes a sequence of stages intended to develop the knowledge, capabilities of the employees and maintain the right attitude at the workplace. It also helps employees to get well acquainted with their roles and responsibilities and perform the task adequately in alignment with the organisational goals (Guest, 2011). The manufacturing organizations in Vietnam, especially the surveyed ones follow the systematic approach to training in conjunction with TNA- an analysis that helps to identify the gaps in the performances of employees currently and what is expected in future, followed by designing training programs to eliminate such gaps (Gelens *et al.*, 2014).

However, it was not clarified whether the Vietnamese manufacturing organizations carry out job analysis as a part of the SAT approach which helps HR managers to identify whether the employees' skill sets and experience match with the job roles and responsibilities that need to be undertaken by them. Other sequential steps in SAT include designing a specific training budget, determining the timelines and scheduling the training, arranging the venue, and procuring resources required for the training. The HR managers intervene to examine such specifics of training are in place and take immediate action based on the shortcomings.

6.5. Effectiveness of training program in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations

Training can be said to be effective if its purpose is met in terms of making employees skilful, knowledgeable and competent to deliver better performance and fulfil the organisational goals. However, there may exist different criteria or parameters to measure the effectiveness of a training program. A range of questions was designed in the survey to seek the effectiveness of the training program imparted by the Vietnamese manufacturing firms to their employees. These included identifying whether the objectives of the training programs were clearly defined, the response to which was mainly positive as shared by the participants. Clear **objectives** imply that the HRM and training team is aware of the purpose of the training being delivered and what its outcomes should be. Formulating objectives is a part of the training design which also includes designing the training plan, schedule, developing content and considering other training needs. Next, the training programs were effective as the training contents are found by employees to be well organised and easy to follow. The trainings can be said to be effective from the fact that the employees in the survey consent that they would recommend such trainings to others in the organisation.

The effectiveness of the trainings given in manufacturing firms in Vietnam can also be assessed from the fact the training materials distributed to the trainees were helpful and could be applied to work. Employees attending the training sessions find that the knowledge they gain are applicable to work implying that the trainings are relevant. Moreover, the trainers delivering the training sessions are also knowledgeable and considered to be fit in terms of preparedness and behaviour. Overall the training received by the employees is also considered effective by them in terms of knowledge enhancement and improving the current level of skills and competencies that could lead to better performance. This is also supported from the findings obtained from the survey indicting that the employees after being trained experienced

improvement in their work performance. The findings correspond to the theoretical claims made by authors in the literature review, for instance, Dent and Holton (2009) performance measurement post training should indicate that employees able to better utilise the organisational resources, deliver superior performance, and contribute towards achievement of organisational goals. Therefore, successful training is one that helps employees to improve performance after gaining knowledge, skills and competencies in their area of work/responsibilities.

Benefits of training program in Vietnamese manufacturing organizations

The main benefits of the training program are that the employees after being trained feel motivated and confident that the training they receive would help them to improve performance. Training also helps them to upgrade their knowledge and improve their skills that are exhibited at the workplace. The employees after getting the necessary training tend to share the learning gained with the co-workers. The importance of training in motivating employees is also identified from the review of existing literature, as Khan (2012) considers training to be a motivating experience. Meanwhile, Eisele *et al.* (2013) explained that training helps employees to gain new skills to enhance their performances, gain higher rewards through job enhancement, promotion, salary increment and gain self-esteem. Self-esteem is identified as higher order need in Maslow's theory of motivation which can be reached by employees who are well trained.

The findings obtained from employee surveys in Vietnamese manufacturing organisations also relate training with motivation, indicating that trained employees are more likely to feel motivated, gain the skills and competencies to deliver superior performance, and achieve higher self-esteem.

6.6. Evaluation of training program at Vietnamese manufacturing organizations

As regards to evaluation of the training programs, the findings obtained from the managerial interviews indicate that different evaluation approaches are followed in each manufacturing organisation in Vietnam depending on the type of training being conducted. **At Vard Vung Tau Ltd.**, ad-hoc training is not evaluated rather evaluation is done by scheduled training programs. The company does not rely on a single training evaluation, but several evaluation techniques are followed. Managerial responses indicate that evaluation is conducted by circulating survey forms in the form of Happy Sheets to employees who have attended training sessions. Such evaluation also meant to identify whether there were any measurable changes in the behaviour and performances of the employees when they carried out their job roles. Other methods used were observation and interviewing employees implemented in the form of 360 -degree feedback to gain insights into employees' behaviour and performance after they have attended the training. As the manager of VARD considered training evaluation to be an 'Acid Test' that helped to measure the immediate effect of the training. Managerial responses indicate that the use of Kirkpatrick model and often the use of Phillips model is made to evaluate training, however, the procedure of the use of such frameworks were not disclosed.

At BlueScope Vietnam, formal evaluation of the training is carried out for each training program across the different organisational levels. The process of training evaluation is different from VARD, as evaluation is conducted before, during, and after the training program using a holistic approach. In each stage, for instance, before the training the HRM ensures that the training modules and content are well designed and align with the training requirements of those to be trained. During the training sessions the HR managers as evaluators examine the behaviour of employees going through the training sessions, their level of enthusiasm, participation, and conduct, and presence. After the training program, short tests or surveys are

conducted to ask simple questions about the effectiveness of the training undertaken. As regards to the use of evaluation models, this Vietnamese manufacturing company uses the **Kaufman's five level evaluation model** that initially evaluates the availability of training inputs such as physical, human, and financial resources, and then 'reaction' that encompasses means, methods, and processes efficiency. This is followed by 'acquisition' to identify the level of individual and group level skills and excellence at work. The model also includes the 'application' stage to measure how far trainees have gained mastery with their work. At the end, the evaluation model involves the evaluation of 'organisational output' as the outcome of output to measure the payoff to the organisation and 'societal outcomes' to assess the scope of payoff to the society. Therefore, training evaluation at BlueScope Vietnam utilise the Kaufman's five level model to evaluate the acceptability and efficiency of the means, methods and processes of the training programs implemented in the organisation. It helps to evaluate training success in terms of the company's overall performance and the return on investment derived as the outcome of the training.

Training evaluation in Baker Hughes Vietnam is different to BlueScope Vietnam in the sense that evaluation is carried out in the former company for selected training program and not for short trainings, huddles, or small sessions to give updates on new software, or changed processes. Baker Hughes conducted training evaluation for trainings that exceeded at least 40 minutes and were planned ahead of time. The approach to training evaluation is quite similar to that of VARD which does not evaluate ad-hoc trainings and considers it necessary to evaluate scheduled training programs carried out for an elongated period and formal in nature. As regards to the training evaluation model the HRM at Baker Hughes follows a framework that is similar to the Kirkpatrick model and can be used to evaluate any type undertaken in the organisation. It helps the evaluators to understand the reaction of employees being trained and the extent to which they found the training was useful in terms of relevancy, and whether they felt engaged. Evaluation of a training program also includes analysing the behavioural

development in the employee after being trained and the extent to which the learning gained in the training could be applied effectively at work. Evaluation in the form of feedback is like a reflection of the training program that helped evaluators to understand whether the employees were able to learn what was supposed to be learnt.

6.7. Benefit of evaluation process

The apparent benefits of the training evaluation at each of the manufacturing companies in Vietnam were manifold as identified in the research. At VARD, the sole purpose of evaluation is to identify whether the objectives of the training have been met, followed by evaluating the changes in employee behaviour, and the extent of improvement in performance, and thereby increase in customer satisfaction. This implies that evaluative models were implemented to measure the outcomes of the training programs by way of behavioural improvement, performance improvement, and ability to deliver better services to clients. Training evaluation made it possible for the evaluators to determine the impact of training on business, measure the cost-benefit ratio, and therefore the return on investment (ROI) due to training program.

Similarly, at BlueScope Vietnam, training evaluation helps to identify whether the objectives (designed on the basis of SMART concept) of the training program has been achieved and to which extent. Evaluation at an early stage helps to determine whether the objectives of the training need to be redesigned or reframed. Evaluation also makes it possible to recognise whether there exist any dysfunctional elements in the training and what improvements can be introduced. It also plays a crucial role in understanding whether immediate managerial intervention is necessary to examine the training effectiveness.

The benefits of training evaluation in Baker Hughes Vietnam is that it is used as an effective tool to check whether training has helped to overcome the skill gaps in a cost-effective way. It also helps to ensure accountability of the training program and assess whether training program has been within the specified budgets, delivered to fulfil the competency gaps without

compromising on training quality and deliverables. Evaluation of the training program also helps to understand whether training has been effective in terms of improvement in behavioural patterns and performance improvement. For this company, training evaluation is the only mechanism helps to gather feedback about the trainer's competencies in terms of training skills and training delivery.

In this research information about the benefits of training evaluation was mainly obtained from the managerial interviews of three manufacturing companies based in Vietnam. While the managers emphasised on several benefits of training evaluation the managers did not emphasise much on knowledge transfer or transfer of learning as an outcome of training. The benefits of training evaluation were not adequately related to the area of human resource development (HRD), although most of the evaluation frameworks focus on 'learning transfer' and HRD.

Irrespective of the training evaluation approach or conceptual model followed by the manufacturing organisations, in general evaluation process comprises of systematic levels such as the participant satisfaction, knowledge gained/learning acquired by the participants (employees attending training), including pedagogical appropriateness categorised into a range of metrics such as training objectives, training content, methodology, material and functional resources (such as questionnaire designed for training, observation by the assessor, self-evaluation), and learning transfer. These levels of training evaluation are meant to identify the benefits of training evaluation from the participants' perspectives while its impact on the organisational goals and objectives is evaluated by calculating return on investment (ROI).

6.8. Gaps in training evaluation in the manufacturing organizations

Findings obtained by surveying the employees of manufacturing firms indicate few gaps in the training evaluation program followed by the Vietnamese organisations. While a systematic approach to training evaluation is followed, there are apparent gaps in 'feedback sharing' and

‘inclusiveness’. After every training session, employee feedback is not encouraged by the HR managers/training co-ordinators thereby leaving no scope to identify the effectiveness of the training already delivered, suitability of the trainer, and appropriateness of the training modules being distributed. This piece of findings obtained from the survey corroborates with the managerial responses obtained from VARD wherein training evaluation is not done for every training or ad-hoc training but only for scheduled trainings. Therefore, the outcome of every training program is not known from the trainees’ perspective with the absence of feedback sharing. Findings also reveal the requirement for formal feedback session post-training (Q25) which allow employees to share their critical views regarding the effectiveness of training based on several parameters.

Another gap is lack of participatory approach to training evaluation implying that the extent of employee participation in evaluation is limited. Even though, the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations conduct training evaluation using appropriate models and frameworks, the most effective use of such frameworks is not made. The employees attending training session do not have adequate voice with regards to sharing their respective views about the training program.

These demonstrated gaps in training evaluation lead to the proposal of an effective training evaluation framework that could eliminate these gaps and help the HR managers to get better values back from their trainings. The proposed framework is fundamentally developed and based on Kirkpatrick’s model and practical results from the research.

6.9. The proposed model

To evaluate a training programme comprehensively, both summative and formative perspectives of evaluation have to be considered. The review of training outcomes helps to determine whether or not training delivered what had been expected. It concerns more or less

measuring the impacts that training has delivered. At the same time, concerning the process of training, with reference to the resultant training impacts, a carefully conducted evaluation can help to reveal the opportunities for improvement (Reay, 1994; Hussey, 1988; Sels, 2002). Kirkpatrick's model provides the framework only for the requirement of measuring outcomes at different levels. Therefore, a more general model will be developed to serve both outcome evaluation (for which Kirkpatrick has laid the foundation in his model) and process evaluation (Sels, 2002). The following discussion is to establish such a model, based on the re-examination of the advantages and disadvantages of the classical work of Kirkpatrick and inputs from his critics.

6.9.1. Kirkpatrick's Model Revisited

Over 40 years of practice have revealed the model's advantages and disadvantages. The classical evaluation model by Kirkpatrick has been universally utilised (Phillips, 1991; Donovan *et al.*, 2001; Bassi and Cheney, 1997; Bernthal, 1995), and it has been exposed to have a number of weaknesses besides strengths. The outstanding characteristics of Kirkpatrick's model lie in its intuition, simplicity, practicality, comprehensibility, communicability, and hence evaluators and others involved in the evaluation can rapidly get familiar with and put the model into practice. These advantages enable evaluators to gain a better understanding of and collaboration from the parties under evaluation. The model guides evaluators on what questions to ask at each level and indicates several suitable measures of training outcomes. Bates (2004) suggests that the model's focus on post-training outcome measures greatly reduces the number of variables with which evaluators need to be concerned. Besides, the higher Kirkpatrick's evaluation level, the more difficult the practice, but due to the independent nature of each level, the model can even be applied partially. However, the categorisation of outcome levels provides little help in signalling the complexity of the journey from training to organisational performance, and the evaluation practice. The extent of levels

of evaluation following the classical model depends on the evaluators' and companies' commitment, skills, resources, and availability of relevant data. The four levels proposed by Kirkpatrick have not always been considered as a real model. It was argued to be a taxonomy or classification and had significant theoretical limitations. So, it could serve as a guideline or an evaluation list rather than a detailed framework for conducting evaluation. Then, following Kirkpatrick's guidelines, evaluators have to create their own tools in practice. The proposed modification and further development of Kirkpatrick's model in the literature aim to achieve a comprehensive and, hopefully, more practical training evaluation framework. The important contributions include those of Phillips (1991) – inclusion of the fifth level of ROI analysis, Warr, Bird and Rackham (1970) – the OEM, CIRO models including context and inputs into analysis, and Holton (1996) – the introduction of the contingent variable class.

The introduction of ROI analysis into the model however brings about a new dilemma rather than a solution. It is always desirable to justify the positive impact of training on the bottom line. Training expenses may be considered futile unless justified by financial returns and evaluation should be considered unfinished until reaching this level (Phillips, 1991). However, no matter how robust the financial accounting system is, a bottleneck still exists in separating improved company performance and benefits due to training from those induced by other sources.

Another problem of ROI analysis regards the comprehensive calculation of the actual costs and opportunity costs of training. The sensitivity of performance and financial data needed is an obstacle in gathering complete data for calculation. Further difficulties can be enumerated here as hidden costs, differences in accounting. Therefore, ROI analysis in this case is for reference only rather than a reliable indicator, and one has to bear in mind possible distortions of ROI. 'Level 5' of ROI analysis complements Kirkpatrick's work to form a comprehensive checklist rather than adding practicality to the model.

Another phenomenon in evaluation is the comments on Level 1 – Reaction, considering it a ritual after training that provides limited information for assessing training impacts. Nevertheless, this is the most exercised procedure in training reality because of the simplicity of the task, habit of the trainers/training organisers, and their inability to go beyond this level. Analysis and utilisation of information on reactions are likely to be superficial (Johnson, 2004). Trainers can even manipulate the answers on the trainee feedback questionnaires. For instance, favourable exam marking by the trainer during a training course may lead to favourable feedback in the ‘happy sheets’ by the trainees in return. Empirical research studies show the loose relations between reactions and training impacts at other levels. It is pointed out that the prediction of training impacts based on trainee reactions – Level 1, is not always valid (Alliger and Janak, 1989). From the perspective of the training providers, or customer-service point of view, information on reactions is very useful for improving consequent training courses. From the company point of view, reactions from the trainee may reflect the effectiveness of the selection of the training partners and partly express the individual needs of the trainees.

Therefore, reactions data are useful provided that they are not from the ‘smiling sheets,’ gather more than just the traditional administrative data, and are analysed properly. Anyway, empirical research studies have always suggested caution in interpreting data on trainees’ reactions.

For the other levels of the classical model, one may ask the following question: when training impacts have been comprehensively assessed at the Results level, is it necessary to evaluate impacts on Learning and Behaviour levels? Or, when training impact evaluation at the Results level is impossible, what is the value of the evaluation at Learning and Behaviour levels? Empirical research studies give several warnings here (Alliger and Janak, 1989). Examining Learning, Behaviour and Results individually helps to track the training impacts at individual, business unit, and organisational levels, and therefore gradually justifies training efforts.

Connecting them in a chain of training impacts indicates the facilitation of organisational learning in relation to training, as well as level of knowledge retention and desired practice in organisational operation.

Therefore, the sole evaluation of training impact at the highest level is not sufficient. In reverse, when Results evaluation is unachievable or not reliable, learning and behaviour can serve as useful indicators, better predicting organisational results (Alliger and Janak, 1989).

To sum up, performing a sound evaluation at every level as proposed by Kirkpatrick might be more valuable and practical than trying to establish a causal chain between the levels.

It is also noted that because the Kirkpatrick model has been considered a classification, or taxonomy of evaluation, evaluation is limited in each level without examining the relevant variables with potential effects on training impacts. These variables can partly provide explanations of the corresponding training outcomes. Moreover, the classical model started *after* training delivery has finished, and the whole pre-training process is overlooked. If the training evaluation follows Kirkpatrick's model without consideration of factors important to the firm such as business strategy, business training needs, individual trainees' training needs, the conclusion may not be robust enough. It provides only the measures of training impacts in a predetermined direction, without indicating whether the training delivered is what the company and the trainees need, whether or not the training strategy is appropriate, and whether training is the solution for the company's performance issues. Following Kirkpatrick's model, if return on training investment is positive, the company may pursue training the same way with the same trainers and for the same trainees, without recognising that other training areas, other training content, or another solution other than training can help the company achieve better performance, possibly at a lower cost. Therefore, several other evaluation models and

practical guidelines introduce the important step of reviewing the pre-training process (Warr *et al.*, 1970; Rae, 2002).

Besides, except for the period of training delivery in a laboratory environment, the outcomes of training are realised in the real work environment. Therefore, training evaluation has to consider the influences of work environment factors. A majority of research studies largely focus on identifying or confirming the effects of those factors. Widening the evaluation perspective, one also has to take socio-economic and cultural aspects into consideration because those predate and accompany training and are both influential and dynamic. Selecting the relevant variables depends on the specific business context, but there are conventional and confirmed variables, e.g. personal characteristics, cognitive ability, organisational commitment, training motivation, link to organisational goals as compiled by Holton (1996) with significant relationships to the levels of training outcomes. Thus, the inclusion of the facilitating and inhibiting factors relating to training outcomes might be another improvement for Kirkpatrick's model.

The discussion above leads to the proposal for the following training evaluation model.

6.9.2. The proposed model

A typical model has to embody a number of components: elements (constructs), relationships, boundaries, system states, deductions about the theory in operation, and predictions about elements (Klimoski, 1991). Kirkpatrick's four levels are not a complete model but provide stepping stones for a more complete training evaluation model.

Basically, the proposed model is developed based on the classical four-level model and adjustments suggested by Holton (1995). Since Reaction has been revealed to be of controversial value to indicate the results of training, only the last three levels of Kirkpatrick's

model are kept at the core of the proposed model (but Reaction is rearranged and discussed later). The results are evaluated under the influence of the training-related actors, namely trainer, trainee, and organisation. The interactions of these actors start from the beginning of the training cycle and last even after training has been delivered. Therefore, the main training related activities are included in the model, represented by the training cycle and the learning transfer process. All are embedded into a broader environment, where the relevant factors: Socio-cultural, Legal, Economic, Political and Technological (SLEPT – environment analysis model [Pettigrew, 1992]) and specific characteristics of the industry are analysed.

Retaining Kirkpatrick's classical elements (Learning, Behaviour Change, and Results) and with the introduction of intervening factors, the proposed model retains the straightforward nature of Kirkpatrick's work and at the same time is augmented with the power to validate training evaluations. The model incorporates both the pre-training components of the training cycle and post- training learning transfer process so that it offsets the shortcomings of the four-level model in neglecting contextual factors. The model is presented in such a way that the outcomes of training have direct relations to and are moderated by the characteristics of the pre-training process and external factors. These characteristics are identified by reviewing the literature in the previous chapter and consideration of specific contextual factors. The full version of the proposed model is presented below and detailed discussion about the model is also given.

Figure 2-7: The proposed model of training evaluation

In the core of the proposed model are the three constructs of the four-level model: learning, behaviour change and organisational results, reflecting the learning transfer process. The linkages among these three constructs will be examined, but in essence, this examination is conducted with reference to the moderating effects of the context and characteristics of the actors. The Reaction level from the original four-level model is not omitted but integrated in the Training Audit function of the training process. The evaluation of trainees' reactions is usually conducted right at the end of any training course. The previous work of Alliger and Janak (1989) suggests using reactions as moderating factors to learning, rather than one of the outcomes of training. Moreover, reactions were not empirically proven as a reliable predictor of other outcomes, so the trainees' reactions after training courses will be considered for formative evaluation purposes (i.e. how to modify training to maximise its potential contribution to individual and organisational effectiveness).

As analysed in the previous part, it is virtually impossible to have reliable calculations of ROI for training activities. Therefore, ROI analysis is not included in the model at level 5, nor is considered as a function of the evaluation practice at Level 4 - Results.

In the proposed model, three actors involved in pre-training and post-training periods are included: the organisation (the management and internal business environment), the trainee, and the trainer. They are all included inside the recurrent process of training, from needs assessment to training audit. The involvement of each actor is significantly different in the pre-training and post-training periods. The trainee's changes in knowledge, skills and attitudes are developed significantly in the classroom and his behaviour changes happen in the workplace. However, the role of the trainer is supposed to be limited mainly in the classroom during training delivery.

Meanwhile, the role of the organisation, mainly in facilitating an enabling transfer environment, is crucial to the process as well as the outcomes of training (Bates, 2004).

Ideally the involvement of trainer, trainee and organisation exist throughout the pre-training process. This ensures that the needs of the organisation as well as the individual would be addressed by training. This secures the relevance of training content or customises the content to the specific group of trainees. This helps the organisation to create favourable conditions to help its trainees to translate knowledge into work practice. Hence, in the proposed model, the roles of the three actors will be examined at each step of the training process to provide a better explanation of the resultant training outcomes.

The outcomes at the three levels are evaluated in connection with the relationships of the players and their attributes. The attributes examined are those regarded of most importance, selected after reviewing the existing research studies. Besides, some specific characteristics of

the business under evaluation might be included. Hussey (1988) provides a set of basic attributes for consideration.

At the learning level, outcomes are largely influenced by the interaction between the trainer and the trainee in the classroom environment. The existing empirical studies show that learning depends on ability, level of motivation of trainers and trainees, individual needs of the trainees, the trainers' skills, and training facilities. Ideally, learning level is measured before and after training to identify changes, and the expectations of the trainers and the trainees have to be taken into consideration. However, it is not usually achieved in reality when the course-end examinations are usually used to screen the trainees for deciding on a certification award only. Behaviour change happens when the trainee has returned to the real work environment. The level of behaviour change is essentially influenced by motivation and facilitating/inhibiting factors in the work environment. If individual needs and expectations in applying new learning into practice are met, as facilitated by the immediate supervisor for instance, the possibilities to attempt and maintain positive behaviours are considerable. The role of the trainers is more limited at this level, but it is likely to have a certain influence when their assistance is another source of motivation that makes the trainee more confident. If the training course includes sections of planning for the trainee's change when returning to work, the role of the trainers needs to be examined. The trainers may provide follow-up technical assistance to the trainees in the areas that work supervisors or managers may not. The role of the organisation, from HR personnel or senior managers, is of a different importance as they can help the trainee to feel secure in transferring knowledge to work. Therefore, all three actors contribute to behaviour change and will be analysed at this level.

Once training matches business strategy, it is then realistic to link behaviour change and results. At this level, the two players to be examined are the trainee and organisation. As mentioned earlier, the ideal measure of the ultimate results from training for firms is the quantifiable

improvement in financial data. Reliable information on this feature is not likely; therefore, the use of several proxies showing training outcomes at this level is necessary. The proxies include output, sales, employee turnover, wastage saved, rate of accidents, sales per employee, market share, stock values. Furthermore, a number of qualitative indicators are also useful, like the competitive position of the organisation after training, opinions on perceived organisation image, capability to design, development and introduction of new products to market, and corporate values (Aragon-Sanchez *et al.*, 2003).

The modular characteristic of Kirkpatrick's original work is preserved in this new proposed model. Focus can be directed at any level, be it learning, behaviour or result, as long as the appropriate environmental factors are taken into consideration. The model is developed with the intention of embodying the total aspects of training evaluation into a framework. This proposed model provides a general framework for training evaluation. In practice, the evaluation design has to consider the specific evaluation environment, and the availability of various data sources.

CHAPTER 7:

CONCLUSION

7.1. Introduction

This chapter concludes the thesis by integrating the objectives and questions designed in the first chapter. Data obtained by enquiring into these research objectives/questions are compared and contrasted and linked with each of the objectives to conclude the extent to which the aims and objectives are fulfilled. This chapter also provides suitable recommendations to the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations in terms of implementing better evaluating methods in a feasible manner. The contribution of the study in terms of adding value to theoretical knowledge and contribution to the management is also given. Finally, the chapter ends with a brief outline of the scope for future research.

7.2. Conclusion

The current chapter concludes the entire thesis by revisiting the research aims and objectives formulated in the first chapter and integrating it with the findings obtained from the primary research. The research aim and objectives are also linked with the literary findings obtained from the theoretical discussions carried out in the literature review. The objectives of the research were to undertake a critical review of extant literature with regards to training and training evaluation frameworks, followed by examining the current practice of training evaluation in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam. The research also intended to identify the challenges in the training evaluation framework of manufacturing firms in Vietnam. The final objective was to develop a strategic training evaluation framework to enhance the long-term benefit of training programmes and the overall performance of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam.

Considering the objectives, and most importantly the last objective of the research, the exploratory research was followed to develop knowledge, or theory in the form of a strategic training evaluation framework for Vietnamese manufacturing organisations, an area where

extant studies are inadequate. Anyhow, the last objective was reached after ensuring that each of the previous objectives were met. Meanwhile, in the next section, each of the objectives is linked with the findings obtained from the literature review, employee surveys and managerial interview. Moreover, the chapter summarises the overall content of the thesis mainly the findings obtained from the case studies, employee survey and interviewing the human resource managers of the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations and the knowledge gained from theoretical debates undertaken in the literature review.

7.3. Linking objectives with the findings

Objective 1: To undertake a critical literature review on training and training effectiveness evaluation and different frameworks of training evaluation

Review of extant literature provided an in-depth knowledge of training, its importance, effectiveness, benefits and challenges. As a key human resource management (HRM) function, the different types of training, aspects, and steps of training are also reviewed in literature. The systematic approach to training (SAT) is also emphasised upon in the literature review by emphasising on the viewpoints and insights of academic scholars and researchers in the HRM domain. As regards to training effectiveness, the impact of training on fulfilling organisational needs, employee motivation as a part of organisational behaviour, implications of training program, and its importance in building knowledge organisation.

Training is defined as the systematic acquisition of skills, rules, ideas or attitude that helps in performance improvement in a working context (Goldstein, 1993). Therefore, training occurs in the form of a planned intervention designed to improve the job performance level of an individual. As compared to training, the concept of development is associated with improving an individual's potential for future role in a workplace, implies that it has long term orientation. The types of training were reviewed as skills training, quality training, technological training,

soft skills training, legal training, managerial training and safety training. The benefits of training to organisations were identified in the form of proper utilisation of resources, particularly human resources, increase in profits, improvement in workforce morale, commitment and reduction in employee turnover. It also helps an organisation to keep up and stay ahead of the competitors in a competitive business environment. Training benefits from employees' perspectives were reviewed as improvement in employee performance at difference levels, increase in the likelihood of internal promotion and career progression, the need for less supervision and more confidence, higher job satisfaction and low turnover intention. Most importantly, training helps employees to adapt to the changes taking place in the internal and external business environment, encourage creativity and innovation. While training includes several benefits, the challenges are also inclusive of several aspects such as inconsistency, lack of flexibility, and training costs.

The training process incorporates a systematic program that initiates with the training needs analysis (TNA), designing appropriate training program, delivery of the training program, and finally training evaluation. The first step – TNA involves identifying the training needs of employees by assessing the performance gaps between their actual performance and the extent of performance expected from them. The next step involves designing the training program by way of defining the training objectives, selecting training methods and materials, designing training package/content, and hiring trainer. The actual training delivery involves imparting the learning in a scheduled venue to a pre-determined number of participants in a stipulated period of time. The final step incorporates training evaluation which involves determining the strengths and weaknesses of the training program by seeking feedback from the trainees/employees taking part in the training session. Training evaluation is also a systematic process that involves planning, implementing, completion, and dissemination of training evaluation, and finally reporting. The main approaches to training evaluation, as identified in the literature review, are participatory evaluation and empowerment evaluation. Meanwhile the

key methods of evaluation incorporate quantitative methods, qualitative methods, and mixed methods that integrate both quantitative and qualitative methods.

After conducting a critical review of the underpinning literature related to training, the current study moves to a theoretical discussion on the concept of evaluation, and related evaluation frameworks such as the CIRO framework, CIPP model of training evaluation, Kirkpatrick's model of training evaluation, and the Phillips ROI (return on investment) evaluation model. The CIRO framework includes context as the factors that require identification of training needs, establishing training objectives that align with the organisational goals, culture, climate and behaviour. It also incorporates 'input' as the training design and delivery of training activity, followed by reaction as the quality of experience that trainees get. Finally, training outcome incorporates the accomplishments gained from three activity levels, immediate level, intermediate level, and ultimate level. In each level the different behavioural changes in employees are ascertained in terms of changes in skills and attitude, transfer of the same to work, and finally performance improvement respectively. The CIPP model is similarly a four-step training evaluation approach that includes context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and product evaluation. The context evaluation involves problem analysis such as planning, identifying training needs, and objective setting. Input evaluation incorporates seeking information about the resources available for training delivery, and achievement of training goals, while process evaluation refers to whether any changes are required in the work environment. Finally, product evaluation is associated with the program outcomes of the training, and decides whether to continue with similar training, modify, or terminate the program.

Review of the literature also indicates that the Kirkpatrick's model serves as a robust framework of evaluation comprising four stages, namely, reaction, learning, behaviour, and results. The reaction stage captures participants' reactions as regards to how they felt about the program they attended, and the extent of their satisfaction. The learning stage indicates the

extent to which the trainees learnt the skills and knowledge, and perceptible changes in their attitudes. In the third stage, behavioural changes are measured as an outcome of attending the training program. Finally, in the last stage, the results of the training program is analysed by implementing quantitative techniques such as return on investment, quantity and quality of production, absenteeism and turnover, and similar other factors. The last training evaluation model discussed in the literature review was the Phillips ROI model that evaluates training from a financial perspective. This framework also provides an additional dimension to Kirkpatrick's model adding to its four stages, thereby providing a methodology to measure the financial contribution if training to the organisation.

Therefore, the first objective was fulfilled by conducting a review of existing literature relating to training, and training effectiveness, training evaluation, and frameworks of training evaluation. After gaining in-depth theoretical knowledge of the aforementioned concepts and frameworks, the next objective intends to examine how manufacturing firms in the Vietnamese context use training evaluation.

Objective 2: To examine the current practice of training evaluation in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam

The current objective to examine the current practices of training evaluation in manufacturing sector in Vietnam, employee survey and managerial interviews was carried out. Surveying 372 employees working with various functional areas such as production, purchase, finance and accounting, marketing and other departments, helped to gain empirical understanding of the training practices and evaluation mechanisms followed.

The training program that the respondents (employees taking part in the survey) had attended recently were systems training, product and process related training, lean, six sigma and quality training, computer related trainings, and training on ICT (information and communications

technology), advanced software training specific to the manufacturing firm. Training also included knowledge of cross-culture, trainings on interpersonal skills, communication and customer relationship management. The main reasons for attending training for most of the participants were to get acquainted with new technology, followed by working knowledge of new work procedures, personal development, and others. The trainings provided by manufacturing firms in Vietnam included both, off the job and on the job training wherein the latter provided practical, hands on experience to the employees relating to work. Surveys also indicated that the training department headed by the HR managers conducted training needs analysis (TNA) which is an essential part of any training evaluation framework. Moreover, the manufacturing organisations in Vietnam follow a systematic approach to training (SAT) to make sure that the trainees get the best out of each training session.

Overall findings from the employee survey also indicate that the objectives of the training session are clearly defined by the training team before the actual training delivery. The content of training program is also organised and easy to follow, while the training materials distributed to the participants are helpful. Employees who attended various forms of trainings were also able to apply the trainings to work implying that the trainings were relevant, work centric, and applicable. Survey also revealed that the trainers are knowledgeable about the training topics, well-versed with the training content and well prepared to conduct the training sessions. The quality of the training program with regards to its content, relevancy, objectives, knowledge, and preparedness of the trainer, and applicability in actual work environment was identified to be high. At the same time, the quantity of the training programs in terms of duration and length of the training was also found to be appropriate.

The training room, venue, the training facilities for the training program designed by manufacturing firms in Vietnam is also found to comfortable and adequate. The trainees after attending the trainings feel confident to apply their learning to work and have experienced improvement in their work areas. Such employees also feel comfortable to share their learning,

knowledge and skills with the co-workers. Employees after being trained also feel that the learning has been effective in terms of knowledge enhancement and improvement in the skills and competencies. The trainings are also found to be effective as regards to enhancing the motivational level of those who attended training. The employees, majority of those who attended training sessions also feel that the training will help them in their future work endeavours. After being trained, the employees feel empowered in terms of taking own decisions to complex work related that arise in the work environment. In addition to the above findings relating to training evaluation in Vietnamese training organisations, it was also found that the trainees would possibly recommend the trainings they attended to others.

Interview conducted from human resource managers of the same Vietnamese manufacturing firms provided a deeper insight into the nature of trainings provided to the staff members, and the related evaluation mechanisms being followed.

Objective 3: To identify the challenges in the training evaluation framework of manufacturing firms in Vietnam

A range of challenges in the training evaluation frameworks was identified from the data obtained from employee survey as well as qualitative information collected from managerial interviews. One of the key challenges identified from employee survey was in terms of lack of employee participation and interaction in training implying that employees' voice was not given much importance to. The human resource department conducting the training evaluation program does not encourage adequate participation of the trainees and their interaction with those evaluating the training sessions. In many cases, as responded by the participants, the time allotted for training was considered insufficient. This is likely to hinder the training and evaluation of training program in terms of allowing employees adequate time to learn, acquire skills, practice, and clarify doubts. Employees taking part in the training may not be able to

offer their feedback about the effectiveness of the training program, and any changes needed in the overall training program. Findings from the employee survey also reveal that not all employees are encouraged to give feedback about the training program while training evaluation is undertaken by HR managers. Therefore, the insights of those taking part in the training are not considered much important neither their experiences are shared to identify the loopholes in the training programs. Findings from the survey also disclose that feedback (if any) about the training is shared by the employees, it is not valued much neither implemented in the subsequent training sessions to bring improvement. Overall, lack of participatory approach to training evaluation is found indicating that employee inclusion in the evaluation framework of Vietnamese manufacturing firms is not given much importance. Lack of employee participation in the evaluation of training program indicates lack of consultation, lack of open communication and sharing feedback from employees in the evaluation and failing to identify the actual gaps in the trainings delivered.

The persistent challenges in the training evaluation were also identified from the managerial interview. Findings disclosed that evaluation often involved distributing ‘Happy Sheets’ to the employees to capture employees’ reactions, however, it is not the best measure to understand the effectiveness of the training program.

Objective 4: To develop a strategic training evaluation framework to enhance the long-term benefit of training programmes and the overall performance of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam

This objective was designed to propose a holistic training evaluation framework to the human resource (HR) managers and the training department of the case study organisations in the Vietnamese context. The strategic training evaluation framework must be developed in accordance to the strategic goals of the organisation in question as well as the goals and

objectives of the training programs implemented by the human resource department. The development of the training evaluation framework will also be based on the gaps or shortcomings identified in the evaluation process followed by each of the organisations being surveyed.

Findings indicate that the different Vietnamese manufacturing organisations follow different approaches to training evaluation; however, the process of training evaluation is similar to training evaluation models identified in extant literature. For instance, training evaluation at VARD follow the distribution of Happy Sheets to the participants post training seeking their response about the training in terms of their experience, learning, and whether the skills gained could be applied at the job. Evaluation also intended to assess any measurable changes in the behaviour and performances of the participants post training and the extent to which such changes were apparent when they were back at work. Evaluation also included the use of 360-degree feedback post-training to get feedback about employee behaviour after attending the training. Training evaluation in this organisation is characterised as the ‘Acid-Test’ which helps to measure the overall outcome of training in terms of improved employee performance and organisational profitability. Organisations such as VARD include measures for training evaluation such as return on (training) investments, and other quantifiable measure such as increase/decrease in customer complaints, quality ratings for the company, and similar other. Overall, no specific training evaluation model was followed in the organisation and evaluation frameworks were adapted according to the type of training delivered. However, there are underlying gaps in the training evaluation approach as over dependency on ‘Happy Sheets’ does not offer a comprehensive review of trainings delivered. Even though the managerial interview purport that the use of Kirkpatrick model is made, there exist persistent gaps in the full-fledged use of such frameworks by the HR managers.

Apparent gaps in the training evaluation were also identified in other Vietnamese manufacturing organisations such as BlueScope Vietnam and Baker Hughes Vietnam. At

BlueScope Vietnam, training evaluation involved systematic stages comprising of input evaluation, process evaluation and product evaluation. The initial stage involved assessment of the training and development needs incorporating the analysis of the extent to which training goals and objectives were met. Similarly, input evaluation involved assessing the extent to which training strategies, activities, and procedures supported the training objectives. Process evaluation stage involved continuous and systematic monitoring of training to get access to crucial information to identify the success or failure of the program. It also helps to find out the extent which trainings are conducted in accordance to the planning, and time, cost, and whether efficient use of resources is practiced. Finally, product evaluation helped to construe, assess, and inspect the extent to which short term and long terms training goals were achieved. Technically, this is the CIPP model of evaluation followed by the company, despite the existence of shortcomings of this model which the HR department/training team failed to acknowledge. Managerial interview also hinted the use of Kaufman's model at the organisation when it is necessary to measure the impact of training for social cause, that is, the improvement in employee skills and knowledge as well as behaviour to serve not only the clients but also undertake activities for social welfare. This evaluation was in the form of assessing the organisational output to measure the payoff of the training to the organisation and social outcomes to measure the extent of payoff to the society of which the organisation was an important part. Finally, the manufacturing company Baker Hughes Vietnam did not use any specific model for evaluating any training program and the use of evaluation process was customised according to the training delivered. Managerial interview however disclosed that training evaluation helped to assess whether training helped to provide tangible outcomes such as cost minimisation, performance improvement, minimal defects, control in wastage, and quality improvements.

The Vietnamese manufacturing organisations use different training evaluation approaches, process and frameworks; yet focus mainly on the short-term benefits in the form of employees

‘skill enhancement, knowledge development, and overall improvement in organisational performance by way of improvement in the KPIs such as cost control, quality up-gradation, and return on investment.

The manufacturing firms in the Vietnamese context have failed to incorporate long term goals in their training evaluation approaches and thereby failed to achieve long term benefits. Managers in their interviews claim the most effective use of popular evaluation models, failing to address the shortcomings in each of the evaluative frameworks. Moreover, employee surveys clearly reveal the presence of inherent shortcomings in the training evaluation approaches followed by the organisations, which were not disclosed by the managers in the managerial interviews. Lack of employee inclusion in the training evaluation, often low employee participation, and lack of feedback sharing are few of the loopholes in evaluation approaches followed by the organisations.

Based on the theoretical reviews and debates carried out in the literature and findings obtained from employee survey and managerial interview it is an emerging requirement that the Vietnamese manufacturing develop a strategic training evaluation framework similar to the Kirkpatrick model integrated with long term goals to derive prolonged benefits. Alternatively, the HR managers/training departments can straightforwardly adapt the Kirkpatrick model in a full-fledged manner, eliminating any limitations that exist. The adaptation of a holistic model such as the Kirkpatrick model could be integrated with the strategic goals of the organisation as well as SMART objectives designed for the training program. Manufacturing organisations may also follow a culture of continuous learning, or long-long learning and such practices integrated with the training evaluation framework directed towards achieving long-term benefits.

The Kirkpatrick model may be customised according to the requirements of a manufacturing company to achieve the best possible outcomes of the evaluation framework. The Kirkpatrick

model is apt for the manufacturing firms as a holistic framework with four successive levels of evaluation including reaction/customer satisfaction, learning/acquiring skills, knowledge, attitude/behaviour, transfer of skills, knowledge, and behavioural attitude at the work environment, and finally outcomes/results. AlYahya and Norsiah (2013) explain that the four levels are meant to principally help in ensuring the appropriateness of the training effects on a manufacturing organisation. Kennedy, Chyung and Winiiecki (2014) argue that the secondary intention of such categorisation is to help in assessing training design and implementation so that continuous improvement can be undertaken. As applied to the Vietnamese manufacturing firms the levels of the Kirkpatrick framework can be developed strategically straight from the preliminary level.

At the participant reaction stage evaluation entails identifying and measuring the reactions of workers/employees who attended the training. It may entail questions as to how well the participants liked and felt satisfied with the program. The rationale for carrying out a reaction level is to gain valuable insights for future training programs, which are frequent in manufacturing firms. It also helps to collect feedback about trainers' appropriateness, provides analytical data for managers, and relevant data to address upcoming training programs whether in the short-run or long run (Kirwan, 2016). The level of reaction-evaluation makes possible information collection on key areas including the training facilities and facilitator, trainees, schedule, and other elements relevant to the manufacturing industry. Following this level of training evaluation is feasible because it is cost effective, easy to administer, adaptation to the type of training such as production, supply chain, logistics and not threatening to the trainers or trainees.

Advocates of this evaluation model such as Stufflebeam and Coryn (2014) consider reaction to be important for three core reasons (i) comments received from participants or their perceptions help the firm to take managerial decisions as to whether go on with the funding of training or hold back the same, (ii) In-depth insights and feedback from participants may help

to enhance the quality of the training programs, and (iii) it helps to assess whether participants enjoy the training, get involved, feel interested and reap maximum benefits from the program. Review of published literature advocates the first reason, i.e. it helps managers to take informed decisions based on comments obtained from participants'. If the main purpose of training program in a manufacturing firm is to provide rewards to those who perform better or revive flaccid spirits at organisational costs, consequently a comprehensive performance-based evaluation is misguided. In this stage, many manufacturing companies such as VARD use 'Happy Sheets' as a simplified reactions assessment which may not be adequate. 'Improving training programs' is the second reason, and feasible if it supports the first reason. If enhancing the participants' interest of training program fails to unfavourably affect the program's efficiency or effectiveness, then these alterations may lead to improvements. The third important reason links participants' enjoyment and/or interest in training to getting benefits from the program. Even though, lack of empirical studies exists to demonstrate an apparent correlation between 'end-of-course' ratings and the level to which trainees apply the learning on job, it can be experimented at big manufacturing firms where trainings are frequent and indispensable, and equally important is applying learning at work.

Level two of the model 'Learning outcomes', conducts assessment of learning taking place throughout the training program. It includes what ideologies, standards, techniques and facts were understood and assimilated by the participants. However, it does not concern how these ideologies, facts and techniques are used on-the-job, rather this level evaluation makes sure that the knowledge and skills promote specific employee behaviour on-the-job that has been learned. Nevertheless, in manufacturing organisations it may assure that the participants (i) acknowledge when to make use of learned behaviour gained from training, (ii) get an opportunity to demonstrate such behaviour, and (iii) most likely to use the learned behaviour when the opportunity is identified.

In manufacturing firms, a simple approach to measure the change, or enhancement in participants' knowledge and skills is using pre-testing and post-testing. This type of level 2 evaluations is often used less frequently relative to level one mainly because the former necessitates increased efforts to suitably develop a valid test, particularly, if the outcomes are used for the purpose of decision making. Even if, this type of training evaluation is effectively designed and capable of addressing validity problems, the best an evaluator in a manufacturing firm can do is to identify whether the core objectives of the training program have been achieved.

The third level of Kirkpatrick's training evaluation deals with measuring behavioural changes on the job and technically referred to as 'training transfer'. Transfer of training is crucial for manufacturing companies such as VARD, BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam because these operate in competitive global environment where client requirements, technology, operational processes, quality standards are subject to frequent changes and hence trainings need to be designed accordingly. To what extent employees have acquired new skills according to market changes and the extent to which learning is applied on the job is crucial to sustain the competitive forces that impact the firm. Evaluation methods at level three incorporate performance contracts, direct observation, peer interviews, and/or surveys using questionnaires. However, training evaluation at this level with regards to behavioural changes is difficult as compared to the reaction and learning evaluation. One of the direct ways to measure performance improvement post training is to make use of existing documentation. Evaluators at this level can document output, quality and quantity of output, time and motion (time taken to complete a task), extent of waste, idle time, efficiency and similar other measures relevant to a manufacturing firm. These measures provide crucial information reflecting change in performance and detecting performance gaps after delivery of training.

Level four of the Kirkpatrick framework replicates the evaluation of impact of training on business outcomes, such as reduction in workers' accidents at the manufacturing site, reduction

in scrap, waste minimisation, cost control at different manufacturing units, and increase in sales. Data in this evaluation level is gathered by way of operational performance data, perceptual data, or financial reports. Level four evaluation aims to ascertain the impact of an intervention on the bottom-line of an organisation. If the aim of the program is to achieve ‘tangible outcomes’ rather than to make employees/participants get familiar with management concepts, principles, and theories, then it is feasible to evaluate in terms of outputs/results.

7.4. Linking the research questions with the findings

Research Question 1: What are the current practices of training evaluation in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam?

The research has provided a comprehensive picture of training evaluation in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam through three representative companies VARD Vung Tau, Bluescope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam.

Overall findings from the employee survey indicate that the companies have put their efforts in evaluating their trainings however, different evaluation approaches are followed in each manufacturing company depending on the type of training being conducted. **At VARD**, ad-hoc training is not evaluated rather evaluation is done by scheduled training programs. The company does not rely on a single training evaluation, but several evaluation techniques are followed. Managerial responses indicate that evaluation is conducted by circulating survey forms in the form of Happy Sheets to employees who have attended training sessions. Other methods used were observation and interviewing employees implemented in the form of 360 - degree feedback to gain insights into employees’ behaviour and performance after they have attended the training. Managerial responses indicate that the use of Kirkpatrick model and often the use of Phillips model is made to evaluate training, however, the procedure of the use of such frameworks were not disclosed.

At **BlueScope Vietnam**, formal evaluation of the training is carried out for each training program across the different organisational levels. The process of training evaluation is different VARD, as evaluation is conducted before, during, and after the training program using a holistic approach. Before the training, the HRM ensures that the training modules and content are well designed and align with the training requirements of those to be trained. During the training sessions the HR managers as evaluators examine the behaviour of employees going through the training sessions, their level of enthusiasm, participation, and conduct, and presence. After the training program, short tests or surveys are conducted to ask simple questions about the effectiveness of the training undertaken. As regards to the use of evaluation models, this Vietnamese manufacturing company uses the **Kaufman's five level evaluation model** that initially evaluates the availability of training inputs such as such as physical, human, and financial resources, and then 'reaction' that encompasses means, methods, and processes efficiency. This is followed by 'acquisition' to identify the level of individual and group level skills and excellence at work. The model also includes the 'application' stage to measure how far trainees have gained mastery with their work. At the end, the evaluation model involves the evaluation of 'organisational output' as the outcome of output to measure the payoff to the organisation and 'societal outcomes' to assess the scope of payoff to the society. Therefore, training evaluation at BlueScope Vietnam utilise the Kaufman's five level model to evaluate the acceptability and efficiency of the means, methods and processes of the training programs implemented in the organisation. It helps to evaluate training success in terms of the company's overall performance and the return on investment derived as the outcome of the training.

Training evaluation in **Baker Hughes Vietnam** is different to BlueScope Vietnam in the sense that evaluation is carried out in the former company for selected training program and not for short trainings, huddles, or small sessions to give updates on new software, or changed processes. Baker Hughes Vietnam conducted training evaluation for trainings that exceeded at least 40 minutes and were planned ahead of time. The approach to training evaluation is quite

similar to that of VARD which does not evaluate ad-hoc trainings and considers it necessary to evaluate scheduled training programs carried out for an elongated period and formal in nature. As regards to the training evaluation model the HRM at Baker Hughes Vietnam follows a framework that is similar to the Kirkpatrick model and can be used to evaluate any type undertaken in the organisation. It helps the evaluators to understand the reaction of employees being trained and the extent to which they found the training was useful in terms of relevancy, and whether they felt engaged. Evaluation of a training program also includes analysing the behavioural development in the employee after being trained and the extent to which the learning gained in the training could be applied effectively at work. Evaluation in the form of feedback is like a reflection of the training program that helped evaluators to understand whether the employees were able to learn what was supposed to be learnt.

Findings obtained from the survey also reveal that while different training evaluation methods and frameworks are applied, there are apparent gaps in feedback sharing and participation in terms of training evaluation. Some trainings are not evaluated as they are not scheduled trainings so the outcome of these training is not known from the trainees' perspective.

Managers in the interviews also claimed the most effective use of popular evaluation models, failing to address the shortcomings in each of the evaluation frameworks. Moreover, they only focused on the short-term benefits of training evaluation and failed to achieve the long-term benefits.

Research Question 2: What are the strategic training evaluation frameworks, their strengths and limitations?

The research has studied different training evaluation frameworks and pointed out their strengths and limitations.

CIRO model of evaluation proposed by Warr, Bird and Rackham in 1970 focusses on Context, Input, Reaction and Outcome (War *et al.*, 1970). The strength of this CIRO model is that the

objectives and the training equipment are considered; the measurements before and after training are carried out. However, this model does not take behaviours into account, so it is suitable for managerial training programs, rather than those for people at lower levels (Tennant *et al.*, 2002).

CIPP model was developed by Stufflebeam and Shinkfield in 1985. It encompasses four main measurements including Context, Input, Process and Product (Stufflebeam and Shinkfield, 1985). The model can be applied to multiple evaluation situations with its comprehensive approach so it has a long history of applicability. However, the model is said to blur the line between the evaluation and other investigative processes so it gradually lost its wide application in business context.

Kirkpatrick's Model is designed by Kirkpatrick in 1977, which contains four learning outcomes: reaction, learning, behaviour and results. Thanks to its simplicity, flexibility and straightforward approach to training evaluation, this model becomes the most widely studied model in contemporary research and commonly adapted in business context (Elliott *et al.*, 2009). The limitations of this model are the omission of main indicators sufficient guidance on how the four stages can be achieved (Lee and Pershing, 2002); the broken chain-type connection of four stages in practice (Cheng and Hampson, 2008); and lack of consideration on any intervening variables that impact training effectiveness (Cannon Bowers *et al.*, 1995).

Phillips' ROI model introduced this model in 2002 by adding Stage 5- Return on Investment (ROI) to Kirkpatrick's four-stage model (Phillips, 2002). The additional stage makes Kirkpatrick's model more complete by providing an elaborate methodology for estimating financial contributions and returns on programs; providing familiar approach of evaluation to many executives across different departments; and primarily creating training and development interventions (Guerra Lopez, 2008). However, the ROI model is criticised for being time-

consuming and expensive; heavily relying on subjective estimations; not fully addressing all important indicators; and intimidating trainers who are not used to dealing with such formulas.

Research Question 3: How can the strategic training evaluation framework be developed and applied to enhance the long-term benefit of training programmes in the manufacturing sector in Vietnam?

By studying different training evaluation models and their strengths and limitations, the proposed model is basically developed based on the classical four-level model of Kirkpatrick and adjustments suggested by Holton (1995). Since Reaction has been revealed to be of controversial value to indicate the results of training, only the last three levels of Kirkpatrick's model are kept at the core of the proposed model (but Reaction is rearranged and discussed later). The results are evaluated under the influence of the training-related actors, namely trainer, trainee, and organisation. The interactions of these actors start from the beginning of the training cycle and last even after training has been delivered. Therefore, the main training related activities are included in the model, represented by the training cycle and the learning transfer process. All are embedded into a broader environment, where the relevant factors: Socio-cultural, Legal, Economic, Political and Technological (SLEPT – environment analysis model [Pettigrew, 1992]) and specific characteristics of the industry are analysed.

Retaining Kirkpatrick's classical elements (Learning, Behaviour Change, and Results) and with the introduction of intervening factors, the proposed model retains the straightforward nature of Kirkpatrick's work and at the same time is augmented with the power to validate training evaluations. The model incorporates both the pre-training components of the training cycle and post- training learning transfer process so that it offsets the shortcomings of the four-level model in neglecting contextual factors. In the core of the proposed model are the three constructs of the four-level model: learning, behaviour change and organisational results,

reflecting the learning transfer process. The linkages among these three constructs will be examined, but in essence, this examination is conducted with reference to the moderating effects of the context and characteristics of the actors. In the proposed model, three actors involved in pre-training and post-training periods are included: the organisation (the management and internal business environment), the trainee, and the trainer. They are all included inside the recurrent process of training, from needs assessment to training audit.

The modular characteristic of Kirkpatrick's original work is preserved in this new proposed model. Focus can be directed at any level, be it learning, behaviour or result, as long as the appropriate environmental factors are taken into consideration. The model is developed with the intention of embodying the total aspects of training evaluation into a framework. This proposed model provides a general framework for training evaluation. In practice, the evaluation design has to consider the specific evaluation environment, and the availability of various data sources.

7.5. Recommendations

Recommendations for the HRM of the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations mainly emphasise on the full-fledged adoption of Kirkpatrick training evaluation model. This evaluation model was found to be the most holistic, appropriate and relevant to the manufacturing organisations as compared to the other models frequently used by the manufacturing firms being studied. However, adoption of the holistic Kirkpatrick model should be backed with some important aspects that have been identified as evaluation gaps in the findings obtained from surveys and managerial interviews. Therefore, the following are the recommendations to the human resource department, particularly to the training department of VARD Vung Tau Ltd., BlueScope Vietnam, and Baker Hughes Vietnam.

7.5.1. Interactive training sessions

The training for adults requires attention span and hence it is important to engage the participants in training to make it interactive and engaging. The best practices show that there are effective methods to make trainings more goal oriented and managed well to meet the training schedule.

- Introduce and tell the trainees what will be covered in the entire training and for the session scheduled for the day. Ask them to introduce themselves to break the ice.
- The training briefing is done with the main part, key points, and setting the training policies, that the trainees need to know to maintain the decorum.
- The training can also include a summary of what the session will be for and be prepared to show and explain multimedia part to make them understand the significance.
- The training must focus on the 'hands on' as much as it can to use trainees' senses. It helps to create greater impact on the trainees existing knowledge level.
- The post training test is a must for everyone. This will force the trainees to go through the training material even if they had trouble in focussing attention in the training class.
- In the class training session, encourage the students to participate, cite examples, cite any experiences, related to training topic. The interactive session pertaining to the training helps to contribute valuable information to knowledge domain. The training interactivity therefore can be maintained when there are different voices, opinions about issues and discussions which make trainings lively.
- Repeating questions before the trainees answer them and breaking it down into parts for them to answer creates more engagement and interest to brainstorm before answering.

- Analyse the training session before you leave as even in midway; understanding what works best can be deciphered as a new technique to improve training that is unmanageable.
- Tracking the training session by hours with respect to time and pace of lectures is important. Interaction is necessary as the adult human attention span is possible for twenty minutes maximum and hence interactive topic related communication helps. The perception of trainees about trainers to adhere to time-based slots helps in terms of assessment.

7.5.2. Encouraging employee feedback in training evaluation

The feedback forms the essence of a two-way learning assimilation process, where help of assessing the employees creates avenues to focus on the performance. Feedbacks for the employees in training should always be aligned to improve their individual performance. The open organisation often offers employees to provide insights for improving business, training process which increases their level of involvement to the task. Therefore, for providing feedback to the individual or group, is a question that needs consideration as most of it is dependent on the time factor. The method of providing feedback process (formal or informal) also depends on the feedback style, organisational culture. The feedback however, requires a commitment from the management to be open and continuous for the employees to improve on the job. Training evaluation is one of the key stages in which the employee learnings is tested and analysed at one to one or at group-based setting. The training feedback generally clears the concepts that has been wrongly misinterpreted as feedback can be on training progress, retraining, development or some cases (disciplinary action). The time being a limitation the objective approach should try to focus on the trainee non-performing areas in areas of physical exercise, written assignment. Hence issues of trainer rate bias about trainee feelings, openness, flexibility is some of the issues, that should be a part of the evaluation

process consideration set. The most structural approach to conduct is to observe the performance and link the job description, employee performance to understand expected outcomes requires to create a system. Therefore, ask the employee, observe performance, and is most common trends. As it helps to understand knowledge level and competencies being embedded requiring the re-training orders. The feedback analysis is also required to understand the employee reaction to the inputs given through training. The feedback is also effective listening, feedback can motivate to the receiver (who receives it). The motivation levels have been found to improve, while it does improve performance.

7.5.3. Participatory approach to training evaluation

This has been chosen as it opposes the autocratic methods of training. The use of participatory approaches is a method that contains essentially all ingredients where the quality of teaching is supported to be more engaging and interactive. Though it depends on the organisational culture, the requirement of local language translator, in case of MNC is needed. The trainer needs to inform new modules, upgrade, that help aids in structural improvements leading the training addressing the issues and problems readily. The method is different as it is not top down approach and focuses on the restructuring the exiting training process to focus on meeting trainee's concepts in the classroom. There are instances of cooperative learning in training which changes the training towards workshops which is able to build greater level of skill in employees.

7.6. Contribution of the study

The main contribution of this research is to unearth the nature of training evaluation followed by manufacturing firms in Vietnam, its benefits and advantages, gaps and challenges involved. While a range of training evaluation frameworks are adopted by the manufacturing organisations in Vietnam including the use of evaluation models and approaches discussed in

the literature review, the HR managers are not able to leverage the full potential of any of the frameworks. Considering the situation of the Vietnamese manufacturing context, and the identified gaps in existing evaluation frameworks, the Kirkpatrick model is proposed with certain customisation to make its adoption and use simpler and more feasible. Therefore, the practical contribution of this research towards the manufacturing industry is the adaptation of the Kirkpatrick framework of training evaluation by HR managers/trainers who should follow a participatory leadership approach.

The importance of proposed training evaluation framework in Vietnamese manufacturing sector

The proposed training evaluation framework is crucial for the Vietnamese manufacturing sector as it a simplified version of the Kirkpatrick model, easy to implement and follow, and likely to eliminate the loopholes present in the existing frameworks used by these companies. The HR managers of the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations valued the Kirkpatrick framework, however, insisted on simplifying the framework in a manner that is more practical and feasible.

The Kirkpatrick Training Evaluation approach is a holistic framework and therefore involves certain complexities that need to be simplified. Moreover, certain criticism against the practical adoption and execution of the model exists in practical terms and therefore need to be highlighted. As hinted by the one of the managers of a Vietnamese manufacturing firm, there exists low correlation between each of the four levels include in the Kirkpatrick model. Users of this model often find it difficult to integrate or coordinate the different levels, therefore, HR managers/training evaluators need to set specific questions for each level, and predetermine what could be the practicability and relevance. This can be diagrammatically presented using tabular format to make it easier for HR managers/trainers to follow step by step in a systematic manner.

Also, manufacturing organisations that already use this model complain that it shows different effects of training at different levels. Before discussing the adoption of the Kirkpatrick model, it is essential to understand the problems in evaluation. The first challenge is lack of goal congruence, i.e. the difference in perception about the training objectives which usually have low clarity in specific training objectives. Trainers often use their past experiences, and some follow intuitive feeling about the training course rather than utilising a scientific method of feedback to improve the upcoming programs. Often HR managers do not set explicit goals and objectives for training but remain undecided and vague. Often senior and/or experienced employees may consider themselves to be in a superior role of being an appraiser.

Simplified version of the proposed training evaluation framework

The following table provides a simplified version of the proposed training evaluation framework for the Vietnamese manufacturing firms.

Level and type of evaluation	Description of Evaluation and characteristics	Use of tools and methods of evaluation in manufacturing organisations	Practicability
Reaction	<p>This level relates to how the trainees felt after attending the training, their personal response to training and/or learning experience.</p> <p>Vietnamese manufacturing organisations (HR managers) should seek answers to the following questions -</p> <p><i>Did the trainees like the program delivery?</i></p> <p><i>Was it worth the time invested?</i></p>	<p>Use of simple ‘HAPPY SHEETS’ can be made</p> <p>Primary research – survey forms/questionnaires (online/offline)</p> <p>Online assessment</p>	<p>This exercise can be conducted immediately after training</p> <p>Helps to obtain feedback about how the trainees react post training</p>

	<p><i>Did the trainees get fully acquainted with the 'ins' and 'outs' / key aspects of production and manufacturing?</i></p> <p><i>Were the trainees able to clarify their doubts?</i></p>		
Learning	<p>Manufacturing organisations should understand that that learning evaluation measures the increase in knowledge/intellectual capabilities from previous to after the learning experience –</p> <p>HR managers should ask the following questions –</p> <p>Did the trainees learn what they were supposed to learn?</p> <p>Did they experience what was intended for them to experience?</p> <p>What is the level of progress or advancement in trainees post training session?</p>	<p>The use of tests/assessments pre and post training</p> <p>Observation or interview may be used pre and post training, even if this may be time consuming</p> <p>Assessment method must be inherently related to the 'learning aims and objectives'.</p>	<p>Feasible and relevant for certain quantifiable trainings/technical skills</p>

Behaviour	<p>This relates to the level to which trainees have applied their learning and transformed their behaviour. This can be evident soon after training or several months post training based on situation.</p> <p>Did the trainees implement their learning into their daily work?</p> <p>Were there perceptible changes in the activities and/or performances of the employees?</p> <p>Were the trainees able to transfer their learning to others?</p> <p>Were they aware of the changes their behaviour and knowledge level after training?</p>	<p>Interview and/or observation over time may be carried out to evaluate change and its relevance</p> <p>Assessments need to be fine-tuned, and continuous, and then transferred to an appropriate analysis tool</p> <p>The design of the assessment should be based on relevant performance standards</p> <p>Self- assessment can be carried out</p>	<p>Measuring behavioural change may be difficult to quantify and interpret as compared to the other levels</p> <p>Line managers and trainees should be involved and offer support to evaluate behaviour change, and therefore must be involved from the beginning</p>
Results	<p>This evaluation is the effect on business or context resulting from enhanced performances of the trainees (acid test)</p> <p>Key performance indicators (KPIs) are the measures such as volume of production, return on investment, percentages, and other elements of organisational performance such as quality ratings, non-compliance, number of customer complaints, turnover and retention (***)</p>	<p>It is likely that most of the measures (***) are already present through usual management systems and reporting</p> <p>Challenge may arise while identifying which measures relate to the input of trainees. Hence it is necessary to recognise relevance with the trainees at the beginning of the training session so that they comprehend what is supposed to be measured.</p>	<p>Evaluation at this level is not particularly complex, across the entire organisation where it becomes very challenging.</p>

Limitations of Study

The limitations of the research are that it is cross sectional in nature and not longitudinal. This is academic research and the limited companies chosen only from one sector of Vietnam limits the research in understanding the training evaluation philosophy, concept and framework. The respondent having difficulty in understanding the meaning and concept of the training evaluation can affect the research outcomes. The quality of responses once affected would dilute the research purpose and the outcomes in the end which is a limitation.

It affects the data collection strategy, the strategy to reach out to the respondent groups, briefing them to get the responses. This whole process is important for the qualitative data procurement as failing to meet the sampling strategy numbers is falling short of the target of data collection. The last issue is about the respondent not able to relate the research questions and the disclosure of the information about the company internal data.

7.7. Scope for future research

The presence of inherent limitations in this study and areas not covered in this research leave scope for future researchers to fulfil the areas. The current research was an inductive study meant to analyse the effectiveness of training evaluation and design a strategic evaluation framework for the Vietnamese manufacturing organisations. Future scholars can use the findings of this research as a secondary resource to build up their own studies in the area of training evaluation and relate this aspect with another dependent variable such as employee satisfaction, retention, or organisational performance. Therefore, future scope lies in analysing the effectiveness of Kirkpatrick evaluation model in key areas such as employee satisfaction or organisational performance.

Training in the workplace is important as it benefits both the organization and the employee when training is conducted properly. It is apparent that training does not simply refer to conducting classroom sessions. Indeed, training process should be considered as a cyclical process (Bee and Bee, 1994) with distinct stages. Training evaluation, the final step in the training process, is critical to an organization because it ascertains the effectiveness of training programs and provides indicators for further development. The models/frameworks of training evaluation are numerous. In the limitation of this research, four significant models are examined, namely CIRO framework, CIPP model, Kirkpatrick's four stage model, and Phillips's ROI model. Based on the comparison of these models, Kirkpatrick's model is chosen to be the fundamental one for this research due to its simplicity and flexible.

In Vietnam, one of South East Asia's fastest-growing economies, the awareness of training evaluation still remains limited in both academic and business context (Zhu, 2002). In manufacturing sector- the dominant player in the country's economy also suffers from the same situation. Training evaluation in manufacturing organizations does not receive adequate awareness and support. Inadequate planning, lack of objectivity, improper interpretation and inappropriate use of results, lack of training expertise are some main challenges facing evaluation process. Therefore, this research is necessary as it not only raises awareness of training evaluation in work place, but also provides the strategic framework for practical application in the context of manufacturing organizations in Vietnam.

The research will be carried out in Vietnam – one of the fastest growing economies in South East Asia. The focus is placed on manufacturing sector as it is the dominant player in Vietnam economy and accounts for the largest portion in attracting FDI. Five particular organizations operating in different industries within manufacturing sector will be a sample of this thesis and be carefully selected. At this time, two organizations are successfully contacted, and they are willing to support this research to its final phase. They are VARD Vung Tau Ltd. – ship

building company and BlueScope Vietnam-the country's leading manufacturer of coated and pre-painted products for the construction market. The other three organizations will be confirmed in the next research stage.

The inductive approach is employed in this research as it is believed to provide the inspiring environment to nurture the further ideas of research topic. The mixed data collection methods are chosen in collecting data, namely observation, questionnaire, semi-structured group interviews and in-depth interview. They are ideal for this research as they together generate the most accurate and comprehensive quantitative and qualitative data. There are some significant access and ethics issues rising when conducting this research. They should be seriously taken into consideration to achieve a successful and ethical research.

With the effort of the researcher and support from her assigned supervisor as well as people involved in the research, this research is believed to benefit both academic researchers and business practitioners who are concerned about training evaluation and human resources management in Vietnam, and other Asia countries sharing the same situation.

REFERENCES

Aguinis, H. and Kraiger, K., 2009. Benefits of training and development for individuals and teams, organizations, and society. *Annual review of psychology*. Vol.60, pp.451-474.

Albrecht, S. L., Bakker, A. B., Gruman, J. A., Macey, W. H. and Saks, A.M. (2015) Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage: An integrated approach. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*. Vol.2, No.1, pp.7–35.

Alyahya, M. S. (2013) Evaluation of effectiveness of training and development: The Kirkpatrick Model. *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*. Vol. 2, No. 11, pp.14-24.

Arnett, R., Johnson, J. and Teasdale, K., (2013) *Training needs analysis.*, Available at: [https://www.lga.sa.gov.au/webdata/resources/files/Training_Needs_Analysis_\(TNA\)_Guide_-_May_2013.pdf](https://www.lga.sa.gov.au/webdata/resources/files/Training_Needs_Analysis_(TNA)_Guide_-_May_2013.pdf).

Arthur, W., Jr., Bennett, W., Jr., Edens, P. S., & Bell, S. T. (2003). Effectiveness of training in organizations: A meta-analysis of design and evaluation features. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. Vol.88, No.2, pp 234–245.

Arunkumar, S. and Parimala, S. (2012) Effectiveness of employee cross training on employee retention. *Life Science Journal*. Vol.9, No.4, pp.649–652.

Arunprasad, P., 2017. Inevitable knowledge strategy: A paradigm shift in strategic HRM practices to augment firm's performance. *Employee Relations*. Vol.39, No.5, pp.753–774.

Arvanitis, S., Seliger, F. and Stucki, T. (2016) The relative importance of human resource management practices for innovation. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*. Vol.25, No.8, pp.769–800.

Aslan Sendogdu, A.K.S.G. (2013) The relationship between human resource management practices and organizational commitment: A field study. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*. Vol.99, pp.818–827.

Bardoel, E.A., Pettit, T.M., De Cieri, H. and McMillan, L. (2014) Employee resilience: an emerging challenge for HRM. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*. Vol.52, No.3, pp.279-297.

Barnes, D.E., Yaffe, K., Belfor, N., Jagust, W.J., DeCarli, C., Reed, B.R. and Kramer, J.H. (2009) Computer-based cognitive training for mild cognitive impairment: results from a pilot randomized, controlled trial. *Alzheimer disease and associated disorders*. Vol.23, No.3, p.205.

Bates, R. (2004) A critical analysis of evaluation practice: the Kirkpatrick model and the principle of beneficence. *Evaluation and Program Planning*. Vol.27, pp. 341–347.

Bbc.co.uk. (2014). *BBC - GCSE Bitesize: Computer-aided design (CAD)*. [online] Available at: <http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/design/systemscontrol/ictinindustryrev2.shtml> [Accessed 8 Feb. 2018].

Bbc.co.uk. (2014). *BBC - GCSE Bitesize: Computer-aided manufacture*. [online] Available at:http://www.bbc.co.uk/schools/gcsebitesize/design/electronics/manufacturing_processesrev2.shtml [Accessed 8 Feb. 2018].

Beamond, M.T., Farndale, E. and Härtel, C.E. (2016) MNE translation of corporate talent management strategies to subsidiaries in emerging economies. *Journal of World Business*. Vol.51, No.4, pp.499-510.

Beardwell, I. H. (2004) *Human Resources Management a contemporary Approach*. 4th ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall.

Bedwell, W.L. and Salas, E. (2010) Computer-based training: capitalizing on lessons learned. *International Journal of Training and Development*. Vol.14, No.3, pp.239-249

Bee, F. and Bee, R. (1994) *Training needs analysis and evaluation*. 1st ed. London: CIPD.

Blake, R. (1989) Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Methods in Family Research. *Families Systems and Health*. Vol. 7, pp.411–427.

BlueScope Vietnam website [online] Available at: <https://www.bluescope.com/about-us/where-we-are/vietnam/> [Accessed on 10 April 2018].

Borate, N.S.; Gopalkrishna; Shiva, P.H.C. and Borate, S.L. (2014) A Case Study Approach for Evaluation of Employee Training Effectiveness and Development Program. *The International Journal of Business and Management*. Vol.2, No.6, pp.201-211.

Bowes, B. (2008) Employees Development Programs Help Companies Achieve Greater Success. *CMA Management*, pp.13-14.

Bramley, P. and Kitson, B. (1994) Evaluating Training against Business Criteria. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol.18, No.1, pp.10-14.

Bransford, J.D., Franks, J.J., Morris, C.D. and Stein, B.S. (2014) Some general constraints on learning and memory research. *Levels of Processing in Human Memory*, pp.331-354.

Brightwell, A. and Grant, J. (2013) Competency-based training: Who benefits? *Postgraduate Medical Journal*. Vol.89, No.1048, pp.107–110.

Brinkerhoff, R.O. (2006) Increasing impact of training investments: An evaluation strategy for building organizational capability. *Industrial and Commercial Training*. Vol.38, No.6, pp.302-307.

Broad, M and Newstrom, J. (1992) *Transfer of training: Action-packed strategies to ensure high payoff from training investments*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.

Brown, J.D., 2011. Likert items and scales of measurement. *Statistics*, 15(1), pp.10-14.

Albrecht, Simon L., Bakker, Arnold B., Gruman, Jamie A., Macey, William H. and Saks, Alan M. (2015) Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage. *Journal of organizational effectiveness*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 7-35.

Budhwar, P.S. and Debrah, Y.A. eds. (2013) *Human resource management in developing countries*. Routledge.

Buller, P.F. and McEvoy, G.M. (2012) Strategy, human resource management and performance: Sharpening line of sight. *Human resource management review*. Vol.22, No.1, pp.43-56.

Bulut, C. and Culha, O. (2010) The effects of organizational training on organizational commitment. *International Journal of Training and Development*. Vol. 14, No.4, pp.309-322.

Burgess, J. and Connell, J. (2008) Introduction to special issue: HRM and job quality: An Overview. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*. Vol.19, No.3, pp.407–418.

Business Development Group (2016) Vietnam's thriving manufacturing sector, strategic advantages and free trade. [online]. Available at: <http://bdg-vietnam.com/en/about/news/details/items/vietnams-thriving-manufacturing-sector-strategic-advantages/> [Accessed on 10 April 2017]

Byars, L.L., Rue, L.W. and Dias, L. (2011) Human Resource Management. *In Development and management of visitor attractions*, p.414. Available at: <file:///D:/Users/dell-pc/Desktop/Human Resource Management.pdf>

Carretero-Gomez, J.M. and Cabrera, E.F. (2012) An Empirical Evaluation of Training Using Multi-Attribute Utility Analysis. *Journal of Business and Psychology*. Vol. 27, pp.223–241.

Cassavaugh, N.D. and Kramer, A.F. (2009) Transfer of computer-based training to simulated driving in older adults. *Applied ergonomics*. Vol.40, No.5, pp.943-952.

Cheng, E.W. K. and Ho, D.C.K. (2001) Research Note: A review of transfer of training studies in the past decade. *Personnel Review*. Vol.30, No.1, pp. 102-118.

Chiaburu, D.S. and Tekleab, A.G. (2005) Individual and contextual influences on multiple dimensions of training effectiveness. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol. 29, No. 8, pp. 604-26.

Chowhan, J. (2016) Unpacking the black box: Understanding the relationship between strategy, HRM practices, innovation and organizational performance. *Human Resource Management Journal*. Vol.26, No.2, pp.112-133.

Dang, T.L.; Le, D.P and Hoang, V.H. (2010) Vietnam's Economy after 20 years of renewal (1986-2006): Achievements and Challenges. Hanoi.

Daniels, S. (2003) Employee training: a strategic approach to better return on investment. *Journal of Business Strategy*. Vol. 24, No.5, pp.39-42.

Dar, A.T.; Bashir, M.; Ghazanfar, F. and Abrar, M. (2014) Mediating Role of Employee Motivation in Relationship to Post-Selection HRM Practices and Organizational Performance. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. Vol.4, No.3, pp.224–238. Available at: <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1550960873?accountid=45394>

Dawson, R. (1995) Fill this in before you go: under-utilised evaluation sheets. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol.19, No.2, pp.3-7.

Delery, J.E. and Gupta, N. (2015) People and Performance. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness*. Vol. 2, No. 3, pp.244– 266.

Dent, F. and Holton, V., (2009) Employee engagement and motivation. *Training Journal*, (November), pp.37–40. Available at: <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bthandAN=45033309&site=ehost-live>

Dickes, D. (2014) Research consistently shows that training employees pays off with profits. [online] Available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/20140731043559-8175758-research-consistently-shows-that-training-employees-pays-off-with-profits> [Accessed on 3 Apr 2017]

Diez, J.R. (2016) Vietnam 30 years after Doi Moi: achievements and challenges. *The German Journal of Economic Geography*. Vol.60, No.3, pp.121-133.

Dysvik, A. and Kuvaas, B. (2008) The relationship between perceived training opportunities, work motivation and employee outcomes. *International Journal of Training and Development*. Vol.12, No.3, pp.138-157.

Eisele, L., Grohnert, T., Beusaert, S. (2013) Employee motivation for personal development plan effectiveness. *European Journal of Training and Development*. Vol. 37, No.6, pp.527–543.

Elliott, M., Dawson, R. and Edwards, J. (2009) Providing demonstrable return-on-investment for organisational learning and training. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol.33, No.7, pp.657-670.

Ertemsir, E. and Bal, Y. (2012) An interactive method for hr training: Managers as simulation players. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, pp. 870–874.

Falola, H.O., Osibanjo, A.O. and Ojo, S.I. (2014) Effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organization competitiveness in the Nigerian Banking industry. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V*. Vol.7, No.1, p.161.

Fazey, I., Bunse, L., Msika, J., Pinke, M., Preedy, K., Evely, A.C., Lambert, E., Hastings, E., Morris, S. and Reed, M.S. (2014) Evaluating knowledge exchange in interdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder research. *Global Environmental Change*. Vol. 25, No.3, pp.204-220.

Flippo, E.B. (1984) *Personnel Management*, New York: McGraw-Hill, 6th Edition.

Fraser, K., Ma, I., Teteris, E., Baxter, H., Wright, B. and McLaughlin, K. (2012) Emotion, cognitive load and learning outcomes during simulation training. *Medical education*. Vol. 46, No.11, pp.1055-1062.

Garavan, T.N. (1997) Training, development, education and learning: different or the same. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol. 21, No.2, pp.39-50.

Gelens, J., Hofmans, J., Dries, N. and Pepermans, R. (2014) Talent management and organisational justice: Employee reactions to high potential identification. *Human Resource Management Journal*. Vol. 24, No.2, pp.159-175.

Georgiadis, A. and Pitelis, C.N. (2016) The Impact of Employees' and Managers' Training on the Performance of Small-and Medium-Sized Enterprises: Evidence from a Randomized Natural Experiment in the UK Service Sector. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*. Vol.54, No.2, pp.409-421.

Ghebregiorgis, F. and Karsten, L. (2012) Human resource management practices in Eritrea: challenges and prospects. *Employee Relations*. Vol.28, No.2, pp.144–163. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01425450610639374>

Ghufli, A.L.I. (2012) Training Needs Analysis. *Brunel Business School - Doctoral Symposium*, (March), pp.1–11.

Goldestein, I. L. and Ford, J.K. (2002) *Training in organization: Need Assessment Development and Evaluation*. 4th, Ed. Belmont: Wardsworth.

Goldstein, I.L. (1993) *Training in Organizations*, Brooks Cole, Pacific Grove, CA.

Goldstein, I.L. and Ford, J.K. (2002) *Training in Organizations: Need Assessment, Development, and Evaluation*. 4th Ed. Wadsworth.

Guerra-Lopez, I.J. (2008) *Performance Evaluation: Proven Approaches for Improving Program and organizational performance*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass

Guest, D.E. (2011) Human resource management and performance: still searching for some answers. *Human resource management journal*. Vol.21, No.1, pp.3-13.

Guzzo, R.A.; Jette, R.D. and Katzell, R.A. (1985) The effects of psychologically based intervention programs on worker productivity: a meta-analysis. *Personnel Psychology*. Vol. 38, No.3, pp. 275-91.

Hayton, B. (2010) Vietnam: Rising Dragon. *Yale University Press*.

Hoffmann, K. (2014) Measuring HRM Effectiveness as a Challenge to Contemporary HRM Scientists (HRM Context). *Kwartalnik Ekonomistów i Menedżerów*. Vol.33, No.3, pp.7–24.

Holbeche, L., 2011. HR Leadership. *Human Resource Management International Digest*. Vol. 19, No.2, pp.364–369.

Holman, D., Totterdell, P., Axtell, C., Stride, C., Port, R., Svensson, R. and Zibarras, L. (2012) Job design and the employee innovation process: The mediating role of learning strategies. *Journal of Business and Psychology*. Vol.27, No. 2, pp.177-191.

Hong, E.N.C., Hao, L.Z., Kumar, R., Ramendran, C. and Kadiresan, V. (2012) An effectiveness of human resource management practices on employee retention in institute of higher learning: A regression analysis. *International journal of business research and management*. Vol.3, No.2, pp.60-79.

Hurn, B.J. (2014) The challenges facing international HRM in an increasingly globalised environment. *Industrial and Commercial Training*. Vol.46, No.7, pp.371–378.

Indiacadworks.com. (2014). *Advantages of Computer Aided Design*. [online] Available at: <https://www.indiacadworks.com/blog/advantages-of-computer-aided-design/> [Accessed 8 Feb. 2018].

Ishaq, H.M. and Mumtaz, T. (2014) Impact of employee behaviour and organizational support in training transfer process. *Management, Knowledge and Learning Journal*. Vol.23, pp. 545–551.

Iyer, R. Pardiwalla, P. and Bathia, J. (2009) Training Evaluation Practices in Indian Organizations. *Human Resource Development News Letter*. Vol.25, No.8, pp. 35-37.

James, C. and Roffe, I. (2000) The evaluation of goal and goal-free training innovation. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol. 24, No.1, pp.12-20.

James, C. and Roffe, I. (2000) The evaluation of goal and goal-free training innovation. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol. 24, No.1, pp.12-20.

Jehanzeb, K. and Bashir, N.A. (2013) Training and Development Program and its Benefits to Employee and Organization: A Conceptual Study. *European Journal of Business and Management*. Vol.5, No.2, pp.243-252.

Jerome, N. (2013) Application of the Maslow's hierarchy of need theory; impacts and implications on organizational culture, human resource and employee's performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*. Vol.2, No.3, pp.39-45.

Jusoh, R., Ziyae, B., Asimiran, S. and Kadir, S.A. (2011) Entrepreneur training needs analysis: Implications on the entrepreneurial skills needed for successful entrepreneurs. *The International Business and Economics Research Journal*. Vol.10, No.1, pp.143-148.

Kamoche, K. (2001) Human Resources in Vietnam: The global challenges. *International Business Review*. Vol. 43, No. 5, pp.625-650.

Kasemsap, K. (2016) Promoting leadership development and talent management in modern organizations. *Project Management: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications*, p.178.

Khan, M.I. (2012) The Impact of Training and Motivation on Performance of Employees. *Business review*. Vol.7, No.2, pp.84–96.

Kim, B. (2006) Managing workforce diversity: Developing a learning organization. *Human Resources in Hospitality and Tourism*. Vol. 5, No.2, pp. 69-90.

Kirkpatrick, D.L. (1977) Evaluating training programs: Evidence vs proof. *Training and Development Journal*. Vol.16, pp.9-12.

Kirkpatrick, D.L. (1998) *Evaluating Training Programs: The Four Levels*. 2nd ed. Berrett-Koehler Publishers, San Francisco, CA.

Kontoghiorghes, C. (2016) Linking high performance organizational culture and talent management: satisfaction/motivation and organizational commitment as mediators. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. Vol.27, No.16, pp.1833-1853.

Krieger, N. (2012) Who and What Is a “Population”? Historical Debates, Current Controversies, and Implications for Understanding “Population Health” and Rectifying Health Inequities. *The Milbank Quarterly*. Vol.90, No.4, pp 634–681.

Kumpikaitė, V., (2007) Human Resource Training Evaluation. *Žmonių Ištekliai Mokymo Vertinimas*. Vol.55, No.5, pp.29–36. Available at: <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bth&andAN=28523397&andsite=ehost-live>

Lazazzara, A. and Bombelli, M.C. (2011) HRM practices for an ageing Italian workforce: The role of training. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol.35, No.8, pp.808–825.

Lee, S.H. and Pershing, J.A. (2002) Dimensions and design criteria for developing training reaction evaluations. *Human Resource Development International*. Vol.5, No.2, pp.175-197.

Lodico, M.G., Spaulding, D.T and Voegtle, K.H. (2010) *Methods in Educational Research: From Theory to Practice*. John Wiley and Sons, p.10.

Martinez, V., Bastl, M., Kingston, J. and Evans, S. (2010) Challenges in transforming manufacturing organisations into product-service providers. *Journal of manufacturing technology management*. Vol.21, No.4, pp.449-469.

McDermott, R. (2017) *What computer- based training can and can't do for your company*. [online] Qualitydigest.com. Available at: <https://www.qualitydigest.com/aug01/html/cbt.html> [Accessed 8 Feb. 2018].

McNulty, Y. and De Cieri, H. (2016) Linking global mobility and global talent management: The role of ROI. *Employee Relations*. Vol.38, No.1, pp.8-30.

Memon, M.A., Salleh, R. and Baharom, M.N.R. (2016) The link between training satisfaction, work engagement and turnover intention. *European Journal of Training and Development*. Vol.40, No.6, pp.407-429.

Nagar, V. (2009) Measuring Training Effectiveness. *The Indian Journal of Commerce*. Vol. 62, No.4, pp. 86-90.

Nestojko, J.F., Bui, D.C., Kornell, N. and Bjork, E.L. (2014) Expecting to teach enhances learning and organization of knowledge in free recall of text passages. *Memory and cognition*. Vol.42, No.7, pp.1038-104

Nguyen, T.N., Truong, Q. and Buyens, D. (2011) Training and firm performance in economies in transition: A comparison between Vietnam and China. *Asia Pacific Business Review*. Vol. 17, No.1, pp.103-119.

Nidhra, S., Yanamadala, M., Afzal, W. and Torkar, R. (2013) Knowledge transfer challenges and mitigation strategies in global software development—A systematic literature review and industrial validation. *International journal of information management*. Vol.33, No.2, pp.333-355.

Niehaus, J. and Riedl, M.O. (2009) Scenario adaptation: An approach to customizing computer-based training games and simulations. *Proceedings of the AIED 2009 Workshop on Intelligent Educational Games*. Vol. 3, No.1, pp. 89-98.

Obeng, E. (2014) Human Resource Management: Gaining a Competitive Advantage. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, pp.197–207.

Parmenter, C.L. (2012) *Motivation and learning strategies: A correlational study of employee training*.

Parry, E. (2011) An examination of e-HRM as a means to increase the value of the HR function. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*. Vol.22, No.5, pp.1146–1162.

Peretz, C., Korczyn, A.D., Shatil, E., Aharonson, V., Birnboim, S. and Giladi, N. (2011) Computer-based, personalized cognitive training versus classical computer games: a randomized double-blind prospective trial of cognitive stimulation. *Neuroepidemiology*. Vol.36, No.2, pp.91-99.

Phan, A.C., Nguyen, M.H., Luong, H.V.M. and Matsui, Y. (2016) ISO 9000 implementation and performance: empirical evidence from Vietnamese companies. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*. Vol.18, No.1, pp.53-77.

Phillips, J.; Stone, R.D.; Phillips, P.P. (2001) *The Human Resources Scorecard: Measuring the Return on Investment*. Woburn: Butterworth-Heinemann.

Pineda, P. (2010) Evaluation of training in organisations: a proposal for an integrated model. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. Vol. 34, No.7, pp. 673-693.

Porter, C. and Spear, B. (2010) Strategic Human Resource Management. *Human Resource Management Review*. Vol. 14, No.2, pp.365–382.

Poston, B. (2009) Maslow's hierarchy of needs. *The Surgical Technologist*. Vol.41, No.8, pp.347-353.

Prasad, C. V. (2015) Emerging trends in HRM. *International Journal of Economic Research*. Vol.12, No.2, pp.511–517. Available at: <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-84937717195&partnerID=40&md5=eae96e0946bae58dee451bdf8882d23>

Preskill, H. and Russ-Eft, D. (2005) *Building Evaluation Capacity: 72 Activities for Teaching and Training*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.

Principles of community engagement (2011) 2nd ed. National Institutes of Health; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, pp.163-179.

Qadeer, F., Shafique, M. and Rehman, R. (2011) An overview of HR-line relationship and its future directions. *African Journal of Business Management*. Vol.5, No.7, pp.2512–2523.

Raab, R.T; Swanson, B.E; Wentling, T.L., and Dark, C.D. (1991) *A trainer's guide to evaluation*. Rome: FAO.

Reay, D. G. (1994) *Evaluating training*. 1st ed. London: Kogan Page.

Reed Learning. Popular Learning Evaluation Models [online] Available at: <https://magic.piktochart.com/embed/1993702-evaluation-models> [Accessed on 9 April 2017]

Rossmann, G., and B. Wilson (1991) Numbers and Words Revisited: Being “Shamelessly Eclectic.” *Evaluation Review*. Vol. 9, No.5, pp. 627–643.

Roughton, J. and Crutchfield, N. (2016) Assessing Training needs. *Job Hazard Analysis*, pp.299–334.

Ruthtrumpold.id.au. (2017) *Computer Integrated Manufacturing Design Technology*. [online] Available at: http://www.ruthtrumpold.id.au/destech/?page_id=150 [Accessed 7 Feb. 2018].

Ryan, V. (2008) *Computer Integrated Manufacture*. [online] Technologystudent.com. Available at: <http://www.technologystudent.com/rmprp07/intman1.html> [Accessed 6 Feb. 2018].

Saad, A.M. and Mat, N.B. (2011) Evaluation of Effectiveness of Training and Development: The Kirkpatrick Model. *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*. Vol. 2, No. 11 pp.14-24.

Sadri, G. and Bowen, C.R. (2011) Meeting employee requirements: Maslow's hierarchy of needs is still a reliable guide to motivating staff. *Industrial engineer*. Vol.43, No.10, pp.44-49.

Saks, A.M. and Belcourt, M. (2006) An investigation of training activities and transfer of training in organizations. *Human Resource Management*. Vol.45, No.4, pp.629–648.

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2007) *Research Methods for Business Students*. England: Pearson Education Limited.

Scheer, A.W., 2012. *CIM Computer Integrated Manufacturing: Towards the Factory of the Future*. Springer Science and Business Media.

Shahrooz, F. (2012) The evaluation of effectiveness of training courses in University by Kirkpatrick model. *Social and Behavioural Science*. Vol. 46, pp. 2837-2841.

Shahzadi, I.; Javed, A., Pirzada, S.S, Nasreen, A and Khanam, F. (2014) Impact of Employee Motivation on Employee Performance. *European Journal of Business and Management Online*. Vol.6, No.23, pp.2222–2839.

Sim, R. (1993) Evaluating Public Sector Training Programs. *Public Personnel Management*. Vol.22, No.8, pp. 35 – 37.

Simon L. A., Bakker, A. B., Gruman, J. A., Macey, W. H. and Saks, A. M. (2015) Employee Engagement, Human Resource Management Practices and Competitive Advantage: An Integrated Approach. *Journal of Organisational Effectiveness*. Vol.2, No.1, pp.7–35. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JOEPP-08-2014-0042>

Smale, A., Bjorkman, I. and Sumelius, J. (2013) Examining the differential use of global integration mechanisms across HRM practices: Evidence from China. *Journal of World Business*. Vol.48, No.2, pp.232–240. Available at:http://ac.els-cdn.com/S1090951612000600/1-s2.0-S1090951612000600-main.pdf?_tid=0905d4dc-afe1-11e4-afa2-00000aacb35f&adcdnat=1423434358_b38a2217ed6aa7df1eb16881d313fbde

Snape, E. and Redman, T. (2010) HRM practices, organizational citizenship behaviour, and performance: A multi-level analysis. *Journal of Management Studies*. Vol.47, No.7, pp.1219-1247.

Sphhp.buffalo.edu. (2018). *Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) - Center on Knowledge Translation for Technology Transfer - University at Buffalo*. [online] Available at: <https://sphhp.buffalo.edu/cat/kt4tt/best-practices/need-to-knowledge-ntk-model/ntk-commercial-devices/master-list-of-tools/mechanical-engineering-/computer-integrated-manufacturing--cim--.html> [Accessed 6 Feb. 2018]

Srivastava, E. and Agarwal, N. (2012) The Emerging Challenges in HRM. *International journal of scientific and technology research*. Vol.1, No.6, pp.46–48.

Steensma, H. and Groneveld, K. (2010) Evaluating a training using the “four levels model”. *Journal of Workplace Learning*. Vol.22, No.5, pp. 319-331.

Stake, R. E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Stewart, J. (1999) *Employee Development Practice*. 1st ed. London: Pitman Publishing.

Stufflebeam, D. L. and Shinkfield, A.J. (1985) *Systematic evaluation: A self-instructional guide to theory and practice*. Boston: Kluwer-Nijhoff.

Sundarajan, S. (2007) Employees’ attitude towards training and development in private sector industries. *Indian Journal of Training and Development*, Vol. 37, No. 3, pp. 45-50.

Suresh, K.P and Chandrashekar, S. (2012) Sample size estimation and power analysis for clinical research studies. *Journal of Human Reproductive Sciences*. Vol. 5, No.1, pp 7-13.

Tangthong, S., Trimetsoontorn, J. andRojniruntikul, N., 2014. HRM Practices and Employee Retention in Thailand—A Literature Review. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and*

Finance. Vol.5, No.2, pp.162–166. Available at:

<http://www.ijtef.org/index.php?m=contentandc=indexanda=showandcatid=50andid=659>

Tatoglu, E., Glaister, A.J. and Demirbag, M. (2016) Talent management motives and practices in an emerging market: A comparison between MNEs and local firms. *Journal of World Business*. Vol.51, No.2, pp.278-293.

Taylor, T. (2016) *The Costs of Training New Employees, Including Hidden Expenses*. [online] Adp.com. Available at: <https://www.adp.com/thrive/articles/2016/01/the-costs-of-training-new-employees-including-hidden-expenses.aspx#> [Accessed 4 May 2018].

Thakore, D. (2013) Training - A Strategic HRM Function. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*. Vol.11, pp.84–90. Available at: <http://www.scipress.com/ILSHS.11.84>

Thibodeaux, W. (2017). *The Disadvantages of Computer Aided Manufacturing* | *Techwalla.com*. [online] Techwalla. Available at: <https://www.techwalla.com/articles/the-disadvantages-of-computer-aided-manufacturing> [Accessed 8 Feb. 2018].

Topno, H. (2012) Evaluation of Training and Development: An Analysis of Various Models. *Journal of Business and Management*. Vol.5, No.2, pp. 16-22.

Training Industry. (2018). *Computer-Based Training (CBT) - Training Industry*. [online] Available at: <https://www.trainingindustry.com/glossary/computer-based-training-cbt/> [Accessed 7 Feb. 2018].

Tran, H.X. (2014) The evolution of productivity in Vietnam’s manufacturing sector. Doctor of Philosophy thesis. *School of Accounting, Economics and Finance, University of Wollongong*.

Truss, C., Mankin, D. and Kelliher, C. (2010) Strategic Human Resource Management. *Human Resource Management*. Vol.14, No.2, pp.365 – 382. Available at: <http://usir.salford.ac.uk/9191/>

Turek, B. (2017) *What Are the Advantages of a Computer-Integrated Manufacturing System?*[online] Bizfluent. Available at: <https://bizfluent.com/info-8588811-advantages-computerintegrated-manufacturing-system.html> [Accessed 7 Feb. 2018].

Van Tuan, N. and Nguyen, M.N. (2012) Effects of Human Resource management on business performance of small and medium size manufacturers in Hanoi-Vietnam. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*. Vol.2, No.6, p.47.

Vard Vung Tau website. [online] Available at: <http://www.vard.com/products/pages/shipbuilding.aspx>[Accessed on 10 April 2017]

Vidal-Salazar, M.D., Cordon-Pozo, E. and Ferrón-Vilchez, V. (2012) Human resource management and developing proactive environmental strategies: The influence of environmental training and organizational learning. *Human Resource Management*. Vol.51, No.6, pp.905-934.

Vui-Yee, K. (2015) The Impact of Strategic Human Resource Management on Employee Outcomes in Private and Public Limited Companies in Malaysia. *Journal of Human Values*. Vol.21, No.2, pp.75–86. Available at: <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-84942436319andpartnerID=tZOtx3y1>

Wallen, E.S. and Mulloy, K.B. (2006) Computer-based training for safety: comparing methods with older and younger workers. *Journal of safety research*. Vol.37, No.5, pp.461-467.

Wilson, J.P. (2014) International human resource development: Learning, education and training for individuals and organisations. *Development and Learning in Organizations*. Vol.28, No.2, pp 125-154.

World Bank (2016) Vietnam- Country at a glance. [online] Available at: <http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/vietnam/overview> [Accessed on 10 April 2017]

Yakaraju, G. (2015) *9 Challenges Faced by the Training Manager of Growing Companies*. [online] Custom Training and E-learning, Anywhere Anytime!. Available at: <https://blog.commlabindia.com/elearning-design/challenges-faced-by-training-manager> [Accessed 4 May 2018].

Yong, J.Y. and Mohd-Yusoff, Y. (2016) Studying the influence of strategic human resource competencies on the adoption of green human resource management practices. *Industrial and Commercial Training*. Vol.48, No.8, pp.416–422.

Zhu, Y. (2002) Economic Reform and Human Resource Management in Vietnam. *Asia Pacific Business Review*. Vol.8, No.3, pp.115-135.

Zide, J.S., Mills, M.J., Shahani-Denning, C. and Sweetapple, C. (2017) Work interruptions resiliency: toward an improved understanding of employee efficiency. *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*. Vol.4, No.1, pp.39-58.

Appendix 1- Survey Questionnaire

TRAINING EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Please complete this evaluation of the training you recently attended.

Your feedback on your experience is appreciated.

Name

Company

Position

1. Gender Male Female
2. Age
3. For how long have you been working with the organisation?

Less than 1 year
Between 1-3 years
Between 3-5 years
Between 5-7 years
Between 7-10 years
More than 10 years

4. Which department do you work with?

Production
Research and Development
Purchase
Marketing
Accounting and Finance
Others

5. What is the frequency of training program implemented in your organisation?

Once a year
Twice a year
5-6 times a year
Once in six months
Twice in six months
Every quarter
Every month
Anytime, according to need

6. Which training did you recently attend?

7. When did the training take place?
8. Who led the training?
9. What was the primary reason you participated in this training?

- New procedure
- New technology
- New to the Company
- Personal development
- Other (Please specify)

10. What kind of training is mostly imparted by your organisation?

On the job training
Off the job training
Both (On and Off the job)
Others

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements. Circle the number that best characterises how you feel about the statement, where 1=Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4= Agree, 5= Strongly Agree.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
11. The use of appropriate technology such as ICT (information and communications technology) is used to impart training?	1	2	3	4	5
12. Before designing the training program the HR managers/training department conducts an appropriate training need analysis (TNA)	1	2	3	4	5
13. The objectives of the training were clearly defined.	1	2	3	4	5
14. Participation and interaction were encouraged	1	2	3	4	5
15. The content was organized and easy to follow.	1	2	3	4	5
16. The training materials distributed were helpful.	1	2	3	4	5
17. The training I received is applicable to my work.	1	2	3	4	5

18. The trainer was knowledgeable about the training topics. 1 2 3 4 5
19. The trainer was well-prepared. 1 2 3 4 5
20. The training objectives were met. 1 2 3 4 5
21. The time allotted for the training is sufficient. 1 2 3 4 5
22. The training room and facilities were adequate and comfortable. 1 2 3 4 5
23. I feel comfortable sharing what I learned with co-workers. 1 2 3 4 5
24. The training you received has been effective in terms of knowledge enhancement and improving your skills and competencies? 1 2 3 4 5
25. Have you experienced improvement in your work performance after getting the necessary training? 1 2 3 4 5
26. Do you feel motivated each time after undergoing training session in the organization? 1 2 3 4 5

27. Would you recommend this training to others?

- Yes No

28. How do you feel you will implement this knowledge when returning to work?

- This training will directly help me with my work in the immediate future.
- This training will help me with my work but probably not for some time.
- This training will have no bearing on my work in the foreseeable future.

29. The organisation follows a systematic approach to training (SAT) to ensure that the participants/trainees get the best out of each training session?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly Disagree

30. The HR managers/training co-ordinators seek feedback from the trainees/participating employees regarding the appropriateness of training after every training session?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly Disagree

31. The feedback of the training program shared by the trainees/participants is valued and implemented in the subsequent training sessions for improvement?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly Disagree

32. You feel that the HR managers follow a participatory approach to training evaluation?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly Disagree

33. You feel empowered after evaluation of the training programs takes place?

Strongly Agree
Agree
Neutral
Disagree
Strongly Disagree

34. What did you like most about this training?

35. What aspects of the training could be improved?

36. Please rate your overall level of satisfaction with the trainer.

Very dissatisfied

- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

37. Please rate your overall level of satisfaction with the training program.

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neutral
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

Thank you for your feedback!

Appendix 2- Interview Questions for Managers

Q1) What are the current HR policies and practices associated with training programs in the organisation? Does the company carry out training needs analysis (TNA), if yes, how? Please elaborate.

Q2) What type of trainings is given to the employees across different levels? How does it contribute to organisational development? Please elaborate.

Q3) Is evaluation undertaken after every training? How often is training evaluation undertaken in the organisation? Please elaborate.

Q4) What models are used for evaluating the training program? Please elaborate.

Q5) What are the apparent benefits of undertaking the training evaluation? Which evaluative model is the most effective in terms of achieving such benefits? Please elaborate.

Q6) What are the challenges faced by the organisation in undertaking training evaluation? Please elaborate.